
FIRE UNDER THE LENS: THE MESOLITHIC MAGNIFIED

A STUDY INTO THE USE AND FUNCTION OF MESOLITHIC HEARTH PITS IN THE NETHERLANDS
THROUGH THE USE OF SOIL MICROMORPHOLOGY

Research Master's Thesis - Archaeology

Date: 12-09-2019

Name: Hester Kartini Kamstra

Student number: s2327910

Supervisors: Dr. J.H.M. (Hans) Peeters

Prof. dr. ir. D.J. (Hans) Huisman

University of Groningen, the Netherlands

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

A master's thesis is not written in an academic vacuum; I owe a debt of gratitude to everyone involved in the process of conducting my research. First of all, my sincere thanks to both of my supervisors: dr. Hans Peeters and prof. dr. Hans Huisman. My interest in the Mesolithic can be traced back to a first-year course on Dutch (early) prehistory, which was partially taught by dr. Peeters. Since then, I have been fortunate enough to learn more about early prehistory and flint technology under his supervision. Hans has, with his extensive knowledge and enthusiasm, managed to inspire me to explore the vast and complex world of prehistoric hunter-gatherers (and all the garbage they have left behind). Equally many thanks to prof. Huisman, for taking the time to teach me the ins and outs of soil micromorphology. Your avidity for the integration of micromorphological analysis in archaeology has been infectious; I am afraid I caught the 'geoarchaeology-bug' at my first sight of a thin section. Furthermore, thanks to both of you for sharing the same first name, making communication sometimes unnecessarily (but amusingly) complicated.

FIGURE 1: HANS (LEFT) AND HANS (RIGHT) STUDYING A SOIL PROFILE DURING FIELDWORK IN HEEZE (THE NETHERLANDS), 23RD OF APRIL 2019.

In addition, I wish to thank the ISRIC (International Soil Reference and Information Centre Wageningen) for allowing me to study the thin sections from Hoge Vaart-A27. Many thanks to Kirsten van Kappel (ArcheoPro), for lending me the thin sections from Dronnten-N23, even going so far as to hand me a missing thin section at the inaugural lecture of one of my supervisors. Thanks to Caroline Vermeeren (BIAX), Lucy Kubiak-Martens (BIAX) and Petra Doeve (BAAC) for providing their knowledge in the determination of charred organic tissue from Hoge Vaart (which turned out to be tree bark). Thanks to Mario van IJzendoorn (RCE), for showing me the art of thin section production. And thanks to Gert van Oortmerssen, for allowing me to use the microscope and photo equipment in your laboratory and for standing very still every time I had to take a picture.

To conclude, I wish to thank everyone that was not directly involved in the research, but contributed in their own way. To everyone in the Groningen Institute of Archaeology, students and staff alike, for being willing to proofread (parts of) the text, for listening to my complaints and for being great company alongside a cup of questionable tea.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Acknowledgements.....	2
List of figures and tables	5
1. Introduction.....	8
1.1 Problem definition	8
1.2 Research aims and research questions.....	11
1.3 Spatial and temporal framework	12
1.3.1 Chronological context.....	12
1.3.2 Palaeogeographical context.....	11
1.4 Outline of the study.....	15
2. Theoretical framework.....	16
2.1 Theory on Mesolithic hearth pits.....	16
2.1.1 Thinking about the Mesolithic	16
2.1.2 Thinking about hearth pits.....	18
2.2 Previous research on hearth pits in the Netherlands.....	21
2.2.1 Chronological and spatial patterning.....	21
2.2.2 Functional interpretations	24
2.3 Interpretative framework.....	31
2.3.1 Scale, measurement and observation.....	31
2.3.2 Interpretative framework.....	33
3. Materials and methods.....	35
3.1 Site description	35
3.1.1 Dronten-N23	35
3.1.2 Hoge Vaart-A27.....	37
3.1.3 Kampen.....	39
thin sections	41
4. Micromorphological Results.....	44
4.1 Dronten	44
4.1.1 HAK-A-572	44
4.1.2 HAK-B-32.....	45
4.1.3 HAK-B-62.....	45
4.2 Hoge Vaart-A27	46
4.2.1 51-914.....	46
4.2.2 51-904.....	47
4.2.3 131-902.....	47
4.3 Kampen	49
4.3.1 22	49

4.3.2 26	49
4.3.3 27	50
4.3.4 75	50
5. Interpretation of results	59
5.1 Identifying heterogeneity	59
5.1.1 Irregularity/lack of internal stratigraphy	59
5.1.2 Presence of voids/concentrations of charred material	60
5.1.3 Extent of charcoal fragmentation.	60
5.2 Charred organic constituents	63
5.2.1 Degree of charring (brown charcoal)	62
5.2.2 Wood charcoal species determination	64
5.2.3 Identification of bark	64
5.2.4 Amorphous organic combustion remains	65
Opaque viscous (vesicular) fragments	65
Charred humus (or moder)	68
5.3 Top part of hearth pit features	69
5.4 Taphonomy/diagenesis	69
5.4.1 Bioturbation	70
5.4.2 Pyrite formation	70
5.4.3 Absence of ash	71
5.5 Other remarks	72
6. Discussion	73
6.1 Identifying variation	73
6.2 Hearth pit use and function: examining existing hypotheses	74
6.2.1 Ants: a non-human agent	75
6.2.2 Tar production	77
6.2.3 Cooking-related practices	78
6.3 Implications for hunter-gatherer studies	81
6.4 The Micromorphological method in Mesolithic archaeology	82
6.4.2 Suggestions for future research	83
7. Conclusions	85
References	86
Appendix I	97

LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES

COVER IMAGE: ARTISTIC IMPRESSION OF HEARTH PITS AND CHARRED CONTENTS (PERSONAL ILLUSTRATION: INK, CHARCOAL AND WATERCOLOR ON PAPER).

FIGURE 1: HANS (LEFT) AND HANS (RIGHT) STUDYING A SOIL PROFILE DURING FIELDWORK IN HEEZE (THE NETHERLANDS), 23RD OF APRIL 2019.

FIGURE 2: MAP OF SITE LOCATIONS MENTIONED IN THE TEXT - 1. HEMPENS, 2. SCHEEMDERZWAAG, 3. NP3, 4. HOGE VAART-A27, 5. DRONTEN, 6. KAMPEN, 7. HATTEMERBROEK, 8. MARIËNBERG-SCHAAPSKOOI. (FIGURE BY: H. KAMSTRA)

FIGURE 3: OVERVIEW OF A RANGE OF HEARTH PITS., VARYING IN SHAPE, SIZE AND LOCATION. NO. 1-6 DRONTEN N23 (HAMBURG & MÜLLER 2012), 7-9 HATTEMERBROEK (LOHOF ET AL. 2011), 10-12 HOGE VAART A27 (HOGESTIJN & PEETERS 2001), 13-14 KAMPEN (PICTURES BY: H. HUISMAN), 15 HEMPENS (HIELKEMA 2006).

FIGURE 4: SUM-PROBABILITY PLOT OF 756 RADIOCARBON DATED HEARTH PITS FROM THE NETHERLANDS. NOTICE THE CLEAR FLUCTUATION IN THE NUMBER OF DATES, WITH A RAPID DECREASE IN NUMBERS DURING THE EARLY ATLANTIC AND AT THE MIDDLE TO LATE ATLANTIC BOUNDARY. FROM: PEETERS & NIEKUS 2017, FIG. 4, P. 231.

FIGURE 5: PALAEOGEOGRAPHICAL DEVELOPMENTS IN THE NETHERLANDS THROUGHOUT THE LATE PALAEOOLITHIC AND THE MESOLITHIC PERIOD, IN RELATION TO OUR STUDY AREA AND CASE STUDIES: 1. HOGE VAART-A27, 2. DRONTEN, 3. KAMPEN. ADAPTED FROM: VOS, P. & S. DE VRIES 2013, 2E GENERATIE PALAEOGEOGRAFISCHE KAARTEN VAN NEDERLAND (VERSIE 2.0). DELTARES, UTRECHT.

FIGURE 6: THE INTERSECTION OF HEARTH PITS AS SHOWN BY PITS OF 'TYPE B' FROM DRONTEN, NOTICE THE REPRESENTATION OF THREE DIFFERENT INTERPRETATIONS OF THE SAME (COMBINATION OF) FEATURE(S). FROM: HAMBURG ET AL. 2012, 128 (FIG. 5.11).

FIGURE 7: PERCENTAGE OF DIFFERENT WOOD TYPES PRESENT IN HEARTH PITS FROM HATTEMERBROEK, DATING BETWEEN 6705-5175 CAL. BC. EACH COLUMN REPRESENTS ONE INDIVIDUAL HEARTH PIT. NOTE THE GENERAL DECREASE IN THE PRESENCE OF PINE DURING THE FIRST HALF OF THE 6TH MILLENIUM, IN ADDITION TO THE 'OUTLIERS' IN THE 7TH MILLENIUM - THREE PITS THAT CONTAIN SIGNIFICANTLY MORE OAK CHARCOAL IN A PERIOD WHEN PINE PREVAILED. FROM: BREIDER 2013, P. 22-23 (FIG. 3.1 & 3.2).

FIGURE 8: PERCENTAGE OF DIFFERENT WOOD TYPES PRESENT IN HEARTH PITS FROM HEMPENS, DATING BETWEEN 7080-6075 CAL. BC. EACH COLUMN REPRESENTS ONE INDIVIDUAL HEARTH PIT. NOTE THE GENERAL TREND OF DECREASING AMOUNTS OF PINE FROM CA. 6650 ONWARDS. NOTE ALSO THE APPARENT EXCEPTIONS TO THIS RULE, CONSISTING OF A HANDFUL OF PITS THAT CONTAIN A LARGE PERCENTAGE OF PINE IN A PERIOD WHEN OAK PREVAILS. FROM: BREIDER 2013, P. 28 (FIG. 3.6)

FIGURE 9: A SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF THE CONVERSION BETWEEN SCALES OF OBSERVATION AS SEEN IN RESEARCH ON MESOLITHIC HEARTH PITS.

FIGURE 10: THE DISTRIBUTION OF HEARTH PITS AT THE SITE OF DRONTEN. FROM: HAMBURG ET AL. 2012, FIG. 5.1 (P. 116)

FIGURE 11: PALAEOGEOGRAPHICAL DEVELOPMENTS HOGE VAART, ADAPTED FROM: PEETERS & HOGESTIJN 2001, FIG.. 65 (P. 162), FIG. 66 (P. 166), FIG. 67 (P. 172), FIG. 68 (P. 173) & FIG. 69 (P. 178).

FIGURE 12: DISTRIBUTION OF PITS (GREY) AND HEARTH PITS (OTHER COLORS) AT THE SITE OF KAMPEN. FROM: GEERTS ET AL. 2019, FIG. 9.14 (P. 222)

FIGURE 13: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE HAK-A-572 SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES.

FIGURE 14: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE HAK-B-32 SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES.

FIGURE 15: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE HAK-B-62 SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES.

FIGURE 16: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURES 51-914 (LEFT) AND 51-904 (RIGHT) SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE SAMPLES. ADAPTED FROM: SPEK ET AL. 2001, P. 99 (FIG. 10).

FIGURE 17: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE 131-902 SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE SAMPLES. ADAPTED FROM: SPEK ET AL. 2001, P. 101 (FIG. 13)

FIGURE 18: PROFILE SECTIONS OF PIT FEATURES (TOP TO BOTTOM) 22, 26 AND 27, SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES. FROM: HUISMAN ET AL. 2019, 3 (FIG. 4).

FIGURE 19: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE 75, SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES. FROM: HUISMAN ET AL. 2019, 3 (FIG. 3).

FIGURE 20: CONCENTRATIONS OF AMORPHOUS CHARRED ORGANIC MATERIAL, EMBEDDED IN VOID AND BETWEEN SURROUNDING QUARTZ GRAINS. A: SECTION 131-B (HOGE VAART), B: SECTION 131-E (HOGE VAART), C: SECTION 4063 (KAMPEN), D: SECTION 4266 (KAMPEN). PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL..

FIGURE 21: EXAMPLES OF CHARCOAL FRAGMENTS WITH SHARP FRAGMENTATION EDGES, POSSIBLY INDICATIVE OF REWORKING. A: SECTION 1727 (DRONTEN), B: SECTION 2182 (DRONTEN), C: SECTION 1247 (DRONTEN), D: NOTE THE SHARP BREAKS ARE LOCATED IN THE INTERNAL STRUCTURE OF THE FRAGMENT, SECTION 131-B (HOGE VAART). PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

FIGURE 22: REWORKED CHARCOAL FROM A WATER-LAIN DEPOSIT AT THE SITE OF LA QUINA (FRANCE). NOTE THE SHARP FRACTURES IN THE INTERNAL STRUCTURE OF THE CHARCOAL FRAGMENT. FROM: MENTZER 2014, 644 (FIG. 10).

FIGURE 23: INCOMPLETELY CHARRED TREE BARK (SECTION 51-II-D, HOGE VAART). NOTE THE 'LAMINATED' STRUCTURE OF ALTERNATING DARK BANDS AND BROWN TRANSLUCENT CELLS. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

FIGURE 24: WOOD CHARCOAL SPECIES DETERMINATION, A: POROUS HARDWOOD, FEATURE HAK-A-572 DRONTEN; B: CORYLUS AVELLANA, FEATURE HAK-B-32 DRONTEN; C: RING-POROUS HARDWOOD, FEATURE 51-914 HOGE

VAART; D: SOFTWOOD, FEATURE 26 KAMPEN; E: FEATURE 26 KAMPEN; F: PINUS SYLVESTRIS, FEATURE 27 KAMPEN. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

FIGURE 25: AMORPHOUS OPAQUE COMBUSTION REMAINS WITH A VESICULAR STRUCTURE: A. NOTE THE REMAINS OF THE CELL STRUCTURE OF PINE WOOD ON ONE SIDE OF THE FRAGMENT, FEATURE 27 KAMPEN (SECTION 4062); B. FEATURE 27 KAMPEN (SECTION 4062); C. FEATURE 51-914 HOGE VAART (SECTION 51-I-D); D. FEATURE 131-902 HOGE VAART (131-E).

FIGURE 26: AN EXAMPLE OF 'FAT DERIVED CHAR' ATTACHED TO A FRAGMENT OF WOOD CHARCOAL, FOUND IN A MESOLITHIC SHELL MIDDEN (POÇAS DE SÃO BENTO, PORTUGAL). FROM: DUARTE ET AL. 2019, 494 (FIG. 4A)

FIGURE 27: AN EXAMPLE OF 'FAT DERIVED CHAR' FROM AN IRON AGE OPEN AIR HEARTH (GREECE). NOTE THE LARGE VESICLES AND THE CRACKING (A SIGN OF DIAGENESIS) INDICATED BY THE RED ARROW. FROM: MALLOL ET AL. 2017, 305 (FIG. 31.2B)

FIGURE 28: CHARRED HUMUS AND HUMUS COATINGS. A: FEATURE 75, SECTION 4270 KAMPEN; B: FEATURE 131-902, SECTION 131-D HOGE VAART; C: FEATURE HAK-B-32, SECTION 1727 DRONTEN. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

FIGURE 29: DIFFERENT MICROSCOPIC INDICATIONS FOR BIOTURBATION, A: CIRCULAR DOMAIN WITH CONCENTRATED FRAGMENTS OF CHARRED ORGANIC TISSUE, SECTION 1247 DRONTEN; B: CIRCULAR DOMAIN POSSIBLY WITH CHARRED HUMUS CONCENTRATION, SECTION 131-E HOGE VAART; C: SLIGHTLY ELONGATED ROUNDED DOMAIN CONTAINING A CONCENTRATION OF CHARRED ORGANIC TISSUE, SECTION 2182 DRONTEN; D: BROWN 'CUT UP' ORGANIC TISSUE AND MICROFAUNA EXCREMENTS IN FRESH PLANT TISSUE, SECTION 4275-M KAMPEN. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

FIGURE 30: PYRITE FORMATION IN FRESH PLANT TISSUE. A: SECTION 4267, KAMPEN; B: SECTION 4268, KAMPEN. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

FIGURE 31: POSSIBLE INDICATION FOR ASH-RELATED DISPLACEMENT OF CLAY ILLUVIATION AND CHARCOAL DUST, KAMPEN (FEATURE 75). THE ORANGE ARROWS INDICATE DARK POWDERY CHARCOAL INSIDE THE CLAY COATINGS; THE YELLOW AND BLACK ARROWS INDICATE THE PRESENCE OF ILLUVIATED CLAY COATINGS (A: PPL, B: XPL).

FIGURE 32: AN EXPERIMENTAL PIT STRUCTURE USED FOR BIRCH BARK TAR PRODUCTION. FROM: GROOM ET AL. 2013, 57 (FIG. 8).

FIGURE 33: THE PRESENCE OF ROCK ELEMENTS IN PITS USED FOR THE COOKING OF PLANT- AND ANIMAL PRODUCTS. FROM: WANDSNIDER 1997, 21 (FIG. 5).

FIGURE 34: EXPERIMENTAL EXAMPLES OF STRUCTURES USED FOR THERMAL FLINT PREPARATION. FROM: MERCECA & HISCOCK 2008, 2637 (FIG. 3).

TABLE 1: A SUMMARY OF PUBLICATIONS DISCUSSING THE POSSIBILITY HUMAN ENVIRONMENTAL MODIFICATION DURING THE MESOLITHIC. NOTE THE RELATIVELY LOW NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS DENYING HUMAN IMPACT. + 'POSITIVE', - 'NEGATIVE', ± 'INCONCLUSIVE'

TABLE 2: FOUR TYPES OF HEARTH PITS THAT WERE IDENTIFIED AT THE SITE OF DRONTEN. A SIMILAR TYPOLOGY WAS USED AT THE RECENT EXCAVATION OF KAMPEN. FROM: HAMBURG ET AL. 2012, 115.

TABLE 3: AN OVERVIEW OF SPECIES PRESENT (AS BOTANICAL MACROREMAINS) IN HEARTH PITS FROM NP3, HOGE VAART-A27 AND HATTEMERBROEK. NOTE THE VARIETY IN LOCAL CONDITIONS REPRESENTED BY THE ECOLOGICAL NICHES OF THE DIFFERENT SPECIES. ADAPTED FROM: BREIDER 2013.

TABLE 4: AN OVERVIEW OF EVIDENCE FOR THE TEMPERATURES REACHED IN SEVERAL ARCHAEOLOGICAL HEARTH PITS. NOTE THAT TEMPERATURES NEVER MATCH OR EXCEED THOSE THAT ARE REQUIRED FOR (PRESENT-DAY) CHARCOAL PRODUCTION (CA. 900°C; KUBIAK-MARTENS ET AL. 2011)

TABLE 5: OVERVIEW OF SAMPLES AND SECTIONS CONSIDERED FOR ANALYSIS.

TABLE 6: OVERVIEW OF KEY MICROMORPHOLOGICAL OBSERVATIONS.

TABLE 7: AN OVERVIEW OF EVIDENCE FOR THE FOUR MAIN HYPOTHESES ON HEARTH PIT USE AND FUNCTION (BURNT ANT MOUNDS, TAR PRODUCTION, COOKING-RELATED PRACTICES AND THE THERMAL PREPARATION OF LITHICS).

FIGURE 2: MAP OF SITE LOCATIONS MENTIONED IN THE TEXT - 1. HEMPENS, 2. SCHEEMDERZWAAG, 3. NP3, 4. HOGE VAART-A27, 5. DRONTEN, 6. KAMPEN, 7. HATTEMERBROEK, 8. MARIËNBERG-SCHAAPSKOOI. (FIGURE BY: H. KAMSTRA)

1. INTRODUCTION

"Archaeologists arguably know a lot about the past."

- (Lucas 2018, 3)

It is hard to dispute Gavin Lucas' statement on archaeologists' comprehension of the past. While a supposed truism, we as archaeologists do indeed have the unique opportunity to gain insight into human life before the appearance of written text, a period which constitutes the majority of our existence as a species so far.

As a consequence of development-driven archaeological excavations, we are not lacking in the number of observations made. Not all prehistoric periods of human activity are equally represented in the material record, however, and our knowledge on different periods is thus not distributed equally either. There are still cases for which we have plenty of observations but lack adequate comprehension. In other words: we know a lot *of* these phenomena, but not enough *about* them.

One of these archaeological phenomena of which we have many examples but lack a solid interpretation, is that of *Mesolithic hearth pits* - the focus of the current study.

1.1 PROBLEM DEFINITION

While both the terms 'hearth pits' and 'pit hearths' have been used interchangeably to describe the same phenomenon, in this thesis only the former will be used from this point onwards. The reason for this relates to the interpretational implications of using either term; the expression 'pit hearths' emphasizes the functional aspect of the features as hearths, implying also that *in situ* fire must have been present at some point in time. The use of 'hearth pits', in contrast, stresses morphological characteristics observable in the field (i.e. a pit shape) and adds the connotation of 'hearth' as a less fundamental (though still important) aspect. This leaves room for a more detailed examination of the 'hearth' part of these features, and is thus more relevant for the current research.

Mesolithic hearth pits are a category of features that are generally U or bowl-shaped and have almost exclusively a rounded base. Their maximum diameter, though not always easy to determine macroscopically, rarely exceeds 1,5 m and the features are often not deeper than 1 m (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 227). The bottom of the features is characterized by a dark fill that often serves as the first sign of recognition in the field, and that contains charred organic material in various forms and fractions. This charred infill is the main reason the pits have until now been classified as *hearth pits*; while not all original elements associated with hearths are present (including charcoal, ashes and sometimes reddened subsoil; Karkanis & Goldberg 2018, 101), the combination of charred remains at the bottom of a pit does seem to indicate the intentional preparation of the feature. Mentzer (2014, 617) has suggested the alternative term "combustion feature" to cover both hearths as well as charred remains in secondary contexts due to human activity or natural processes.

The features are associated with a process of 'closed' heating, and it is likely that temperatures of somewhere between 200 and 500°C were reached within the pits (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 227). They are found in clusters of up to hundreds of features (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 232), and are rarely associated with settlement or campsite remains (Groenendijk 2004, 22-23). Moreover, some of these clusters have been found to represent a significant time-depth (from

Early to Late Mesolithic), while others appear to have been used during a relatively short time span. As such, the variability between and within sites is substantial.

Hearth pits have previously played an important role in Dutch Mesolithic research for a number of reasons: first of all, they are thought to provide a consistent source of study material because of their easily recognizable shape and generally good preservation as a result of being sealed soon after use (Groenendijk 2004, 22). Secondly, in terms of chronology, hearth-pits seem to have been used throughout a large part of the Mesolithic and each represent a short-lived firing event, thus being representative on a large chronological scale without losing temporal resolution (loc. cit). Thirdly and finally, hearth pits often contain a good amount of charred botanical remains from which we might reconstruct palaeoenvironmental conditions as well as possible activities related to subsistence (Groenendijk 2004, 22). These reasons, however, do not remain entirely unopposed.

Hearth pits are commonly found throughout the Mesolithic of the Netherlands, though our knowledge of their function remains limited. Although their suggested homogeneity (Groenendijk 1987, 85-88) has been contested on the basis of variability in shape and content (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 226), questions surrounding their function continue to exist. Possible functions have been identified on the basis of ethnographic information, but none of them are easily identifiable archaeologically (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 228). This is partially due to the fact that there are hardly any indications of flint working or food consumption in association with the features (op. cit. 227). The hypotheses regarding the possible use of the pits can broadly be categorized as follows: firstly, pits might have been used for roasting of nuts and/or other seeds. A second hypothesis considers pit hearths as having functioned as cooking pits for various types of (plant or animal) food. Thirdly, smoking and heating of hides, fish and thermopreparation of flint and stone is another potential use of pit hearths. A final proposed utilization of Mesolithic pits is for the production of tar from wood (pine, *Pinus*) and bark (birch, *Betula*), of which the use is known from hafted tools and lithic artefacts with tar residue (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 229). Crombé and others (2015) have, in contrast to the abovementioned hypotheses, questioned the predominantly anthropogenic interpretation of the pit features, suggesting an alternative natural origin instead: they argue that most of the features resemble (in morphology, distribution as well as content) burnt ant mounds (Crombé et al. 2015, 158).

As a consequence of this uncertainty, the search continues for archaeologically identifiable evidence that points towards one or more of these interpretations. This is where soil micromorphology can possibly be of use. Soil micromorphology concerns the use of microscopic techniques to study the nature of the components that form (undisturbed) sediments and soils (MacPhail et al. 1990). Human activities produce sediments that are unique in their combination of fabrics, stratigraphy and geometries within the body of anthropogenic deposition, thus enabling us to distinguish them from natural sediments by use of microscopic techniques (op. cit.; Karkanis & Goldberg 2018, 99).

Soil micromorphological research has a lot to add to the sparse remains from the Mesolithic that are found in unfavorable preservation conditions (such as encountered on the Dutch cover sand soils). Hearth features themselves are not often encountered in 'pristine' condition: unfortunately, the upper level of pit hearths is often missing because the features are only recognized at the lower charcoal-rich level (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 228). As for the charcoal

FIGURE 3: OVERVIEW OF A RANGE OF HEARTH PITS., VARYING IN SHAPE, SIZE AND LOCATION. NO. 1-6 DRONTEN N23 (HAMBURG & MÜLLER 2012), 7-9 HATTEMERBROEK (LOHOF ET AL. 2011), 10-12 HOGE VAART A27 (HOGESTIJN & PEETERS 2001), 13-14 KAMPEN (PICTURES BY: H. HUISMAN), 15 HEMPENS (HIELKEMA 2006).

concentrations themselves, they range in form from large recognizable chunks of charred logs and branches to finely dispersed charcoal dust in the soil matrix that leaves a grey to blackish hue (loc. cit.). In regard to evidence of in situ heating (and thus evidence of fire *within* the pits), this has been limited to sporadic identification of oxidation of iron and possibly the presence of cracked quartz grains as a result of thermal shock (Exaltus, 2001). However, cracked quartz grains are recognized in thin sections from various other features as well and are thus not inevitably related to exposure to high temperatures. They might even be the result of the thin section preparation process (H. Huisman, pers. comment). Moreover, the presence of organic

components such as animal or plant residues, as well as the identification of certain pedofeatures are, when considered in their proper context, good indicators of anthropogenic activity.

New micromorphological research on the use and function of hearth pits is strongly dependent on the availability of research matter, that is, on the availability of thin sections. For this reason the current study is limited to archaeological sites from which thin sections could readily be obtained. These are: Dronten, Kampen and Hoge Vaart-A27. The use of soil micromorphology in this research will thus hopefully add to our understanding of both the use and function of Mesolithic hearth pits, as well as our insight into the variability among these seemingly similar features.

The main question that has remained unanswered thus far and that needs to be a starting point for further interpretation, is whether we are looking at a micromorphologically uniform category of features. Are we dealing with a single, widespread phenomenon, or is there a number of separate practices that underlie the features we observe in the field?

1.2 RESEARCH AIMS AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The aims of this research are to gain insight into the use and function (and the possible variation within) of Mesolithic hearth pits in the Netherlands, to explore the use of soil micromorphology in providing additional data, as well as to reflect on the methodology used thus far to interpret the pit features.

Consequently, the main research question that is addressed in this thesis is as follows: *What was the use and function of hearth pit features dating to the Mesolithic period that are found consistently around the Netherlands?*

To come to an answer it is necessary to define a series of sub questions that each cover an important element of the research (interpretational background, the method of soil micromorphology and excavation practice). The sub questions that are thus considered, are the following:

1. How have Mesolithic hearth pits in the Netherlands/Northwestern Europe been interpreted in previous research?
2. How do the micromorphological characteristics observed in the thin sections from Kampen, Dronten and Hoge Vaart-A27 relate to earlier research and existing hypotheses regarding the use of, and variation among these pits?
 - 2.1 Are there indications for emptying of the pit, backfilling or redeposition?
 - 2.2 What are the characteristics of (any) charred/non-charred organic material observed in the thin sections?
 - 2.3 Is it possible to say anything (on the basis of micromorphological observations) about similarity and variability of features among the hearth pits?
3. To what extent do subsoil characteristics determine the archaeological recognizable shape and micromorphologically observable contents of the pit?
4. Prior to further research:
 - 4.1 What information might get lost when the tops of features are not recognized and subsequently removed in the field?
 - 4.2 Can our current sampling methods and strategies provide us with sufficient answers to future questions, or are methodological changes necessary to prevent us from stagnating in a cycle of asking and answering the same questions persistently?

1.3 SPATIAL AND TEMPORAL FRAMEWORK

1.3.1 CHRONOLOGICAL CONTEXT

The current study focuses on hearth pits dating to the period ranging between 9200-5000 cal. BC (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 225). The earliest dating pits fall within the Late Preboreal, and at the transition from Middle to Late Atlantic hearth pits almost completely disappear from the archaeological record (fig. 4). At the time of this study, more than 750 radiocarbon dates (of charcoal samples) from hearth pits are available (op. cit., 231). When plotting these dates against each other as remains of single events, there appears to be an interesting chronological pattern reflected in the frequency of pit occurrence through time: while the number of dates rises gradually during the Boreal (ca. 8200-7000 cal. BC; Peeters & Niekus 2017, 231; 9000-8000 BP; Peeters 2007, 61) numbers decrease significantly during the Early Atlantic (7000-6000 cal. BC; Peeters & Niekus 2017, 231; 8000-7000 BP; Peeters 2007a, 62), only to rise again in the Middle Atlantic (7000-6100 BP; Peeters 2007a, 63) after which the phenomenon slowly disappears altogether (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 231; fig. 4). Possible explanations behind this pattern will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 2 (2.2.2).

1.3.2 PALAEOGEOGRAPHICAL CONTEXT

To come to a better understanding of the pit features it is necessary to demarcate the geographic context within which Mesolithic communities in the Netherlands might have moved around, looked for resources and dug their hearth pits. Site-specific landscape developments for our case studies will be further explained in Chapter 3.

The general palaeogeographic picture at the onset of the Holocene is that of rapid temperature rise leading to a significant raise of the sea level; local groundwater levels, however, were less affected during this period

(Peeters 2007, 61). The increase in temperature made for the ideal landscape conditions for woodland species such as pine (*Pinus*) in higher zones, while willow (*Salix*) and sedges (*Carex*) thrived in lower-lying areas (Peeters 2007, 61; Bos et al. 2005, 280; Hoek 1997). Pine still prevailed as a species during the course of the Boreal, though the ongoing rising temperatures caused an increase in elm (*Ulmus*) and hazel (*Corylus*) (Peeters 2007, 61; Bos et al. 2006, 40; Woelders et al. 2016, 188).

During the Atlantic, wetland environments in the western part of what is now the Netherlands expanded as a result of sea level rise. The number of

pine trees decreased significantly due to the increasing inland groundwater levels, making place for oak (*Quercus*) and alder

FIGURE 4: SUM-PROBABILITY PLOT OF 756 RADIOCARBON DATED HEARTH PITS FROM THE NETHERLANDS. NOTICE THE CLEAR FLUCTUATION IN THE NUMBER OF DATES, WITH A RAPID DECREASE IN NUMBERS DURING THE EARLY ATLANTIC AND AT THE MIDDLE TO LATE ATLANTIC BOUNDARY. FROM: PEETERS & NIEKUS 2017, FIG. 4, P. 231.

(*Alnus*), though pine was still somewhat prevalent on the nutritionally poorer sandy soils and among raised peat bogs (Peeters 2007, 63; Bos et al. 2005, 280; Woelders et al. 2016, 188). From the Late Atlantic onwards, the coastal landscape opened up as a result of increased tidal activity; at the same time, peat continued to form further inland and led to the expansion of large wetland areas. In time, the woodlands would be dominated by oak in both highlands as well as the lower marsh zones. River dunes that were once attractive locations for human occupation disappeared (the quickest in the river systems near the tidal inlets), and the sustained extension of environmental conditions associated with wetlands must have affected the possibilities for human exploitation of the landscape to a great scale (Peeters 2007, 61).

The distribution of hearth pits appears to be confined to higher sandy parts of the Mesolithic landscape, which for a large part consist of (but are not restricted to) river dunes that were formed during the Late Dryas and Late Glacial coversand plains that are located alongside river plains (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 230). This does not necessarily mean that pits were not dug in the loess soils that characterize the south-eastern part of the Netherlands; the absence of features in this case might be due to taphonomy, since the loess landscape has suffered severe surface erosion during the Early Holocene (loc. cit.). Moreover, even amongst river dunes there seems to be variation in the occurrence of hearths pits; while the pits are often encountered in the Flevoland Polders (Peeters 2007), they are less commonly found on river dunes in the Rhine-Meuse valley. An interesting observation in this regard is the fact that river dune formation might have continued well into the Early Holocene in the Rhine-Meuse valley, whereas we do not know whether this is the case for the Flevoland region (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 230). It was perhaps the high environmental dynamicity of the former region, or a different type of land use, that prevented the digging of hearth pits in this area.

The geographic area that is relevant for the current investigation encloses what is now known as the Northern part of the Flevopolder in addition to a small part of Overijssel that borders the Flevopolder to the East (fig. 5). This area was significantly affected by the gradual drowning of the landscape, thus limiting the locations suitable for habitation but at the same time increasing the variety of resources available to Mesolithic communities. Specific palaeogeographical developments for the case studies used in this thesis are described in more detail in Chapter 3 (3.1).

9000 BC

Holocene landscape

Coastal dunes

- Younger Dunes
- Older Dunes and coastal barrier ridges
- Beach plains and lower dune valleys

Land dunes

- Coversand areas

Inundated areas

- Tidal inlets and channels
- River plains and mudflats
- Salt marshes

Peat areas

- Peat

Anthropogenic areas

- Leveed tidal and fluvial areas
- Drained former lake areas

Permanently submerged

- Fluvial channels and lakes
- Coastal subtidal waters

Pleistocene landscape

- Periglacial valley incisions
- Pleistocene sand deposit, lower than 16m -NAP
- Pleistocene sand deposit, between 16-0m -NAP
- Pleistocene sand deposit, above 0m -NAP
- River dunes
- Ice-pushed morains
- Loess area
- Tertiary and older deposits

Symbols

- Outline Netherlands
- Province border
- Watercourses

5500 BC

FIGURE 5: PALAEOGEOGRAPHICAL DEVELOPMENTS IN THE NETHERLANDS THROUGHOUT THE LATE PALAEOOLITHIC AND THE MESOLITHIC PERIOD, IN RELATION TO OUR STUDY AREA AND CASE STUDIES: 1. HOGE VAART-A27, 2. DRONTEN, 3. KAMPEN. ADAPTED FROM: VOS, P. & S. DE VRIES 2013, 2E GENERATIE PALAEOGEOGRAFISCHE KAARTEN VAN NEDERLAND (VERSIE 2.0). DELTARES, UTRECHT.

1.4 OUTLINE OF THE STUDY

In this chapter an overview was given of the research problem, the research aims and questions of the study have been defined. The remainder of this thesis will be structured as follows: in the second chapter existing theory on the Mesolithic (2.1.1) and hearth pits (2.1.2) will be discussed, after which an overview is given on hearth pit research previously conducted in the Netherlands (2.2). Chapter two concludes with a consideration of scale and observation in archaeological research and an outline of the approach taken in this study (2.3). Chapter three provides the site descriptions (3.1) of Dronten (3.1.1), Hoge Vaart-A27 (3.1.2) and Kampen (3.1.3) and the selection of thin sections will be accounted for (3.2). In the fourth chapter the micromorphological results are summarized for Dronten (4.1), Hoge Vaart-A27 (4.2) and Kampen (4.3) respectively, on the basis of individual pit characteristics. Following this overview, the results are interpreted in chapter five according to the following four themes: identifying heterogeneity (5.1), the charred organic constituents (5.2), the top part of hearth pit features (5.3) and taphonomy/diagenesis (5.4). In the sixth and final chapter the micromorphological observations will be contextualized by considering the meaning of variation in the results (6.1), and through comparing existing literature on different use hypotheses with the results of the study (6.2). The implications of this contextualization for our perception of prehistoric hunter-gatherer behaviour is briefly highlighted in (6.3) and the thesis is ended with a reflection on the micromorphological method (6.4.1) and a number of recommendations for future research (6.4.2).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Both the Mesolithic period as well as Mesolithic hearth pits in particular have been discussed to a great extent in recent decades. The period as a whole is most often considered in the light of human-environment relationships and the agency of hunter-gatherers, while the pit features have been (especially in the case of the Netherlands) the subject of discussions on spatial patterning, site-use duration and structured activities. Moreover, hearth pits are not only structuring elements for Mesolithic communities in a spatial sense, but they serve an important role in structuring our knowledge and chronology of the Mesolithic period as well.

In this chapter we will gradually zoom in on the existing interpretations concerning Mesolithic hearth pits, starting with theoretical ideas about the Mesolithic as an archaeological concept, then moving on to an overview of earlier multidisciplinary research on the hearth pit features and concluding with a brief discussion on the role of scale and detail in archaeological (hearth pit) research. What will result is a theoretical framework from which we can continue further investigation.

2.1 THEORY ON MESOLITHIC HEARTH PITS

2.1.1 THINKING ABOUT THE MESOLITHIC

Originating in the late 19th century, the term *Mesolithic* was far from a well defined concept or period since its initial use. Research into the Stone Age had been fundamental for early archaeology (Czarnik 1976, 59), though it was originally broken down into two periods (i.e. the Palaeolithic and the Neolithic) on the basis of technological characteristics, subsistence base and absolute chronology (op. cit. 60). This dichotomy subsequently implied some sort of conceptual 'hiatus' between both periods. It was only in 1893 that J. Allen Brown first argued for *continuity* in human prehistory, suggesting the addition of an intermediate period between the Palaeolithic and the Neolithic to account for stone implements that showed 'transitional' characteristics. From then onwards the term Mesolithic was used to describe what was then thought to be a period of cultural descent and deterioration (Price 1987, 227; Spikins 2008, 2). It is important to keep in mind that the Mesolithic was thus *negatively* defined; both as a period of negative developments as well as one lacking characteristics from preceding and succeeding periods.

One of the ideas central to much of the Mesolithic debate concerns the way in which humans dealt with rapidly changing environmental conditions during the end of the Pleistocene. While environmental changes vary on a local scale, the general picture is that of increasing sea (and water table) levels from the Late Glacial/Early Holocene transition onwards due to the increase in temperature following the Weichselian glaciation (Crombé et al. 2011). It is thought that populations responded to this change by altering their land use and mobility patterns; while traditional Mesolithic research has framed these responses in terms of linear development of complexity and the intensification of land use, more recent investigations have argued for varying responses to environmental change on a regional scale (loc. cit.). The term 'Epipalaeolithic' as an alternative descriptor for the Mesolithic is an obvious illustration of this strong relation to preceding environmental change, the term still being used in recent research (Spikins 2008, 4). Early theories on human-environment relationships of hunter-gatherers were connected to notions about 'stages of civilization'; social groups represented the lower stages were thought to lack the capability to actively transform their environment and thus their behaviour was *determined* by their surroundings (Spikins 2008, 2; Coughlan 2015, 706). This is well illustrated by Gordon Childe's description of Mesolithic societies being caught in a "state of helpless barbarism" (1925, 1). The idea of passive adaptation to new environmental conditions was, however, mainly expounded alongside the appearance of New Archaeology (Meier 2012,

505; Trigger 1989). Even when the origins of social complexity were started to be sought in Mesolithic contexts, theories on social change and so-called 'complex' societies were still based on environmental determinism and passive adaptation (Spikins 2008, 4).

Other research into the Mesolithic has, in contrast to the environmental investigations, been occupied with labelling lithic typologies and technologies as well as site-types. Functional site-type labels such as 'hunting camps', 'base camps' and 'aggregation camps' are heavily ingrained in prehistoric hunter-gatherer research (Peeters 2007, 695). Issue has been taken by some over the assumption that hunter-gatherer behaviour is definable in such a way, arguing instead that material and occupational continuity is not necessarily reflective of behavioural continuity and that Mesolithic culture and -behaviour might be much more variable than our 'hard' dates and labels suggest (Peeters 2007; Spikins 1999; Grøn et al. 2002; Preston & Kador 2018, 325-326). This dynamicity is thought to be directly related to that of past environments, though here the role of Mesolithic man is not that of passive adaptation, but of active symbiosis.

In more recent years, a great proportion of Mesolithic research has for an increasing part focused on human-environment interaction (as opposed to typology and technology), covering topics such as subsistence, environmental impact and hunter-gatherer mobility (Preston & Kador 2018; Garvey & Bettinger 2014). Moreover, there has been a tendency to move away from type-site based syntheses and to focus instead on a more landscape oriented perspective. Important Mesolithic sites such as Star Carr (Milner et al. 2018a; Milner et al. 2018b; Taylor et al. 2019) and Lepenski Vir (Borić 2002; Bonsall et al. 2008) in a European context, and Hoge Vaart-A27 (Hogestijn & Peeters 2001) and Hardinxveld-Giessendam (Louwe Kooijmans et al. 2001a; Louwe Kooijmans et al. 2001b) in the Netherlands specifically, are still referred to in the light of new discoveries, but there has been more room for syntheses on a broader landscape-based scale. As such, it has become clear that the variability among archaeological sites with a Mesolithic origin is significant and a topic worthy of research in itself.

Recent discussion on the interaction between humans and their environment can broadly be divided into two main stances; those arguing *for* and those that argue *against* the evidence for large-scale anthropogenic modification of the natural surroundings in the Mesolithic. In publication, many authors acknowledge the occurrence of vegetation clearance and deliberate environmental modification on a very local scale (see Table 2) but the firing of (British) woodland on a very large scale as argued by some (Innes & Blackford 2003; Simmons & Innes 1987, Innes et al. 2013) is not as apparent throughout Europe. The discussion is based mainly on the presence or absence of microcharcoal and the sudden decrease or rise of species in pollen spectra; small-scale phenomena that are distributed over a larger area. Taking either stance in the debate has important implications for the way human behaviour (and intentionality) is considered for Mesolithic hunter-gatherers. Arguments against environmental modification presuppose a more passively adaptive role for Mesolithic people, while those arguing for intentional alteration of the landscape imply that hunter-gatherers, though mobile, valued the investment of time and energy in resource management (and were thus capable of doing so).

Author	Conclusion	Opinion on active environmental management
Bell et al. 2009	Coastal environmental manipulation with fire	+
Bush 1988	Human intervention in post-glacial vegetation succession	+
Brown 1997	Opportunistic deforestation	±
Hörnberg et al. 2006	Detectable human impact on the environment, but effect of this impact on fire pattern was difficult to distinguish	±

Woldring et al. 2012	Small-scale forest clearance and burning of the local vegetation in Meerstad	+
Mason 2000	Fire used to manage acorn supply; earlier emphasis on vegetation clearances is misled	+
Bishop et al. 2015	Deliberate pruning of hazel or deliberate coppicing of hazel and oak during firewood collection	+
Bos et al. 2005	Burning of the reed swamp in Zutphen, possibly natural, maybe anthropogenic	±
Warren et al. 2014	Small scale woodland interference; though the extent of human interference is hard to establish and we should be cautionary in collecting, interpreting and presenting our data	±
Simmons 1975	Sporadic clearance of the forest by purposeful alteration of the vegetation, but hard to distinguish between deliberate forest removal or it being a by-product of other actions	±
Innes & Blackford 2003	Animal concentrations in Mesolithic post-fire areas, possibly pointing towards deliberate firing strategies to attract animals, proven by fungal data	+
Tolksdorf et al. 2013	Human activity may have had at least a local effect on the dune vegetation	±
Boyd & Kenworthy 1991	No indication of resource management at <i>Nethermills Farm</i> , pattern of wood use is explained as the response of a human community to local availability	-
On the possibility of firing woodland		
Macklin et al. 1999	Woodland declines in association with above-average charcoal concentrations	±
Bos & Urz 2003	Evidence of openings in the woodland canopy associated with records of elevated charcoal, disturbed vegetation and fungi	±
Woelders et al. 2016	Questionable whether fire activity was caused by human activity; very little human impact on the environment	-
Bennett et al. 1990	Charcoal is the result of low-intensity domestic fires; not enough evidence for large-scale clearance	±
Colombaroli 2008	Fire-based clearance around the Mesolithic-Neolithic transition	+
Moore 2000	Woodland removal and subsequent regeneration cannot be seen as solely the cause of human action	±
Grant et al. 2014	Important role of climate events (among which natural forest fires) on natural woodland structure dynamics, as opposed to only human influence	±
Innes et al. 2013	Identification of late Mesolithic woodland disturbance through firing, multiple small instances of burning designed to maximise resource benefits	+
Simmons & Innes 1987	Forest disturbance through fire is more probable of human origin than a result of natural causes	+

TABLE 1: A SUMMARY OF PUBLICATIONS DISCUSSING THE POSSIBILITY HUMAN ENVIRONMENTAL MODIFICATION DURING THE MESOLITHIC. NOTE THE RELATIVELY LOW NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS DENYING HUMAN IMPACT. + 'POSITIVE', - 'NEGATIVE', ± 'INCONCLUSIVE'

2.1.2 THINKING ABOUT HEARTH PITS

As is the case with the Mesolithic as a whole, specific research into hearth pit features falls within a wider research tradition as well, the features having been encountered and interpreted in numerous cases prior. Four distinct aspects of thinking about (hearth) pits will be considered in more detail below.

A first essential research question concerns the origin of the pit features. While the general consensus has been that the darkened bowl-shaped features are the result of human activity, Crombé et al. (2015) have recently raised doubts about this anthropogenic nature. They question the integrity of the 'hearth pits' and instead argue that the features resemble (in both morphology, distribution and content) the remains of burnt ant hills (Crombé et al. 2015, 158). If this hypothesis turned out to be true, it would have two significant consequences for future (Mesolithic) archaeology: first of all, there would be no need to focus on the detailed sampling and registration of the features, since they represent natural phenomena (op. cit. 169).

Furthermore, contents of the 'pits' would not be suitable for dating human occupation of the Mesolithic sites that the features belong to. Since the alternative sample sources for dating that the authors propose (i.e. the use of carbonized hazelnut shells or the sampling of surface hearths; Crombé et al. 2015, 169) are not readily available at every Mesolithic site, this would cause problems in constructing chronologies on both site-level as well as on a broader geographic scale.

Assuming that the hearth pits are anthropogenic in nature, however, a second point of debate relates to the formality in tradition (or randomness) of the pit shapes and fills. Identifying similarities and differences between objects and features, thinking about classifications and creating typologies are all processes that belong to the fundamentals of archaeological research. It is, however, important to question the validity and usefulness of these tendencies. Classifications are meaningful only when it is clear what purpose they were created for; it must be made explicit on what basis the data underlying a classification system are structured, and which conclusions can be drawn from the resulting system. While some archaeologists contend that the sizes and shapes of Mesolithic pits are difficult to classify because of post-depositional disturbance and taphonomy (Blinkhorn et al. 2017; Lawton-Matthews & Warren 2015; Fries et al. 2013), some recognize a surprising degree of uniformity among the features (Lohof et al. 2011, 138) and others have indeed attempted to create a site-based pit typology (Table 2; Geerts et al. 2019, 284; Hamburg et al. 2012).

TABLE 2: FOUR TYPES OF HEARTH PITS THAT WERE IDENTIFIED AT THE SITE OF DRONTEN. A SIMILAR TYPOLOGY WAS USED AT THE RECENT EXCAVATION OF KAMPEN. FROM: HAMBURG ET AL. 2012, 115.

Pit type	Description
HAK-A	Simple bowl-shaped pits containing a layer of charcoal dust at the bottom of an otherwise relatively clean fill.
HAK-B	Pits with a rectangular cross-section that contain a messy fill with large pieces of charcoal, possibly showing multiple phases of filling and clearing.
HAK-C	Small bowl-shaped pits that are circular in plane, surrounded by a thin layer of burnt sand and containing a messy fill.
HAK-X	Features that are still recognizable as hearth pits, but which have been disturbed or disappeared to such an extent that they cannot be placed in one of the abovementioned categories.

The Dronten typology, however, is already questioned in the same publication within it was proposed since the charcoal species composition does not appear to follow the same classification (Kooistra 2012, 386). This of course does not necessarily imply that the pit typology is useless or 'false', it simply shows that there are boundaries for its implementation. Alternatively, pits have been classified according to their date, as is the case in for instance the publication of Scheemderzwaag-Scheemda (Ilson 2013, 108). Apart from the recognition of some spatial and temporal patterns, it is not explained what meaning lies behind the pit classifications.

Thirdly, pits have also been considered in the light of structuring (social and domestic) space. While some authors do not think that pits (for storage, refuse or otherwise), are frequently

constructed by (mobile) hunter-gatherers (Crombé et al. 2012), such features dating to the Mesolithic period have nevertheless been recognized. The coastal site of Halsskov in Denmark revealed a number of shallow pits in a settlement context that contained wood charcoal, ashes, burnt clay and charred remains of parenchymatous tissue belonging to edible roots (Kubiak-Martens 2002, 23). Similar observations were made at a relatively permanent base camp found at Nethermills Farm (Scotland); amongst posthole features and flint scatters many pits were recognized that contained wood charcoal as well as charred hazelnut fragments (Boyd & Kenworthy 1991). It is, however, important to consider the possible circular argument that underlies the relation between Mesolithic settlements (i.e. largely permanent base camps) and pits; the presence of pits at a site might be the primary reason to classify it as a settlement, making 'Mesolithic pits in a settlement context' a tautology. A different but equally significant way in which pits might structure space is in the form of storage ("caching") units outside of settlement contexts. While direct evidence for storage is lacking for the Mesolithic period, indirect evidence and ethnographic data indicate the possibility of small-scale storage of resources in the form of *caches* that were located at multiple points along route ways (Cunningham 2011; Dunham 2000). Not only are these storage pits then *indicative* of structured space (e.g. routes), but they might also have served an *active role* in maintaining and recognizing these long-used route ways (loc. cit.).

Similar to pits, *hearths* and *fire* are often thought of as central in the structuring of social (domestic) space, though less so for the Mesolithic. Fire and combustion features are actively being discussed for (pre)Palaeolithic periods and Neanderthal sites (in relation to the active role and use of fire; Mallol et al. 2017, 324; Kedar & Barkai 2019), but for the Mesolithic this is hardly the case. Instead, the role of fire in the Mesolithic is more often considered in association with woodland disturbance and vegetation clearing/altering events (see Table 1). This might partly be due to the 'intermediate' nature of the Mesolithic, which lacks the fundamental focus on 'firsts' that is associated with earlier periods (e.g., the first use of fire) as well as with the succeeding Neolithic (e.g., the introduction of agriculture and the emergence of settlements). As a result, the focus on human-environment interaction and hunter-gatherer behaviour that is so heavily engrained in Mesolithic studies dictates the way in which we look at hearths in this period. It might also be the relative lack of definitive domestic contexts, however, that causes Mesolithic fire use to be rarely considered in terms of structuring social space.

A final issue that is brought up in the publication of hearth pits concerns the methodological issues that relate to excavation practices and the recognition of features in the field. In Ireland and England, excavation circumstances appear to have had a direct effect on the chance of identifying pits; developer-led fieldwork has, in recent years, caused an increase in the likelihood of hearth pits being found (Blinkhorn et al. 2017, 212). Since this type of infrastructure development requires exposing large areas during excavation, many more pits have been identified than would have been the case with smaller research-oriented projects. Consequently, it is now unavoidable to take the presence of hearth pits seriously (Lawton-Matthews & Warren 2015, 143-144). A similar situation can be observed in France, where both academic- and development-driven excavations have brought to light the presence of (quite uniform) Mesolithic pits all throughout the country (see for example Marchand 2017; Granai & Achard-Corompt 2017; Wattez et al. 2017; Achard-Corompt et al. 2017).

The process of recognizing hearth pits, or any burnt structure really, is nonetheless not as straightforward as it may appear. Careful interpretations in the field related to for instance colour, can form the basis for misinformed interpretations. For example, reddening ('rubification') of the subsoil has often been quoted as major evidence for the presence of prehistoric hearths, but various studies have revealed this line of evidence to be unfounded in many cases (Karkanias & Goldberg 2018, 100; Goldberg et al. 2001; Stahlschmidt et al. 2015b). While soil reddening is indeed sometimes the result of fire (though only affecting a thin layer of the substrate), the red colour can also be produced by diagenetic processes long after initial

sedimentation such as the dissolution of iron (hydr)oxides followed by the incorporation into clay coatings (Huisman et al. 2012, 999; Karkanas & Goldberg 2018, 100). The presence of reddened soil should thus not be taken as primary evidence for hearth features, nor should the absence of soil rubification serve as an argument *against* the presence of such features (as is for instance done by Crombé et al. 2015).

Similar issues arise with the (lack of) identification of ashes in hearths. Ash is the product of total combustion of organic matter and the recognition of ash (layers) is consequently brought up as evidence for *in situ* fire under well oxidized conditions. The absence of ashes in a supposed hearth feature (identified by the presence of charred organic material) however, does not necessarily mean that fire was not originally present. In acidic conditions ashes are instable and prone to dissolving, thus leaving no traces of the presence of a hearth (apart from the presence of other burnt materials such as charcoal; Karkanas & Goldberg 2018, 104).

As such, geoarchaeological assessment (including soil micromorphology) ought to be an important part of investigation into the presence and nature of hearth pit features. The disparity between field observations and microscopic study is well illustrated by research done by P. Woodman (1985), who concluded that soil samples from seemingly homogenous pit fills may have had possible different origins or, in contrast, apparently different fills being very much alike (Blinkhorn et al. 2017, 215). This revision of initial observations might have consequences for publications that identified (a lack of) internal stratification in the pit features; while homogeneous fills are generally associated with deliberately filling the pits after one use (Verlinde & Newell 2006, 204; Crombé et al. 2012, 8) and layered fills are interpreted as the result of the features gradually filling up, a switch in observation from homogeneity to heterogeneity (and vice versa) will cause a change in the interpretation of the use of hearth pits.

A multitude of theoretical entries into the research on hearth pits has been discussed above. How does the corpus of research on Dutch hearth pits fit in this theoretical framework?

2.2 PREVIOUS RESEARCH ON HEARTH PITS IN THE NETHERLANDS

It is important to consider the different branches of research that have previously dealt with Mesolithic hearth pits in the Netherlands, for all their individual conclusions add to our knowledge of this phenomenon. Research thus far can be broadly split up into two categories: those investigations that deal with the chronological and spatial patterning of the features, and those that are concerned with the functional interpretation of hearth pits. A brief overview of the existing data will be given according to these categories.

2.2.1 CHRONOLOGICAL AND SPATIAL PATTERNING

CHRONOLOGY

A significant part of hearth pit research has focused on dating the features to place them within a chronological context. This is mainly related to the fact that charcoal samples from hearth pits are considered by many to be very suitable material for ¹⁴C-dating for the following reasons: 1. a supposed lack of reworking within the features that points to a short use-time and thus a narrow dating window, 2. limited risk of contamination due to the layer of charcoal lying well below the reach of most bioturbation and 3. restriction of the "old wood effect" as a result of branches being actively selected as fuel (Crombé et al. 2015, 160).

Dating charcoal retrieved from hearth pits is not without problems, however. Three main issues can be identified in relation to the use of charcoal from hearth pit contexts for dating Mesolithic occupation: first of all, there is the possibility of the admixture of 'intrusive' charcoal that is not

related to the original use phase of the hearth pit (Crombé et al. 2012, 8). Secondly, the resolution of the dates is not sufficiently large to determine the frequency and duration of use of the individual pits, even though this plays a significant role in the interpretation of these features. A third problem is related to the palimpsest character of Mesolithic sites (Groenendijk 2004, 25); it is difficult, if not impossible, to directly relate the dating of a single hearth pit to other find distributions and thus to specific periods of occupation. This is due to the fact that the sites with the largest number of dateable features have been visited repeatedly over a large amount of time, increasing the amount of anthropogenic indicators left behind but at the same time making it harder to distinguish between different 'visits'.

Alternative ways of dating a site, mainly by the use of typochronology, are however not a good solution for the charcoal-related issues. At the site of Scheemderzwaag-Scheemda, where both radiometric as well as typological dating of flint was carried out, resulting occupation dates differed significantly from each other (Ilson 2013, 96). A better way of dealing with problems related to carbon dating charcoal would be to select samples of carbonized hazelnut shells instead of wood charcoal, though this obviously is not a feasible method when such botanical macroremains are absent (Crombé et al. 2012).

A final important question to consider in the light of hearth pit chronology relates to the actual *meaning* of the dates obtained. What do single dates and chronological patterns actually tell us about Mesolithic human behaviour? Do they bear any weight in the light of the socio-cultural questions we want to answer? We need to elucidate and be aware of the differences in scale that are incorporated both in our data as well as in our research questions and aims (see also paragraph 2.3). For example, hunter-gatherer presence as reflected by the dates of Mesolithic hearth pits cannot give insight into population density; instead the dates equate to specific activities at particular moments in time (Peeters 2007b). Peeters and Niekus (2017) have suggested breaking down the dataset into smaller (geographical) units to come to grips with landscape dynamics on a scale that might have matched changing patterns of human behaviour (see also Peeters et al. 2017).

SPATIAL PATTERNING

On the level of individual sites archaeologists have tried to identify evidence for intra-site spatial and chronological patterning. Several types of spatial arrangements of pit hearths were distinguished by Niekus, which include 1) isolated pits, 2) pairs of features, 3) triangular arrangements, 4) square and polygonal configurations, 5) linear arrangements and 6) clusters without a clear internal structure (Niekus 2011, 19-20). Dense clusters appear to be present mainly throughout the later part of the Middle Mesolithic and the start of the Late Mesolithic, but most configurations can be found throughout the entire Mesolithic period (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 232).

In the excavation report of the *Hanzelijn tracé* (Hattemerbroek), four different spatial arrangements of hearth pits were identified on the basis of their distribution and size: 1) isolated pits, 2) small clustered distributions of pits ($N_{\text{pits}} < 7$), 3) relatively large distributions of pits with minimal clustering and 4) relatively large distributions of pits with a large degree of clustering (Lohof et al. 2011, 124) and similar configurations were recognized at the Northern German site of Oldenburg-Eversten (Fries et al. 2013).

As for explanations for the observed patterns, some place emphasis on spatial restrictions as a result of environmental characteristics. Groenendijk (2004, 22-23) observed that the pit features were systematically absent within the reach of shallow depressions on top of coversand dunes, suggesting that it was rainfall flooding the depressions that made these locations unsuitable for making fire. Large clusters of hearth pits, however, are quite possibly located in small areas that were especially suitable for digging pits and that were consequently (re)visited

by hunter-gatherers over a large period of time (Niekus 2011, 22; Lohof et al. 2011, 200). The areas might have been major focal points in the landscape for Mesolithic communities, structuring their movement across generations. Moreover, the presence of a natural (in the form of trees or bushes) or an anthropogenic barrier (such as a windscreen or a similar structure) might serve as an explanation for certain configurations of hearth pits (loc. cit.).

Another remarkable observation that concerns most sites with hearth pits, is the lack of intersecting features. Only one intersection between hearth pits was observed at NP3 (Veenkoloniën) on a total amount of 142 recognized features (Groenendijk 2004, 24) and intersecting pits were only observed very sporadically in the Hanzelijn project (Lohof et al. 2011, 200) and in Mariënberg-Schaapskooi (Verlinde & Newell 2006, 204). Important to acknowledge in the light of site variability, however, is that hearth pits (mainly of the site-specific 'type B') at Dronten *do* frequently intersect (fig. 6), sometimes in a linear fashion, which might be the result of the continuous long-term use of a small dune area for pit-digging activities (Hamburg et al. 2012, 145).

Groenendijk suggests that the lack of intersection is the result of the deliberate avoidance of existing hearth-pits, with Mesolithic people choosing empty territory for digging new pits instead (2004, 24). This implies that the older hearth pits may have been visible at the surface for a long time after their initial use and abandonment, which would be more likely in a situation where one site was visited repeatedly without long periods of absence in between (Lohof et al. 2011, 200; Fries et al. 2013, 104; Verlinde & Newell 2006, 204). Another possibility, however, is that the sediment proved to be 'unsuitable' (because of the intersection with an older feature, for instance) after a first few centimetres of digging; this small-impact event will be unrecognizable in the archaeological record.

FIGURE 6: THE INTERSECTION OF HEARTH PITS AS SHOWN BY PITS OF 'TYPE B' FROM DRONTEN, NOTICE THE REPRESENTATION OF THREE DIFFERENT INTERPRETATIONS OF THE SAME (COMBINATION OF) FEATURE(S). FROM: HAMBURG ET AL. 2012,128 (FIG. 5.11).

A final point of interest concerns the lack of evidence for occupation and habitation in direct association with the pit clusters; flint scatters are restricted to areas *outside* of the pit concentrations and locations with large amounts of settlement remains hardly ever contain hearth pits (Crombé 2015, 162)¹. One explanation for this restricted feature distribution is directly related to the possible use of the pits: the process of tar production releases a strong and noticeable smell that would not

¹ This issue has been also linked to incompatible chronologies; the dates of hearth pits on the one hand and settlement waste on the other hand do not line up (Peeters et al. 2001; Peeters 2009).

have been pleasant to live close to. Consequently, if the pits were indeed used to produce tar, the production might have been intentionally carried out at some distance from the closest camp or settlement (Kubiak-Martens et al. 2011, 497). This interpretation, however, is heavily based on modern (Western) perception of smell, on what smells 'bad' and on what are deemed 'pleasant' living conditions. Projecting perceptions such as these onto prehistoric behaviour and societies should be treated with great caution.

2.2.2 FUNCTIONAL INTERPRETATIONS

FIRST INVESTIGATIONS & EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH

The first publication on the use and function of Mesolithic hearth pits in the Netherlands appeared in 1987, within which Henny Groenendijk gave an overview of the observations that were made during several archaeological excavations in the Veenkoloniën (a south-eastern area of Groningen, the Netherlands) and related them to Late Palaeolithic occupation. The excavations revealed a fairly uncontaminated coversand landscape with concentrations of pit features located on the tops and slopes of the highest sand dunes, none of which were associated with flint scatters (Groenendijk 1987, 88). The hearth pits appeared to be remarkably homogeneous in shape and contents and thus formed a very suitable subject to study Mesolithic behaviour (loc. cit.). Two important general conclusions were drawn from the hearth pit data: first of all, the features appeared to occur strictly outside domestic areas. They do not include the (flint) waste normally associated with domestic hearths and the clustering of the concurrent features would be spatially impractical within a domestic setting (Groenendijk 1987, 98). Secondly, the most probable function of the features was suggested to be related to food processing activities (loc. cit.). In addition to these initial conclusions, a number of significant questions remained open for future research: it was unclear to what extent the subsoil determined the type of hearth that was used (Groenendijk 1987, 98) and reconstructing the pits and their function ought to be the objective of future study (op. cit. 99).

The article by Groenendijk made way for a series of further investigations and subsequent publications featuring Mesolithic hearth pits and -hearth pit clusters. In 2001 the results of the large-scale excavations at Hoge Vaart-27 were published in an extensive twenty-part volume. While the publication did not primarily focus on the recognition and interpretation of hearth pits, the features were broadly highlighted in the synthesis due to their large numbers. The authors recognized the infrequent presence of flint and bone around some pits, but they do not see any functional relation between the features and the scarce finds (Hogestijn & Peeters 2001, 36). It was acknowledged, however, that anthropogenic and biological activity have probably influenced the archaeological record to a great extent through the truncation of Mesolithic occupation surfaces. The authors suggested food processing to be the most likely function of the hearth pits, and differences in pit occurrence above and below the major river systems in the Netherlands might be the result of different cultural attitudes towards food processing between different Mesolithic communities (op. cit., 141).

Since 2001, multiple excavations have brought to light similar large concentrations of hearth pits that are highlighted in their subsequent reports (Dronten, Hamburg et al. 2012; Kampen, Geerts et al. 2019).

The most recent synthesis of hearth pit data (Peeters & Niekus 2017) features an extensive overview of related research in the Netherlands that covers function, geological and chronological distribution and behavioural context. In summary, shifting temporal and spatial patterns of hearth pit distribution are observed both on a regional level (over a long period) as well as on the level of individual sites, and configurations of contemporaneous hearth pits exist on the basis of a large amount of ¹⁴C-dates. Possible functions that are identified include roasting, cooking or smoking food, the production of tar as well as the heating and cracking of

flint and other stone. Similar to the 1987 paper by Groenendijk the authors finish with a series of suggestions for future research and the conclusion that there still remains a lot of work to be done (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 237).

In addition to the abovementioned research, very few small-scale experimental projects have been realized to aid hypotheses on the function of the hearth pits. In November 1986 John Smit and Henny Groenendijk reconstructed two types of Mesolithic hearth pits in an open area (since the pits were hardly ever associated with settlement remains) to search for their possible function: type A consisted of pits with a maximum diameter of 45cm at a similar depth and type B was 85cm in diameter at a depth of 40cm, both types having been recognized archaeologically (Groenendijk & Smit 1990, 215). The pits were dug by bare hand, with a piece of sandstone the size of a fist and with a pig's scapula. Both methods that included an additional tool proved to work well; a pit could easily be dug by one person in ca. 15 minutes (op cit. 217). In the pits of type A some effort was needed to ignite the fuel, but once the fire was started it was easily controllable and heat loss proved to be very gradual (Groenendijk & Smit 1990, 216). A maximum temperature of 850°C was reached in these pits, leaving an ash layer of ca. 5 cm thick as well as some sizeable pieces of charcoal (op. cit. 218). In contrast, the funnel-shaped pits of type B needed only little effort to ignite and a maximum temperature of 900°C was reached very quickly. Much more heat radiated from these pits, and only a few charcoal fragments were left after the fire died out (Groenendijk & Smit 1990, 218). The location of a soot layer and a crust of agglomerated sand were determined by the direction of the wind; soot was deposited at the leeward side of the pit, while the 'cemented' sediment occurred at the opposite side (op. cit. 216). No definitive conclusion on the function of the hearth pits was drawn, however; the authors suggested that multiple functions (including drying, smoking and roasting food as well as cracking stone) would have been possible and that more experimental research is necessary (Groenendijk & Smit 1990, 219).

ANTHRACOLOGY & ARCHAEOBOTANY

The charred organic contents of hearth pits have been the subject of investigation in many of the publications dealing with these features. Archaeobotanical and anthracological research are featured prominently in publications as a result of the general lack of artefacts associated with the pit features. Charcoal and other charred organic remains therefore provide important alternative data to aid in the interpretation of Mesolithic hearth pits. Moreover, the data can supplement the reconstruction of the palaeoenvironment as an addition to other palaeoecological research (such as palynology). Certain species occupy specific environmental niches, with a preference for either wet or dry, cool or warm, and dark or light local conditions. Compiling a list of species present in a hearth pit will therefore be, to a certain extent, a representation of a certain habitat.

The charcoal in hearth pits to a certain extent represents a one-off selection of wood to aid a specific goal; when a hearth surface is used more than once, charcoal fragments remaining from earlier firing are reduced to ashes and new charcoal is left from the most recent use of the hearth (Van Rijn & Kooistra 2001, 26). Anthracological investigation of material from sites such as Hoge Vaart-A27 (Van Rijn & Kooistra 2001; Visser et al. 2001), Scheemderzwaag-Scheemda (Ilson 2013), Dronten (Kooistra 2012), Hattemerbroek (Kooistra 2011) and Hempens (De Roller, 2006) has shown that firewood was deliberately selected in terms of species as well as material condition.

Observations at multiple sites have revealed that at least a significant part of the firewood was dead at the moment of collection: not only is the wood very porous, some fragments are also littered with fungal mycelia (Ilson 2013, 110; Kooistra 2012, 380-381). The collection of this type of (old) kindling does not appear to be species-related. Another indication for the intentional selection of firewood might be found in the exclusive use of certain tree parts (Van Rijn & Kooistra 2001, 18).

When looking at the patterns of firewood use on various sites throughout the Mesolithic, it can be concluded that earlier pits contain mostly pine (*Pinus*) and that this changes to a prevalence of oak (*Quercus*) from the middle Mesolithic onwards (figs. 7 & 8). This development

Hattermerbroek

FIGURE 7: PERCENTAGE OF DIFFERENT WOOD TYPES PRESENT IN HEARTH PITS FROM HATTEMERBROEK, DATING BETWEEN 6705-5175 CAL. BC. EACH COLUMN REPRESENTS ONE INDIVIDUAL HEARTH PIT. NOTE THE GENERAL DECREASE IN THE PRESENCE OF PINE DURING THE FIRST HALF OF THE 6TH MILLENIUM, IN ADDITION TO THE 'OUTLIERS' IN THE 7TH MILLENIUM - THREE PITS THAT CONTAIN SIGNIFICANTLY MORE OAK CHARCOAL IN A PERIOD WHEN PINE PREVAILED. FROM: BREIDER 2013, P. 22-23 (FIG. 3.1 & 3.2)

Hempens

FIGURE 8: PERCENTAGE OF DIFFERENT WOOD TYPES PRESENT IN HEARTH PITS FROM HEMPENS, DATING BETWEEN 7080-6075 CAL. BC. EACH COLUMN REPRESENTS ONE INDIVIDUAL HEARTH PIT. NOTE THE GENERAL TREND OF DECREASING AMOUNTS OF PINE FROM CA. 6650 ONWARDS. NOTE ALSO THE APPARENT EXCEPTIONS TO THIS RULE, CONSISTING OF A HANDFUL OF PITS THAT CONTAIN A LARGE PERCENTAGE OF PINE IN A PERIOD WHEN OAK PREVAILS. FROM: BREIDER 2013, P. 28 (FIG. 3.6)

TABLE 3: AN OVERVIEW OF SPECIES PRESENT (AS BOTANICAL MACROREMAINS) IN HEARTH PITS FROM NP3, HOGE VAART-A27 AND HATTEMERBROEK. NOTE THE VARIETY IN LOCAL CONDITIONS REPRESENTED BY THE ECOLOGICAL NICHES OF THE DIFFERENT SPECIES. ADAPTED FROM: BREIDER 2013.

Species	Common name	Environmental indicator	Site(s)
<i>Beta vulgaris ssp. maritima (L.) Arcangeli</i>	Sea beet	Moist, well-drained soils - no shade (<i>Online Atlas of the</i>	NP3

		<i>British and Irish Flora</i>)	
<i>Dryopteris filix-mas</i> (L.) Schott	Male fern	Shaded areas, in woodlands (Perry 1997)	NP3
<i>Equisetum</i>	Horsetail	Along rivers, wet soil in deciduous forest (<i>Online Atlas of the British and Irish Flora</i>)	NP3
<i>Hippuris vulgaris</i>	Common mare's-tail	Stagnant or slow streaming water (<i>Online Atlas of the British and Irish Flora</i>)	Hoge Vaart-A27
<i>Moehringia trinervia</i>	Apetalous sandwort	Dry nutrient poor soils in deciduous forest (<i>Online Atlas of the British and Irish Flora</i>)	Hoge Vaart-A27
<i>Monocotyledon</i> (cf. <i>Cyperaceae</i>)	Sedge (nutsedges)	Aquatic, in stagnant or slow streaming water (<i>Online Atlas of the British and Irish Flora</i>)	Hattermerbroek
<i>Nymphaea alba</i>	European white water lily	Stagnant or slow streaming water (<i>Online Atlas of the British and Irish Flora</i>)	Hoge Vaart-A27
<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	Eagle fern	In light deciduous forest, on moderately wet soil (<i>Online Atlas of the British and Irish Flora</i>)	Hattermerbroek
<i>Pteridophyta</i> (cf. <i>dryopteria</i>)	Fern (male fern?)	In light deciduous forest, on moderately wet soil (<i>Online Atlas of the British and Irish Flora</i>)	Hattermerbroek
<i>Scirpus</i>	Club-rush/deergrass	In water or at waterside (Perry 1997) In water or at waterside	NP3
<i>Typha</i>	Bulrush/cattail	Semi-waterplant, in water or at waterside (Perry 1997)	NP3

has been linked to large scale vegetation changes throughout the Holocene which are associated with increasing water levels and rewetting of the landscape; in contrast to pine, a species that thrives in dry sandy soils, oak is much better suited to the increasingly wet conditions (Lohof et al. 2011, 440;). Thus, the prevalence of certain species in the charcoal spectra is associated with

the presence and availability of these species in the area. Moreover, both pine as well as oak possess favourable properties in terms of their material characteristics; pine is relatively easy to ignite and contains a type of resin that might have been used as an adhesive (Van Rijn & Kooistra 2001, 27) while wood from oak is sturdy and creates a fire that will burn for a long time (op. cit. 23).

While the overall data do show distinct chronological patterns in the use of firewood species, information on the variability *between* (estimated) contemporary hearth pits is lost in this overview. Since part of the aim of the current research is to examine the extent of this variability, this is an important issue to consider; variation within our spectrum of data can possibly be related to questions regarding intentional behaviour (intentional selection of firewood) and, more broadly, to ideas on the influence of people on their environment and vice versa. At the site of Scheemderzwaag-Scheemda, for example, we see an example of material continuity instead of gradual change: the use of pine as a staple firewood species persists throughout the entire Mesolithic period, despite changes in vegetation (Ilson 2013, 112). This continuous prevalence of pine, however, is not necessarily mirrored in the pollen spectrum; pine must have been present locally, as is evidenced by the occurrence of pine cone scales in the hearth pits, though not to the extent that is suggested by the charcoal data (loc. cit.).

Individual 'outliers' amongst a fairly homogenous spectrum can be found in Dronten and Hattemerbroek (fig. 8), as well as in Hempens (fig. 7). At the site of Dronten, while pine is the dominant choice of firewood during the early Mesolithic, two hearth pits dating to this period show a different charcoal composition: both pit A-451 as well as pit A-206 stand out for oak makes up the majority of the charred remains. Since the number of charcoal fragments is very low and the remains are small in size, the prevalence of oak in these pits was thought to be the result of charcoal being displaced and thus ending up in a secondary fill (Kooistra 2012, 380). In a similar fashion, one pit dating to the latest occupation phase at Hattemerbroek (the middle Mesolithic period, ca. 7000-6450BC) contains two times more oak than pine; the exact opposite of the contents of all other pits dating to that period (Kooistra 2011, 487-488). It is, however, argued that this might be due pine being a less common species in this later period, since pine seems to have been deliberately selected in earlier periods despite the prevalence of oak from the Atlantic onwards (loc. cit.).

Species determination is not always possible due to either the extent of fragmentation of the charcoal, or because larger pieces of charcoal were sintered or otherwise structurally altered. However, both these 'destructive' processes provide us with valuable information regarding the use of hearth pits. In regards to fragmentation, larger charcoal fragments are associated with the material representing a primary context (which does not have to be *inside* of the pit), i.e. fire *in situ* (even more so when the charcoal is brown and very fragile), while a high degree of fragmentation reveals the possible displacement of primary pit fillings (Kooistra 2012, 380-381). Additionally, the presence of brown charcoal indicates burning at lower temperatures (possibly in a less oxygenated environment) while completely charred black charcoal generally points towards a higher burning temperature (Ilson 2013).

It is challenging to determine the species of the structurally modified fragments; at Hempens all determinable fragments proved to be pine, which is not surprising, considering the amount of pitch (pine resin) present in the wood would increase the chance of sintering (De Roller 2006, 170-174). Similar pieces of 'glassy' pine charcoal were found at Scheemderzwaag-Opdiep (Ilson 2013, 109), Hattemerbroek (Kooistra 2011, 489-490) and Dronten (Kubiak-Martens et al. 2012, 344-345; Kooistra 2012, 382). Because of its challenging morphology, additional chemical research on the glassy charred material has been carried out as well, in an attempt to reconstruct the processes underlying the formation of this material (see *SEM, geochemistry and micromorphology*).

Botanical remains other than wood have been encountered in a few instances, though they are certainly less abundant than their arboreal counterpart. Botanical evidence from hearth pits from the sites NP3 and S51 (Veenkoloniën, Groningen) was investigated by Perry (1997) in an attempt to reconstruct the use of plants by Mesolithic hunter-gatherers (see Table 3). Additional research on the sites (including new data from NP9) was done in 2002, which resulted in the identification of several fragments of parenchymatous tissue; soft plant tissue belonging to vegetative storage organs such as roots and tubers (Perry 2002). Hazelnut remains were recovered at all three sites, though they were very rare at NP3 and S51. In this case it seems that vegetative tissues were more abundant and more generally present than hazelnut shells (op. cit. 14). Similar research at Hattemerbroek, Hempens and Hoge Vaart-A27 has led to the identification of more parenchymatous tissue, as well as a number of other plant species that are indicative of a specific habitat (Table 3).

SEM, GEOCHEMISTRY & MICROMORPHOLOGY

A final category of research methods concerns those involved with *direct measurement* and *soil properties*. These methods have been implemented mainly to answer questions related to the contents of the hearth pits and the extent to which fire (or a different source of heat) was once present in the feature.

The techniques used to aid this research include: *scanning electron microscope (SEM) physicochemical analysis, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), electronic paramagnetic resonance (EPR), thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) and soil micromorphology.*

At Dronten, use was made of SEM to investigate the microscopic texture of the 'glassy' substances described earlier (see 2.2.4). It was found that all samples showed a somewhat porous structure, pointing towards the fact that the material was highly viscous at some point in time (Kubiak-Martens et al. 2012, 347)². Similar conclusions were drawn after SEM imaging of fragments coming from Hattemerbroek (Kubiak-Martens et al. 2011, 501). Furthermore, SEM was used by Perry (2002, 111) to examine the internal structure probable parenchymatous tissues from pit samples to aid his research into hunter-gatherer plant use (see 2.2.4). SEM was employed for similar purposes in the case of Hattemerbroek (Kubiak-Martens 2011, 469-470).

To investigate thermal degradation and the chemical composition of the glassy charred material, additional samples have been analyzed using FT-IR, GC-MS and EPR. FTIR-spectra for samples from Dronten, Hattemerbroek and Scheemderzwaag-Scheemda, for example, showed that the molecular structure of most glassy fragments were heavily degraded as a result of exposure to high temperatures (see Table 4). Additionally it was shown that the degree of thermal degradation of the organic compounds present in the soil increased towards the bottom of the hearth pit, though the charred organic material was quite unevenly dispersed through the fill (Kubiak-Martens et al. 2012, 352). In terms of micromorphological observations, we should also recognize the heterogeneous dispersal of this charred organic material. Moreover, researchers were able to link organic compounds (in the form of FTIR-spectra) in multiple hearth pits to several stages of destructive wood distillation as well as various stages of thermal wood tar degradation (op cit. 352-354).

² The viscous state of the material should not be confused with the phenomenon of vitrification, however. While the term 'vitrification' is used in multiple archaeological publications (McParland et al 2010; Marguerie & Hunot 2007) to describe a state of once-viscous charred material, the actual meaning of the term as used in mineralogy cannot be related to organic material and thus causes confusion and inconsequent vocabularies. It is relevant only in cases where substances have been transformed into *glass* (McParland et al. 2010, 2679), and though it is easy to see how the lumps of 'tar' might appear glass-like, this does not equate to an actual product of vitrification. In the current investigation the term is therefore avoided and, where necessary, replaced by adequate alternative descriptions.

An additional indication for the presence of (pine) wood tar was found in the GC-MS results of a sample from Dronten: results of the analysis revealed the presence of *retene*, a polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon that serves as a biomarker for the thermal degradation of pine during pyrolysis (Kubiak-Martens et al. 2012, 349). In other words, the fragment could be considered the heavier hydrocarbon fraction of pine tar (loc cit.). In contrast, GC-MS analysis of a sample from Hattemerbroek showed that it contained a derivative product of abietic acid - an organic compound that, while it is associated with pine resin, indicates a low reaction temperature or a short reaction period. Consequently, the sample could not be identified as 'proper' tar in this case; the organic compounds were only partially converted into tar and the sample therefore was interpreted as the result of *accidental* pine tar formation (Kubiak-Martens et al. 2011, 505).

Lastly, TGA provided some possible insight into the temperatures which were reached in the hearth pits and which led to the degradation of organic remains present in the soil (Table 4). While the measurements vary, they match the generally quite low temperatures reconstructed in the FTIR-analyses. The results from Scheemderzwaag-Scheemda are especially interesting in the light of micromorphological research, since they were interpreted as the consequence of the primary heat source being located elsewhere, not at the location of the soil samples (Ilson 2013 114-115). The presence of rubified soil or ashes in the vicinity of this soil sample (inside the pit) would thus not be expected

There are several possible explanations for the variations in temperature exposure observed at the different locations: samples might have been taken at different distances from the original primary heat source, thus representing part of a continuous heat spectrum that is similar for all locations. It is also possible that the different temperatures represent a difference in function between the hearth pits; this is not very likely, however, since the anaerobic conditions remain constant for each pit and the measurements show fairly low temperatures overall.

TABLE 4: AN OVERVIEW OF EVIDENCE FOR THE TEMPERATURES REACHED IN SEVERAL ARCHAEOLOGICAL HEARTH PITS. NOTE THAT TEMPERATURES NEVER MATCH OR EXCEED THOSE THAT ARE REQUIRED FOR (PRESENT-DAY) CHARCOAL PRODUCTION (CA. 900°C; KUBIAK-MARTENS ET AL. 2011)

Site	Type of analysis	Temperature reached	Reference
Dronten	FTIR - analysis of glassy charred material	Exceeding 200-400°C, but significantly lower than 900°C	Kubiak-Martens et al. 2012, 349
Hattemerbroek	FTIR - analysis of glassy charred material	Exceeding 200-400°C, but significantly lower than 900°C	Kubiak-Martens et al. 2011, 505
Scheemderzwaag-Scheemda	FTIR - analysis of glassy charred material	Exceeding 200-400 °C, but significantly lower than 900°C	Ilson 2013, 189
Dronten	TGA - analysis of soil organic matter	Exceeding 450°C	Kubiak-Martens et al. 2012, 354
Hattemerbroek	TGA - analysis of soil organic matter	Between 300-600°C	Kubiak-Martens et al. 2011, 505
Scheemderzwaag-Scheemda	TGA - analysis of soil organic matter	Not exceeding 265°C	Ilson 2013, 186

The results from the previous geochemical analyses can be summarized as follows: first of all, evidence for tar production in the form of 'glassy' black substances that contain retene corresponds with the observation that pits are found outside of settlement contexts (for reasons of smell and smoke). Moreover, temperatures that were reached in multiple pits did not match

or exceed the temperatures required for charcoal production, so it is unlikely that the hearth pits were used for this purpose. These temperatures were also too low to be representative of *in situ* fire, which suggests that the primary heat source was not located at the place of the soil samples (and thus probably not in the pit itself). All in all, evidence indicates a use of the features that required relatively low temperatures and which resulted in the formation of organic compounds associated with wood tar. This does not confirm or deny food- or tar-related hypotheses regarding hearth pit function, however.

Since hearth pits can be classified as soil features, a number of research methods relating specifically to soil characteristics have been applied in prior investigation. Of these methods, *soil micromorphology* has been used the earliest to help interpret ten deep hearth pits found at Hoge Vaart-A27 (Exaltus 2001). Since then, this method has been applied at multiple sites, including Dronten (Van Kappel & Exaltus 2012) and Kampen (Huisman et al. 2019; Van Kappel & Exaltus 2019). Questions that were asked prior to the analyses cover the possibility of the hearth pits being emptied, the way the pits have been filled or closed and the soil formation processes that have taken place after the pit was filled (Van Kappel & Exaltus 2012, 451). Following the research, the general conclusions that were drawn can be summarized as follows: 1. Remains of the original layered stratification that is expected of a hearth (sediment, ash, charred remains) have not been encountered. This is most likely the result of the features being used multiple times (Exaltus 2001, 34; Van Kappel & Exaltus 2012, 488). 2. There is evidence for the emptying of the pit after firing activities (Van Kappel & Exaltus 2012, 488; 494). 3. The pits have been filled deliberately after use, as is evidenced by a lack of sedimentation layers in the tops of the features (op. cit., 483). These existing interpretations are relevant for the micromorphological analysis in the current research in the following manner: the supposed re-use of features might be recognized as the heterogeneous dispersal of inclusions. We can also expect a lack of natural sedimentation in the features, as well as an absence of the stratification associated with intact combustion structures. What will differ radically from previous research, however, is the comparative approach taken in the current study: for the first time, thin sections from *multiple* sites are described and compared integrally.

2.3 INTERPRETATIVE FRAMEWORK

2.3.1 SCALE, MEASUREMENT AND OBSERVATION

To conclude this chapter, it is important to acknowledge that not all research into hearth pits operates on a similar scale of observation. Observations that are made at an excavation in the field, through a microscope lens or with the use of a mass-spectrometer do not only generate different *kinds* of data, but varying levels of *precision* and *accuracy* as well. It is therefore important to consider the implications of these different scales of observation in relation to interpretation, not only to be aware of possible methodological limitations, but to evaluate the dynamics *between* the scales as well - especially when they are integrated in a single narrative. What 'scale' relates to in this instance, is both inclusiveness (the scope of material that is measured and described) as well as resolution (the degree of detail that is observed) (Ramenofsky & Steffen 1998, 5). Of importance is the fact that these two components are inversely correlated; when the inclusiveness of research increases, for instance by moving up from chemical analyses to inferences about artefact categories, the resolution will inevitably decrease. Moreover, when the scale of research changes, the units by which the material is analyzed will change accordingly (loc. cit).

This conversion between scales of observation is especially evident in research on Mesolithic hearth pits (fig. 9). The initial recognition of pit features happens on the *macroscopic* scale; black or grey hues in the sediment are observed in the field and, in combination with the recognition of the location of this hue in a pit-like feature, the *inference* is made that the features

are supposed to be hearth pits. From there on, the association of macroscopic observation with further interpretation becomes difficult; processes of initial use and digging of the pits as well as associated postdepositional processes are hard to reconstruct by contemplation in the field alone.

Exactly at this point, where macroscopic observations do not suffice to provide answers, soil micromorphology proves to be a suitable tool to reach the scale of observation needed for answering these questions. Layers and phenomena that are observed in the field can be confirmed by looking first at the impregnated micromorphological sample blocks and then at the thin section as a whole, after which the individual layers can be studied at a microscopic level using increasing magnifications (MacPhail et al. 1990, 168). When field samples are studied at a microscopic scale straight away however, interpretational problems might occur, since the relationship between materials (and geological phenomena) is best observed at a series of varying scales (loc. cit.; Goldberg & Aldeias 2018, 273-274).

Moreover, when reassessing the micromorphological observations in the light of interpretations on a broader scale ('upscaling' the micromorphology as such) again a number of possible problems arise. First of all, we ought to consider to what extent we can generalize our microscopic observations and when this generalisation is in fact justified. In other words: can a few samples from *part* of one or two hearth pits tell us something about the use and function of *all* hearth pits within a certain location, and does this location then represent the even larger number of hearth pits from all known locations in the Netherlands? Here it is especially important to be aware of multiple stages of inference since they represent the process of 'bridging the gap' between different scales of observation. One chemical measurement of a tar-like substance does not equate to evidence for intentional tar production in the Mesolithic without these inferences.

For the current investigation the generalisation of micromorphological observations to a certain extent is not rejected altogether. Soil micromorphology is not the only level of research that deals with the 'problem' of scale; it comes into play in every stage of interpretation and inference that is associated with archaeological research. What is important, however, is to recognize the limitations of our observations and to choose appropriate entities of research to aid our knowledge of the Mesolithic period (Groenendijk 2004, 26). To explore both the possibilities as well as the limits of our morphological data, this thesis emphasizes the identification of *variability* within and between the features that have been selected for investigation. Archaeological deposits are by their nature heterogeneous and thin sections often reveal significant variability, so the use of soil micromorphology might actually be an especially suitable approach in the light of this emphasis on variation (Goldberg & Aldeias 2018, 271-272).

A final, practical, issue to consider is the importance of *integration* of the different scales used in the archaeological record. While the investigation of this record ideally would involve the integration of the macroscopic and microscopic records (Goldberg & Aldeias 2018), this is often not the case in practice. This problem relates directly to the way in which archaeological investigation is structured: it involves methods and epistemologies from the humanities (macroscopic focus), the natural sciences (microscopic focus) as well as the social sciences (macroscopic focus), each with their own specialists with specific approaches and diverse backgrounds. It is here between these scientific worlds that communication and solid integration continue to be insufficient (Weiner 2010). While it is not part of the focus of this thesis, this is a discussion that remains of importance in archaeology; the role micromorphology plays in Mesolithic research will therefore be reconsidered in the *Discussion*.

FIGURE 9: A SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF THE CONVERSION BETWEEN SCALES OF OBSERVATION AS SEEN IN RESEARCH ON MESOLITHIC HEARTH PITS.

2.3.2 INTERPRETATIVE FRAMEWORK

It is clear that the corpus of previous research on Mesolithic hearth pits has led to a number of important conclusions: pits were dug in dry sandy soil, often located near streams or bodies of water, and in environments that were ecologically diverse. The practice of pit digging appears to have been continuous for nearly a millennium, though the resolution of available carbon-dates does not allow for a clear picture of pit digging frequency. Anthracological and archaeobotanical evidence shows the rich local availability of resources, including different wood taxa and edible plant species. Geochemical analysis of the pit contents has shown the presence of (pine) wood tar, which indicates low-temperature, oxygen-poor conditions inside of the hearth pit. Similar analyses of the thermal degradation of organic sediment content have also led to the conclusion that the temperatures reached in the feature were too low to demonstrate fire *inside* of the pit, suggesting that a fire might have been located on top of (or near) the feature.

Still, there are no definitive indicators about the use and function of the hearth pits, regardless of the intensive research. The thorough investigations are almost always confine to the level of a single site, or even a single pit (in the case of geochemical analysis). The multitude of data and research entry points (ranging from the micro- to the macroscale) would provide a unique opportunity to thoroughly compare observations, exploring the variability within an archaeological phenomenon that has been treated as if it were homogenous.

Moreover, there has been the tendency to focus on structural explanations, treating the hearth pit as a feature that exists at present and had a function in the past. We must realize, however, that a pit structure as we archaeologically recognize it has come to life through digging, filling (either through natural sedimentation or anthropogenic action) and excavation (Marchand

2017, 131; Huisman & Deeben 2009, 151). This complex process is what underlies the hearth pit feature as we observe it; the end product of a series of events. Previous research has been partially unsuccessful in incorporating this coming-to-be of the features. Thus, in order to gain more insight into the use and function of Mesolithic hearth pits (i.e. the main aim of this study), a new approach is needed.

This new approach should focus on *comparative* and *qualitative* analysis of the features, by using existing data and in combination with new observations from multiple sites and features. Soil micromorphology provides an excellent tool to explore such an approach; comparing microscale observations that relate to soil formation processes, including anthropogenic activity, on an inter- and intrasite level will hopefully help to form a more complete picture of the hearth pit phenomenon. The aim is thus to use soil micromorphology as a tool to bridge the gap between scales of observation and to acknowledge the processes responsible for pit formation, enabling us to both draw conclusions on individual pit genesis as well as variability and patterning on a larger scale. Revisiting and comparing micromorphological samples from three large Mesolithic sites will allow for a comparative analysis of the pit contents, the relation between pits and subsoil characteristics, and the functionality of soil micromorphology in Mesolithic contexts.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To operationalize the new comparative approach to hearth pit analysis, three Mesolithic sites from the Netherlands were selected: Dronten-N23, Hoge Vaart-A27 and Kampen. These sites were found to be sufficiently comparable in a palaeo-ecological and -geological sense, making them especially suitable for inter- and intra-site analysis (and the search for possibly variability). Moreover, a large number of hearth pits were discovered at all three sites. Finally, for all three sites thin sections were readily available, enabling a complete focus on micromorphological analysis as opposed to thin section production.

To start this chapter, the selected sites will be described according to the following four subjects, which are all relevant for the interpretation of phenomena observed in the thin sections: 1. The general characteristics and spatiotemporal patterns of archaeological activity at the site, 2. The site prior to the first signs of occupation, 3. The situation during the period the pit-digging activities took place and 4. The site after human abandonment. Following these descriptions, information will be provided on the selection of the samples, and the production and analysis of the thin sections.

3.1 SITE DESCRIPTION

3.1.1 DRONTEN-N23

The archaeological site of Dronten (fig. 10) consists of a large accumulation of features related to hunter-gatherer activity on top of a Late Glacial coversand dune. A significant number of carbon dates shows that the location was occupied during the latest phase of the Dutch Early Mesolithic period to the Mesolithic-Neolithic transition (ca. 8300-5000 BC; Müller et al. 2012, 389). The local dating curve was based primarily on developments in the groundwater levels as well as direct (AMS) dating of the *Basisveen* peat horizon, and a site-specific typology of hearth pits was created for the purpose of distinguishing between possible use phases of the dune (Bouman & Bos 2012, 301).

The most notable features within the site are without doubt the hundreds of clustered hearth pits that are scattered over the entire dune. After sieving the contents of a large number of pits, it quite quickly became clear that the features yielded very little (if any) finds (Opbroek & Hamburg 2012, 118). No clear correlation was established between the depth, width and shape (in cross-section) of the pits (op. cit., 122). Hypotheses regarding the use and function of the various hearth pits were focused on the production of wood tar, resulting from the analysis of glass-like dark charred lumps that were found in several of the pits (Kubiak-Martens et al. 2012).

Prior to the first signs of occupation, the local landscape can be considered remarkably stable. From the start of the Holocene onwards, a peat layer (known as the 'Basisveen' formation) gradually developed on top of the Pleistocene coversand as a result of increasing sea levels (De Moor 2012, 66). At the same time, however, the top of the coversand remained undisturbed throughout a large part of the Holocene and was thus especially suitable for habitation. At the moment of initial occupation, and throughout the period of human presence at the site, peat formation continued. However, the impact on the coversand dune remained limited; rising groundwater table levels did not directly influence the occupational suitability of the site.

A small depression in the centre of the dune seems to have mainly influenced the location of the first human activity, since most of the archaeological finds were found on the higher spots as opposed to the central concavity, which contained almost no material (Wansleben & Laan

2012, 108). A diachronic and spatial analysis of the pit features has led to the conclusion that the dune was probably used from the Middle Mesolithic onwards, and that there appears to be a gradually developing preference for the southwest and southeast areas. In contrast, during the Late Mesolithic period only the south southwest zone was used (Opbroek & Hamburg 2012, 139). While the rising groundwater levels must have had some influence on location choice, it seems improbable that this was the sole reason for the preference of the southern area since other large parts of the dune were still suitable up until the disappearance of the hearth pits (op. cit., 145). Local vegetation as well as the prevalent wind direction would probably have been just as important in the selection of suitable locations. While the pits themselves contained little or no material remains, flint scatters were identified between the clusters of hearths. The two phenomena are both spatially as well as chronologically segregated, and are thus of limited relevance to each other's interpretation (Opbroek & Hamburg 2012, 139). Locations where the soil profile appeared to be disarranged or strongly mixed up, matched with the areas of the excavation that contained the highest density of hearth pits. The disturbance of the subsoil could therefore be related to anthropogenic activity (De Moor 2012, 82).

When the area was ultimately abandoned around 5300BC, the slow inundation and subsequent peat growth at the site continued (Bouman & Bos 2012, 335). Samples from one of the hearth pits showed a disturbed layer that was interpreted as being the result of the increasing groundwater levels: the subsoil was completely water saturated (and possibly even inundated). As a result, root growth and the movement of aquatic plants caused plant remains to mix with the sandy substrate (De Moor 2012, 78). The contents of the pits might thus have been relocated as well.

Observations of similarly dynamic environmental conditions were made in a number of soil profiles, in the form of multiple clean and white sand layers as well as the irregular appearance of the top of the coversand. The thin sand layers were most probably redeposited and 'washed clean'; during the excavation these layers were interpreted as rinsing sand deposits, and XRF measurements have shown that the white sand has a different composition than the 'in situ' quartz grains (De Moor 2012, 82). A final consequence of the complete inundation of the area is the lack of possible water movement within the subsoil. As a result, little to no transportation of iron and humus will have taken place during the time the area was water saturated (loc. cit.).

The developments described above are relevant for the interpretation of phenomena observed in the thin sections in the following manner: the lack of water movement within the subsoil after complete inundation will have prevented the transportation of iron and humus by groundwater fluctuations. Although the area is currently not inundated, we might thus observe only limited amounts of illuviated FeO, if any. Moreover, the erosion of the occupation surface on top of the pits will have caused an irregular appearance of horizon boundaries in the top of the features; only if the pits were filled already, however. If not, the erosion might have caused sedimentation to take place inside the open pits, which will be micromorphologically recognizable as horizontal layers of sediment. Finally, the movement of plants and root growth in the post-abandonment phase (up until present) might have caused the relocation of pit contents. This is important for the interpretation of thin sections, since the presence of charred tissue and charcoal in certain locations might not always be reflective of the original anthropogenic activity.

FIGURE 10: THE DISTRIBUTION OF HEARTH PITS AT THE SITE OF DRONTEN. FROM: HAMBURG ET AL. 2012, P. 116 (FIG. 5)

3.1.2 HOGE VAART-A27

From 1994 to 1997 an extensive excavation was carried out at the site of Hoge Vaart-A27. Following prior prospection by coring, an area covering 1700 m² was excavated in 0,5x0,5m squares (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001). The site, which is located on top of a coversand ridge, consists of a substantial amount of features, ranging from hearth pits and surface hearth to a number of basket traps. A large

collection of carbon dates indicate that the site was occupied between ca. 7800-5300BP (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 127). A number of different activity zones were identified within the site, on the basis of geomorphological characteristics as well as find distribution patterns. The largest concentrations of refuse (which consist of a homogenous mix of different types of material) appear to overlap with the main cluster of features, including post-holes and hearth pits (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 49). Though this main activity zone possible represents a palimpsest situation, the combination of qualitative and quantitative homogeneity seen in the occurrence frequency of both material- and artefact types seems to suggest that the area was used for a single activity (op. cit., 50). People might have revisited the site multiple times for the purpose of this specific activity. The majority of the hearth pits fall outside of this zone, however. Instead, they are mainly located on the western part of the coversand ridge, at a distance from the other occupation refuse (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 122).

While no definitive conclusions were drawn regarding the use of the hearth pits, the suggestion of (plant or animal) food preparation was put forward as a main hypothesis (op. cit., 37).

Prior to the first signs of occupation, the local landscape can be considered fairly stable; characterized as a 'subarctic parkland' (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 162), the area consisted of an aeolian coversand ridge formed during the Weichselien (70000-10000) flanked by a gully to the east. During the course of the Early Holocene, extensive birch- and pine forests developed on the higher coversand area, while the badly drained gully wetland enabled the growth of mesotrophic sedge bogs (loc cit.). The stream must have been of low dynamicity for peat formation to be possible, which emphasizes the stable character of the environment. Thin sections made for the purpose of landscape reconstruction show that a significant amount of sand was deposited in the bog during its growth. Combined with the recognition of brown humus coatings (which indicate minimally moist or dry conditions), this has led to the conclusion that some sediment must have eroded off of the coversand ridge (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 162).

As it turns out, the transition from coversand to wetland manifested as a fairly steep slope, with an approximate height difference of three meters (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 165). This must have been a striking visual contrast to the hunter-gatherers that first occupied the area in the Boreal/Early Atlantic period (ca. 6900-6500 cal. BC). Moreover, the transitional zone between dry woodland and open wetland would have been rich in (floral and faunal) resources and thus an attractive locale for habitation. The first hearth pits were dug during this early period of occupation, but little else is known about this phase (loc. cit.).

During the course of the Atlantic, groundwater levels in the area of Hoge Vaart became increasingly influenced by the rising (North) sea levels that affected the Dutch west coast (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 167). On the higher grounds, the Holocene pine and birch canopy was gradually replaced by deciduous forests dominated by linden and oak, while the bogs in the lower wetlands grew significantly (Spek et al. 2001, 26). It appears that, between ca. 7000 and 6100 BP, the site was part of the transitional border between these relatively dry and increasingly wet landscape zones. Again, multiple hearth pits were dug during the course of this occupational phase. Additional indicators of the type and intensity of the habitation are, however, scarce due to surface erosion (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 168).

While the increasing wetness of the landscape might have complicated long distance movement over land, the same changes would have caused an increase in ecological diversity, especially in wetland zones. Moreover, water-based travel might have served as an alternative mode of transport in the 'patchy' environment (op cit. 169).

Though occupation continues after 6100BP, the practice of hearth pit digging ceases to exist (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 176). The disappearance of this activity in the Hoge Vaart area is possibly connected to soil moisture levels, which increased in accordance with the continuously rising groundwater tables. This development might have hampered the use of hearth pits, ultimately resulting in the termination of this practice altogether.

The site was eventually abandoned around or after 5400BP (op. cit., 179). By this time, the coversand ridge had almost 'drowned' completely in the marshland, covering the settlement area (which had been gradually overgrown by reed) with clay and peat. In the period prior to the complete inundation, landscape developments are characterised by alternating phases of increased- and low dynamicity (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 174). Instances of flooding eroded the humic topsoil in the forested areas, which would have been deposited alongside sand after aquatic transportation. This process is probably responsible for the truncation of many of the hearth pits as well, a phenomenon which has been observed in thin sections. Other indicators of palaeogeographical changes include bleaching of the soil (caused by alternating reducing and oxidising conditions), thinly laminated sub-aquatic deposits consisting of alternating layers of white sand and black organic material, and large-scale peat formation (loc cit.).

The developments describe above are relevant for the interpretation of phenomena observed in the thin sections in the following manner: first of all, the features were dug into a coversand ridge (with an observable main fabric of quartz). The habitation surface at that time was partially covered in woodland, so the surface of pit-digging activity was possibly an original O-horizon. This might have caused an influx of organic tissue and humified remains into the pit, both during the digging as well as after use (if the feature was not immediately filled). Some of the charred organic contents might therefore reflect unintentional by-products of the use of the feature. Moreover, surface erosion of the Mesolithic occupation horizon might have led to the erosion of the top of the pit (if it was filled at the time), which would translate micromorphologically to an irregular transition between the top of the feature and a 'messy' appearance.

Flooding during the post-abandonment phase might have truncated some of the features as well, and alternating phases of oxidizing and reducing circumstances in the soil have possibly caused the transportation and deposition of FeO and the bleaching of sediment. To conclude, the

process of large-scale peat formation will probably be recognizable as a medium layer of horizontally oriented organic matter located on top of the feature

FIGURE 11: PALAEOGEOGRAPHICAL DEVELOPMENTS HOGE VAART, ADAPTED FROM: PEETERS & HOGESTIJN 2001, FIG. 65 (P. 162), FIG. 66 (P. 166), FIG. 67 (P. 172), FIG. 68 (P. 173) & FIG. 69 (P. 178).

3.1.3 KAMPEN

After a series of corings and test trenches, ADC Archeoprjecten excavated the site of Kampen (measuring ca. 1.8 ha) in preparation for the construction of a high water channel (Geerts et al. 2019, 15). The site consists mainly of multiple spreads of flint artefacts and more than 800 hearth pits on top of a coversand plateau along the western edge of the Oer-IJssel valley, bordering a large body of water (op. cit., 11). The area appears to have been occupied from the Early Mesolithic (based on flint typochronology) until ca. 6000 BC (based on carbon dates). A further significant discovery was that of a cluster of posthole features in an anthropogenic depression, which was interpreted as a Mesolithic hut structure. Since our knowledge about the use of space and habitation structures in the Mesolithic is limited, especially in the Netherlands, the identification of a hut among the numerous hearth pits is certainly important.

Only a partial relation could be recognized between the microrelief and the distribution of Mesolithic (pit) features. The spatial configuration of the hearth pits shows a number of different clusters, of which most are situated near the eastern part of the site.

Interestingly, intentional selection of pine for firewood appears to have taken place during the Early Atlantic; while other wood species must have been readily at hand, only pine was found in the hearth pits dating to this period. During the Late Atlantic, however, hardwood became the main source of fuel, which correlates with the availability of this wood type in this period (though one Late Atlantic feature was found to contain both pine and hardwood; Geerts et al.

2019, 284).

Three additional conclusions on the use and function of the hearth pits are worth mentioning: first of all, hazel seems to be actively avoided as a fuel source. While thousands of hazelnut shell fragments were discovered on the site, no hazel wood was found in the hearth pits. Secondly, only dead wood was used as fuel, regardless of species or period (loc. cit.). Finally, no definitive evidence for tar production was identified at Kampen. While multiple pits did contain the amorphous charred remains recognized as 'tar' in other research, these substances were mainly attached to knots and similar woody parts that are inherently less exposed to oxygen during heating. Combined with the fact that firing pine in a pit hearth will always be less oxygenated than in a surface hearth, the researchers concluded that the amorphous fragments were probably an accidental by-product of a different process (Geerts et al. 2019, 284).

When looking at landscape developments in the area, one can generally conclude that the landscape was stable in a geomorphological sense, but this does not necessarily mean that the environment was static: the largest changes would have taken place in the local vegetation (and thus in the *biotic* landscape; Geerts et al. 2019, 279). Prior to the first signs of occupation, the subsoil consisted of stratigraphic accumulations of aeolian sediment (on the coversand plateau) and Pleistocene riverine deposits (quartz sand and grit) in the river valley, that was crosscut by some small creeks (loc. cit.).

At the time of the occupation the transition from the coversand plateau to the river valley must still have been a remarkable morphological feature in the landscape. The 'meeting point' of two specific zones in the landscape, each with their particular ecological niche and thus a variety of exploitable natural resources, must have been an attractive location for Mesolithic hunter-gatherers (Huizer 2019, 43). The earliest hearth pits were dug between 7939-7601 BC, but not yet in huge quantities (Geerts et al. 2019, 280). Digging the hearth pits would have taken place on the higher coversand plateau where firewood was readily available, resulting in the disturbance of the Pleistocene topsoil. Interestingly, the use of the pits seems to be reflected in local pollen diagrams; woody vegetation decreased slightly and people created open areas. Additionally, multiple fire indicators (such as microcharcoal and *Pteridium aquilinum* or eagle fern, a plant species associated with the firing of woodland) were recognized outside of the pit features (Bos & Dijkshoorn 2019, 49).

While Kampen was not exempt from increasing temperatures and rising groundwater levels, significant inundation of the landscape only became an issue around the Iron Age, so geomorphologically the area actually appears to have been more stable than both Hoge Vaart and Dronten. (Geerts et al. 2019, 279) Similar ecological changes can be observed, however: open woodland that consisted predominantly of birch and pine slowly changed into more diverse and closed deciduous forest during the course of the Holocene. It is also during this period that a podzol was formed in the coversand (Huizer 2019, 40).

When the site was ultimately abandoned (around the start of the fifth millennium BC), the lack of human intervention resulted in woodland regeneration (which is again reflected by the pollen spectra; Geerts et al. 2019, 281). At the same time, the rising groundwater tables start to have an increasing effect on the local environment. According to the available sea-level curves and palaeogeographical data, the area around the dune starts to inundate slowly around 4000BC, while simultaneously being covered in peat (Huizer 2019, 40). The coversand area itself only comes under the influence of the peat growth 2500 years later, becoming completely covered by ca. 1000BC (Huizer 2019, 40). At some places within this peat layer, small deposits of alluviated coversand can be recognized; these are most probably the result of wave-erosion in open water, leading to the transportation of the eroded sediment. This hypothesis is further confirmed by the presence of layers of bleached ('clean') sand in the top of the coversand horizon (Huizer 2019, 37).

The developments describe above are relevant for the interpretation of phenomena observed in the thin sections in the following manner: the influence of dynamic aquatic systems has possibly led to the transportation of sediment from the top coversand and therefore the possible erosion of the top of the pit features. If the pits were not filled at the time, but still lay open, we might observe indications of natural sedimentation (small-scale horizontal layering of deposits). The formation of a podzol in the subsoil might have led to bleaching of horizons, including part of the pit fills, and the transportation of soil organic content. To conclude, the large-scale formation of peat will be recognizable as a layer of horizontally oriented strongly degraded organic tissue; as a result of continuing wave-based erosion, some layers of bleached (cover)sand might be present in this peat horizon.

FIGURE 12: DISTRIBUTION OF PITS (GREY) AND HEARTH PITS (OTHER COLORS) AT THE SITE OF KAMPEN. FROM: GEERTS ET AL. 2019, P. 222 (FIG. 914)

THIN SECTIONS

For the current study a selection of thin sections was made based primarily on the availability of already existing samples (Table 4). Sections from Hoge Vaart-A27, Kampen and Dronten were already produced prior to this study. In the case of Dronten, thin sections were produced by Kirsten van Kappel (ADC ArcheoProjecten) at the Cultural Heritage Agency (RCE) laboratory in Amersfoort (the Netherlands). The sections from Kampen were prepared at the same laboratory by Mario van IJzendoorn, and the samples from Hoge Vaart were produced by Dick Schreiber at the Staring Centrum laboratory in Wageningen (the Netherlands).

At Dronten, each sample core of 50x10cm yielded three sections of 15x3cm to get an overview of

a complete profile. The micromorphological samples (originally intended for geological and palaeo-ecological analysis) from Hoge Vaart measure 15x8cm and at Kampen standard Kubiena tins measuring 8x6cm were used. For the exact location of the samples in relation to their corresponding features, see Chapter 4 (*Micromorphological results*).

Samples from all four sites were sent to laboratories for standard thin section preparation, which involves impregnation with resin, sawing, gluing and polishing the remaining sections to a thickness of approximately 30µm. All samples were additionally exposed to gamma radiation to ensure the polyester resin set more quickly (Spek et al. 1999, 31).

All sections were studied at the Laboratory for Conservation & Material Studies (LCM) in Groningen with the use of a Zeiss Axioskop 40A polarizing microscope as well as with an additional *Leica* microscope at the Groningen Institute of Archaeology, under both plane-polarized (PPL) and cross-polarized (XPL) light and under various magnifications (from x20 up to x1000). Detailed photomicrographs of microscopic features were made using a mounted Nikon D7000 camera at the LCM and a mounted MRc5 digital camera at the RCE.

Micromorphological descriptions were made according to Stoops (2003), and species determination of the wood charcoal was (where possible) done according to Schweingrüber (1990). In the case of sections that had already been described previously for micromorphological studies (Dronten, Kampen) or palaeoecological investigation (Hoge Vaart-A27), existing reports were consulted *after* the current description to aid unbiased interpretation.

TABLE 5: OVERVIEW OF SAMPLES AND SECTIONS CONSIDERED FOR ANALYSIS.

Site	Feature	Labcode	AMS sample material	Age BP	Sigma	Cal. BC from	Cal. BC to	Associated thin sections
Hoge Vaart-A27	Pit 51-914	UTC-5709	Charcoal	7800	60	6690 6900	6500 6450	51-I-a 51-I-b 51-I-c 51-I-d
Hoge Vaart-A27	Pit 51-904	UTC-5708	Charcoal	6135	49	5210 5260	4950 4850	51-II-a 51-II-b 51-II-c 51-II-d
Hoge Vaart-A27	Pit 131-902	UTC-4623	Charcoal	6112	45	5210 5230	4860 4850	131-a 131-b 131-c 131-d 131-e 131-f
Dronten	HAK-A-572 (2181-2182)	GrA-52174	Charcoal			6066	5909	2181 2182
Dronten	HAK-B-32 (1727)	GrA-50723	charcoal, Salix twig			5842 5976	5670 5744	1727
Dronten	HAK-B-62 (1246-1247)	GrA-50729	Charcoal			5845	5669	1246 1247
Kampen	Pit 75	Poz-93493	Charcoal	6080	40	5206	4847	4265 4266 4267 4268 4269 4270 4271

								4272 4273 4274
Kampen	Pit 22	Poz-93498	Charcoal	7650	50	6595	6430	4263 4264
Kampen	Pit 26	Poz-93495	Charcoal	7720	50	6641	6467	4065 4066
Kampen	Pit 27	Poz-93496	Charcoal	7730	50	6644	6470	4062 4063

4. MICROMORPHOLOGICAL RESULTS

The following chapter provides an overview of the results from the micromorphological analysis for each individual hearth pit feature. The results are summarized in Table 6. Features are, where possible, described from bottom to top, as is the standard in soil micromorphology. The observations will be discussed according to their context and relation to the moment the pit (and its contents) came into existence (i.e. the moment of 'deposition'), which is either (I) pre-depositional, (II) at the moment of deposition, or (III) post-depositional. The descriptions as well as scans of each individual thin section are provided in Appendix I.

4.1 DRONTEN

4.1.1 FEATURE HAK-A-572

FIGURE 13: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE HAK-A-572 SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES.

I: The groundmass is primarily made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. The natural subsoil underneath the pit consists of relatively clean sand with little to no traces of organic matter.

II: The pit fill itself shows a sequence of layers containing different fractions and amounts of charred organic remains and wood charcoal. 1. The lowest horizon has a quite 'messy' appearance. A common organic fraction is present, including a few small (<1mm) charcoal particles, one larger charcoal fragment (8-9mm, brownish black) and fragments of charred plant tissue/charcoal dust. 2. The second layer appears quite clean in contrast, but contains a number of larger (>1cm) charcoal fragments (one of which is brownish black and rounded, while the others are black with sharp edges). 3. Layer three contains homogeneously dispersed smaller charred organic fragments (<1mm) and abundant charcoal dust (which is amorphous in character and is not microscopically recognizable as distinct 'bits', in contrast to small charcoal fragments). This layer is 'split' by a ca. 2cm thick 'cleaner' band of sediment that contains relatively less charred organic remains. 4. The top layer of the fill contains less charcoal dust than the lower layers. Its remaining organic fraction includes small (<1mm) rounded fragments of charred organic material.

III: Observations relating to post-depositional processes include: pyrite framboids, sclerotia, common domains associated with bioturbation, fragments of uncharred plant tissue, raw humus and light humus coatings. The top ±10cm of the soil profile that covers the top of the pit consists of a mix of amorphous horizontally oriented organic matter with some small bands of clean sand interspersed through this heavily organic layer.

4.1.2 FEATURE HAK-B-32

FIGURE 14: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE HAK-B-32 SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES.

I: The groundmass is primarily made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. The natural subsoil underneath the pit consists of relatively clean sand with a few traces of organic matter.

II: The pit appeared to be 'layered' in the field, showing a sequence of alternating light grey and darker grey to black bands. The following four layers are distinguished on the basis of micromorphological characteristics. 1. The lowest horizon at the bottom of the hearth pit contains an abundant (charred) organic fraction, including some charcoal dust, one larger ($\pm 2\text{cm}$) piece of wood charcoal, a number of smaller ($< 5\text{mm}$) charcoal fragments and similarly sized fragments of charred organic tissue, as well as two pieces ($0,5\text{-}1\text{cm}$) of charcoal that show a partially viscous (vesicular) structure that is black and opaque. 2. The next layer shows a significant increase in the amount of charcoal dust, while at the same time a decrease in the number of wood charcoal fragments. The few fragments present are only very small ($< 1\text{mm}$). 3. Layer three contains similarly large amounts of charcoal dust, two larger ($\pm 1\text{cm}$) and several smaller ($1\text{-}2\text{mm}$) pieces of wood charcoal and charred organic tissue. Additionally, one small ($\pm 5\text{mm}$) fragment of charcoal has a partially viscous vesicular structure that is black and opaque. 4. Finally, the top layer of the pit still shows some small ($< 5\text{mm}$) pieces of charcoal and other charred tissue, but lacks the abundant amount of charcoal dust seen in the other layers.

III: Observations relating to post-depositional processes include: several domains filled with sand and strongly fragmented charred tissue (which can be related to bioturbation) and fragments of fresh (and decaying) plant tissue, some of which contain pyrite framboids and fungal hyphae.

4.1.3 FEATURE HAK-B-62

FIGURE 15: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE HAK-B-62 SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES.

I: The groundmass is primarily made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. The natural subsoil underneath the pit consists of relatively clean sand with a few traces of organic tissue.

II: Though no clear layering of the pit fill was observed in the field, three different layers were distinguished microscopically. 1. The bottom layer (ca. 9cm in thickness), corresponding with the bottom of the hearth pit, contains two large (± 1 and 4cm) fragments of charcoal with sharp edges, as well as some smaller (1-2mm) charcoal fragments and charred organic tissue. Charcoal dust is abundantly present in this layer. 2. On top of this rests a layer with significantly less charcoal dust which is unevenly dispersed throughout the fabric (giving the layer a more 'messy' appearance). Its remaining charred organic fraction includes two large (1-2cm) fragments of charcoal with rounded-off edges and several incompletely charred (brown) fragments of organic tissue (1-2mm). 3. The top horizon (ca. 40cm in thickness) contains significantly less charred material than the lower substrate, and therefore appears cleaner and lighter in colour. The charred organic fraction includes one larger (± 2 cm) fragment of charcoal, a number of smaller (1-2-mm) fragments of charcoal and charred organic tissue with sharp edges, as well as one piece of charcoal (black and opaque) that shows a partially viscous (vesicular) structure.

III: Observations relating to post-depositional processes include: very thin humus coatings in the soil below the feature, small amounts of illuviated charcoal dust (present as very small ($<0,1$ mm) loose particles and coatings in the top of the feature) and channels and domains (some with rootlets and/or mesofauna excrements) that are indicative of bioturbation. The top horizon contains extremely large amounts of decaying horizontally oriented plant tissue, which can otherwise be described as peat.

4.2 HOGE VAART-A27

FIGURE 16: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURES 51-914 (LEFT) AND 51-904 (RIGHT) SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE SAMPLES. ADAPTED FROM: SPEK ET AL. 2001, P. 99 (FIG. 10).

4.2.1 FEATURE 51-914

I: The groundmass is primarily made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. The natural subsoil underneath the pit consists of relatively clean sand with some decaying organic tissue.

II: A distinction can be made between the left and right side of the bottom fill; on the left side, charred organic remains and fragments of charcoal (ranging in size from <1 mm to 2cm) with sharp edges are common, in addition to charred humus, which is quite evenly dispersed throughout this area. Moreover, one larger (2cm) and one smaller (± 2 mm) fragment of charcoal have black and opaque sides that have a viscous (vesicular) structure. While the right side largely matches the left, what differs slightly is the presence of brown and black-brown *partially* charred humus that is not evenly dispersed. Another fragment of the 'viscous' tissue is present here. Towards the top of the feature, the amount of charred humus decreases, leaving only a small amount of charred organic fragments and charcoal fragments at the top of the fill.

III: Observations that relate to post-depositional processes include: common channels and

domains (often with rootlets in cross-section, some circular with concentrated burnt humus) that increase in number towards the top of the profile, fresh plant tissues (brown concentrations of amorphous organic matter, rootlets, orange-brown tissue fragments), sclerotia (increasing in number towards the top of the profile) and some fungal hyphae. The very top of the profile, above the pit features, shows a transition from peat to sand (with a groundmass of orange, brown and black-brown partially amorphous organic matter that is largely horizontally oriented), in addition to some humus coatings.

4.2.2 FEATURE 51-904

The samples taken from- and in relation to this feature represent both the pit (904) as well as part of the profile in between features 904 and 914 (fig. 16). On the basis of the micromorphological results, it is not completely clear if the 'natural profile' is in fact part of feature 904, or whether it is indeed the natural profile that has been intensely disturbed through bioturbation.

I: The mineral fraction of the groundmass of both the natural profile as well as that of the feature itself consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains.

II: The bottom of the feature contains a ca. 8-9cm wide horizontal dark band consisting of abundant fine fragmented charred organic tissue and one large (1cm) fragment and several smaller pieces of charred tree bark (with rounded-off edges). The horizon above contains significantly less charred material, but still includes; some partially charred sclerotia, a few concentrations of fine amorphous black material dispersed between the surrounding quartz grains and one fragment of amorphous black charred tissue with a vesicular viscous structure. The overall look of this part of the pit is quite messy.

The 'natural profile', in contrast, shows common charred humus that is heterogeneously dispersed in voids between quartz grains, in addition to a few small (<1mm) charcoal fragments and piece of charred plant tissue and two small (± 1 mm) fragments of charred tree bark. All of this is prevalent in the bottom 7,5cm of the profile, but much less so towards the top.

III: Observations that relate to post-depositional processes include: common small channels and domains, increasing in number and size towards the top of the profile, some of which with rootlets. Noteworthy are two bands of sediment that 'duck downwards' which contain material that is noticeably darker than the surrounding matrix and quite similar to the uppermost layer. The presence of fragments of charred tissue *under* and *besides* the pit bottom indicate movement/disturbance as well. Other observations include sclerotia, some fungal hyphae, a few pyrite globules in degrading/fresh plant tissues and some gypsum crystals (inside the horizontal dark band of the feature). Finally, a layer of peaty substrate (ca. ± 6 cm) covers the top of the feature and the rest of the profile (with horizontally oriented orange, brown and black-brown partially amorphous organic tissue).

4.2.3 FEATURE 131-902

FIGURE 17: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE 131-902 SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE SAMPLES. ADAPTED FROM: SPEK ET AL. 2001, P. 101 (FIG. 13)

None of the samples from feature 902 were taken with the intention to reflect the contents of the hearth pit. As such, all six sections come from either the upper half of the dark fill, or from the lighter horizon above (which might be a different fill from the pit or a horizon on top of the pit remains), covering a horizontal layer of $\pm 30\text{cm}$ measured from the top of the profile. Noticeable variability was recognized among the samples from both the darker fill as well as the top horizon (see Table 6), but general observations will be described below.

I: The mineral fraction of all thin sections consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains.

II: 1. (bottom fill) Abundant charred organic fraction, including common charred humus, a number ($N=10$) of partially charred brown charcoal fragments with sharp edges and come small ($<5\text{mm}$) pieces of rounded charcoal and a large amount of very finely fragmented charred organic material. Also one very large ($\pm 4\text{cm}$) piece of sharp fragmented charcoal of which the right half is very heavily degraded (possibly as the result of sampling or thin section preparation - the profile (fig. 17) show that the section intersects a large wood stump) and which contains domains consisting of clean quartz grains and some thin black fibers/bands. The middle of the fill contains abundant charred humus and charred humus coatings that increase in thickness towards the bottom of the pit, and the right side of the fill contains much less charred organic matter, including one small fragment of charred black opaque organic tissue with a viscous (vesicular) structure. The overall appearance of the fill is quite 'messy'.

2. (top fill) Contains a common charred organic fraction, including charred humus and -coatings which increase in amount towards the middle of the fill, some very small ($<1\text{mm}$) charcoal fragments and pieces of charred organic tissue, and five small ($<5\text{mm}$) fragments of charred black opaque organic tissue that show a viscous (vesicular) structure.

III: Observations that relate to post-depositional processes include: common small and medium channels and domains, most with rootlets in cross-section, though some larger domains are present in the upper right corner of the profile. Additionally, sclerotia (which increase in abundance towards the top of the profile), plant tissues (brown and orange brown fresh tissue, dark brown amorphous fragments and amorphous orange-brown concentrations), some iron oxides and gypsum crystals in the bottom fill (partially embedded in the matrix of charcoal fragments), and in one section from the bottom fill a band with very slight clay coatings was recognized.

4.3 KAMPEN

4.3.1 FEATURE 22

FIGURE 18: PROFILE SECTIONS OF PIT FEATURES (TOP TO BOTTOM) 22, 26 AND 27, SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES. FROM: HUISMAN ET AL. 2019, 3 (FIG. 4).

I: The groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains; the feature was truncated so it is hard to say anything about the original surface into which the feature was dug. Some degraded (brown and orange-brown) plant tissues in the natural soil could have been present in the pre-depositional stage, however.

II: The dark bottom fill of the hearth pit contains a common charred organic fraction, which includes: charred humus and humus coatings (the latter are attached to the fresh plant tissue present in the section), some partially charred sclerotia, a few small fragments of charcoal (<1mm) and charred particles of organic material. Some charcoal dust (amorphous in contrast to the polymorphic charred humus) is embedded in a number of cracked quartz grains, which are dispersed throughout the entire section.

III: Observations that relate to post-depositional processes include: a common organic fraction in the natural soil consisting of sclerotia, decaying amorphous fragments of organic tissue and fragments of plant tissue (brown and orange-brown). Channels filled with rootlets are abundant in the thin section taken next to the feature, but are less common in the charred fill. Some pyrite globules are present in the fresh plant tissues.

4.3.2 FEATURE 26

I: The mineral fraction of the groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains; the feature was truncated so it is hard to say anything about the original surface into which the feature was dug.

II: The dark fill of the pits contains a number of small (1-2mm) fragments of charcoal and fragments of charred organic material, as well as charred humus and -coatings that are irregularly distributed throughout the feature (but increase in concentration towards the top of

the pit).

III: Observations that relate to post-depositional processes include: small voids with fresh rootlets (observed beneath the bottom of the feature as well as in the charred pit-fill) and some rounded domains, a few fragments of micro-charcoal below the bottom of the feature, thin humus coatings at the bottom of the pit that decrease in intensity towards the top of the profile, fungal spores and some pyrite globules present in the fresh plant tissues.

4.3.3 FEATURE 27

This feature was described in the field as having two separate fills, both of which were sampled.

I: The mineral fraction of the groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains; the feature was truncated so it is hard to say anything about the original surface into which the feature was dug.

II: A common charred organic fraction is evenly distributed throughout the lower fill, which includes small fragments of charcoal and charred organic matter (0,5-2mm), (fragments of) charred sclerotia, one larger fragment of charcoal (>2cm) and a similar smaller fragment (± 2 mm) with sides that show a viscous vesicular structure. The horizon above also contains a common charred organic fraction, which decreased slightly in concentration upwards. The charred contents of this layer appear to be more finely fragmented. In contrast to the lower fill, this horizon contains common small brown fragments of charcoal as well as a concentration of fine amorphous black organic material (possibly charcoal dust) which is dispersed in between the surrounding quartz grains. Charred humus coatings are present throughout both fills. The mineral fraction of the bottom half of the feature appears to be more tightly packed.

II: Observations that relate to post-depositional processes include: common small channels with rootlets, concentrations of FeO and decaying organic matter embedded in the matrix of some charcoal fragments, and degrading plant tissues (some of which with pyrite globules).

4.3.4 FEATURE 75

FIGURE 19: PROFILE SECTION OF PIT FEATURE 75, SHOWING THE LOCATION OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL SAMPLES. FROM HUISMAN ET AL. 2019, 3 (FIG. 3).

For this feature a (nearly) continuous profile was sampled for both the pit feature as well as the adjacent natural profile. The results from the natural profile will not be described below, but can be found in Table 6.

I: The mineral fraction of the groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains; the feature appears to have been dug in a pre-existing podzol.

II: On the basis of micromorphological characteristics, two fills were recognized within the feature. 1. The bottom fill contains an abundant charred organic fraction, including abundant charred organic remains, some large (± 1 cm) and some smaller (<5mm) pieces of wood charcoal (some with sharp edges, some rounded) and abundant charred humus and charred organic coatings. 2. The top fill still contains some charred organic material, but significantly less so than the fill below. The charred organic fraction includes a few charcoal fragments and some very small (<1mm) fragments of rounded charred organic tissue, some charred sclerotia and

common charred humus. In contrast to the bottom layer, this fill shows more non-charred ('raw') degrading organic tissue, (partially charred?) dark brown humus, and dark thick humus coatings (some of which with small amounts of powdered charcoal).

III: Observations that relate to post-depositional processes include: common domains and (vertical) channels, some with rootlets (mainly present in the top of the profile), sclerotia, some pyrite framboids in fresh plant tissue and illuviated humus in a few charcoal fragments. To conclude, small bands (or 'fibers') consisting of illuviated clay and charcoal dust (also as coatings) have been recognized under the bottom of the feature, in addition to some small (<1mm) charcoal fragments and small amounts of charcoal dust ('powdery' charred remains) that were also present underneath the feature.

TABLE 6: OVERVIEW OF KEY MICROMORPHOLOGICAL OBSERVATIONS.

Site	Sample code	Feature	Description feature	Mineral groundmass	Microfeatures	Non-carbonized organic material	Carbonized remains				
							Wood charcoal	'Tar'	Charred humus	Other charred material	Powdered charcoal
Dronten	2181-1	HAK-A-572	Transition peat to A horizon	Fine sand	Pyrite, some small bands of clean sand interspersed throughout organic layer	Some sclerotia, abundant horizontally oriented organic matter (degrading peaty plant tissues), abundant humus, abundant humus coatings					
Dronten	2181-2	HAK-A-572	A horizon	Fine sand			Few small pieces				
Dronten	2181-3	HAK-A-572	Transition A horizon to B horizon (cover upper fill)	Fine sand		Small cluster of peaty remains, possibly the result of bioturbation, sporadic sclerotium, some humus coatings					
Dronten	2182-1	HAK-A-572	Transition B horizon to upper fill	Fine sand		Some sclerotia	Quite a few small pieces				
Dronten	2182-2	HAK-A-572	Transition upper fill to lower fill	Fine sand			A number of larger (± 1 cm) pieces				
Dronten	2182-3	HAK-A-572	Lower fill, lower part fill, BC horizon (bottom 6cm)	Fine sand	Very slight organic coatings in BC horizon	Some rootlets in cross section	Some small pieces, more fragmented than above				
Dronten	1727-1	HAK-B-32	Secondary layer	Fine sand	Pyrite		Some small pieces				Present
Dronten	1727-2	HAK-B-32	Transition secondary layer to	Fine sand		Some decaying organic tissue fragments	Some small pieces				Present

			upper fill								
Dronten	1727-3	HAK-B-32	Transition upper to lower fill, lower part fill, BC horizon	Fine sand		Sporadic sclerotia	One large (>2cm) piece, number of smaller fragments				Present
Dronten	1245-1	Natural	Sandy peat, A horizon	Fine sand		Abundant organic fraction (top 4 cm is horizontally oriented peat layer), including fresh plant tissue fragments and amorphous organic matter	Small fragments			Sporadical	
Dronten	1245-2	Natural	AB horizon to B horizon	Fine sand	Light humus coatings	Light humus coatings, some rootlets, some fresh plant tissue fragments, amorphous dark organic fragments	Few small pieces				
Dronten	1245-3	Natural	BC horizon to C horizon	Fine sand	Abundant humus coatings						
Dronten	1246-1	HAK-B-62	Sandy peat, A horizon	Fine sand		Amorphous horizontally oriented organic matter (top 2cm), some rootlets and fresh plant tissue fragments					
Dronten	1246-2	HAK-B-62	Transition A horizon to upper secondary fill	Fine sand		Degrading plant tissue fragments, some rootlets	Fairly large piece and some smaller fragments	Present		Some fragments	
Dronten	1246-3	HAK-B-62	Upper secondary fill	Fine sand		Fungal spore, some rootlets	Some small fragments				

Dronten	1247-1	HAK-B-62	Upper fill	Fine sand		Few degrading plant tissue fragments, few small concentrations of mesofauna excrements	One large and some smaller fragments				Present
Dronten	1247-2	HAK-B-62	Upper fill	Fine sand			Two larger (1-2cm) fragments and abundant small (<1mm) fragments				Abundant (though less than lower sample)
Dronten	1247-3	HAK-B-62	Transition upper to lower fill, lower part fill, BC horizon	Fine sand	Sporadic very thin humus coatings in BC horizon	Some rootlets	Two larger (ca. 1 and 4cm) and some smaller (1-2mm) fragments			Present	Abundant
Hoge Vaart	51-I-a	914	Transition 1C (peat) to 2Ce to 3E horizon	Fine sand		Lots of organic remains, humus, number of sclerotia, organic bands	Few small pieces				
Hoge Vaart	51-I-b	914	Upper fill	Fine sand	Abundant humus coatings	Some fungal hyphae, some sclerotia (fragments)	Few small pieces				
Hoge Vaart	51-I-c	914	Transition lower fill, lower part fill to BC horizon	Fine sand	Charred humus coatings		One large (>2cm) piece, number of smaller fragments	Present		Present (abundant in top half)	
Hoge Vaart	51-I-d	914	Transition lower part fill to BC horizon	Fine sand	Partially charred humus coatings			Present		Abundant	

Hoge Vaart	51-II-a	904	Transition 1C (peat) to 2Ce to 3E horizon	Fine sand		Degrading peaty organic remains, sclerotia, fresh roots					
Hoge Vaart	51-II-b	904	Transition upper to lower fill	Fine sand			Number of small fragments		Present		
Hoge Vaart	51-II-c	904	Transition 1C (peat) to 2Ce to 3E horizon	Fine sand		Sclerotia, fresh rootlets, fungal hyphae, dark degraded organic remains, horizontally oriented lighter peaty remains	Some small fragments	Present			
Hoge Vaart	51-II-d	904	Transition upper to lower fill	Fine sand	Pyrite and sporadic gypsum crystals	Fungal hyphae abundant in partially charred organic remains	Some small fragments	Possibly present (dark charred concentrations might be charred tar?)	Abundant?	Partially charred, present	
Hoge Vaart	131-a	902	Upper fill	Fine sand	Partially charred humus coatings			Present	Present		
Hoge Vaart	131-b	902	Transition upper to lower fill	Fine sand	Fe oxide, gypsum crystals, some (dusty) clay coatings, jarosite spheres				Abundant		
Hoge Vaart	131-c	902	Upper fill	Fine sand	Charred humus coatings		Fair number of large (>1cm) fragments		Abundant		
Hoge Vaart	131-d	902	Transition upper to	Fine sand	Fe oxide, pyrite	Some sclerotia	Small pieces		Abundant		

			lower fill				present				
Hoge Vaart	131-e	902	Transition upper to lower fill	Fine sand				Present	Present		
Hoge Vaart	131-f	902	Upper fill	Fine sand				Present			
Kampen	4263	22	BC next to pit 22	Fine sand	Pyrite	Few roots, quite some decaying tissue fragments				A small number of fragments	
Kampen	4264	22	Lower fill	Fine sand		Sclerotia, fungal spores, few decaying organic tissue fragments			Abundant	Number of fragments	
Kampen	4065	26	Lower fill	Fine sand		Small amount of organic coatings, few roots, few fragments decayed tissue					Small amount of ash coatings
Kampen	4066	Natural	C horizon below pit 26	Fine sand	Pyrite	Fungal spores, quite a number of fragments decayed tissue, few roots			Abundant		Present
Kampen	4062	27	Lower fill	Fine sand	Fe oxide	Sclerotia, decayed organic material, dark degraded moder	Present, one large piece	Present	Abundant		Present
Kampen	4063	27	Transition upper to lower fill	Fine sand	Pyrite	Strongly degraded organic remains, dark degraded humus	Present		Present		
Kampen	4275-B	Natural	AE horizon upper part	Fine sand		Degraded moder (?) humus. Many fungal hyphae. Roots.					
Kampen	4275-B	Natural	AE horizon lower part	Fine sand	Thick humus coatings, pyrite	Sclerotia, abundant degrading plant tissue					
Kampen	4275-M	Natural	B1 horizon	Fine sand	Band with thick humus coatings	Few rootlets; few fragments decaying plant					

						tissue					
Kampen	4275-0	Natural	B2 horizon	Fine sand	Pyrite, Fe oxide, very light thin coatings	Few roots; few fragments decayed tissue; fungal hyphae and sclerotia; thin humus coatings (?)					
Kampen	4276-B	Natural	B2 horizon	Fine sand	Pyrite, Fe oxide, very light thin coatings	Few roots; few fragments decayed tissue					
Kampen	4276-M	Natural	C horizon	Fine sand	Pyrite, Fe oxide, very light thin coatings	Few roots					
Kampen	4276-0	Natural	C horizon	Fine sand	Pyrite, Fe oxide, very light thin coatings	Few roots					
Kampen	4265	Natural	AE horizon in top feature 75	Fine sand	Pyrite, Fe oxide	Dark brown degraded moder or humus				A number of fragments	
Kampen	4265	Natural	AE horizon in top feature 75	Fine sand	Pyrite	Dark degraded moder/humus, less than in top of section, no proper coatings, roots, fragments of sclerotia	Very small piece in bottom section				
Kampen	4266	75	Transition AE horizon to upper fill	Fine sand		Dark degraded moder/humus					
Kampen	4266	75	Transition AE horizon to upper fill	Fine sand	Pyrite	Dark degraded moder/humus, fungus embedded in degrading organic matter, sclerotia, roots, organic tissue, some light humus coating	Small fragment			Quite a few fragments	

Kampen	4267	75	Upper fill	Fine sand	Pyrite, Fe oxide	Roots, decayed organic material, lots of humus coatings in top section	Present		Present		
Kampen	4268	75	Upper fill	Fine sand	Pyrite, Fe oxide	Large amount of sclerotia fragments, charred moder/humus?, degraded roots vertically oriented	Number of small fragments			Dispersed, though not evenly distributed, throughout entire section, charred sclerotia	
Kampen	4269	75	Transition dark-brown to black fill	Fine sand		Sclerotia	Fairly large piece in bottom left		Present, fairly common	Sclerotia	Abundant
Kampen	4270	75	Lower fill	Fine sand	Pyrite, Fe oxide		Few fragments		Abundant		Abundant
Kampen	4271	75	Lower part fill	Fine sand	Pyrite		Few fragments		Abundant		Abundant
Kampen	4271	75	C horizon	Fine sand		Fungal tissue fragments				Some fragments	Sporadic
Kampen	4272	Natural	C horizon with dark root fill	Fine sand		Few sclerotia, few roots	Small fragments				Small amount
Kampen	4273	Natural	C horizon	Fine sand	Bands with thick clay coatings, pyrite						
Kampen	4274	Natural	C horizon	Fine sand	Fe oxide	Few roots, few decaying tissue fragments					

5. INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

To come to further insights into the use and function of Mesolithic hearth pits it is important to consider our micromorphological observations as the result of a variety of underlying processes related to the period during and after use of the features. The following interpretations are structured *thematically* and will therefore be expounded along the main issues of 1. Identifying heterogeneity, 2. The charred organic constituents, 3. The top section of the features and 4. Identifying taphonomy and/or diagenesis.

5.1 IDENTIFYING HETEROGENEITY

Pit structures associated with combustion are often associated with intentional excavation (and possibly removal) of burnt contents, therefore causing a certain degree of reworking - and thus geological heterogeneity - to inevitably be present in the features (Mallol et al. 2017, 314).

Following this, an often used indicator for the reworking of combustion features is a presence of combustion residues but a lack of internal stratigraphy (op. cit., 315). An intact (undisturbed) combustion feature contains a stratigraphic sequence of sharply divided sedimentary layers: the top layer contains the burnt products of combustions, while the underlying layers comprise the heat-altered combustion substrate below the original fire (Mallol et al. 2017, 303).

The evidence of heterogeneity within the microstructure of our features (and thus the possibility of reworking, though other processes might be responsible) will be considered further along four main lines of evidence: 1. Irregularity of the microstructure and/or lack of internal stratigraphy, 2. The presence of voids and/or concentrations of charred remains and 3. The extent of charcoal fragmentation.

5.1.1 IRREGULARITY/LACK OF INTERNAL STRATIGRAPHY

No clear intact stratigraphy, related to either intact combustion features or to natural sedimentation processes filling up the pit, was recognized in any of the thin sections. While some features showed indications of internal layering (for example features

FIGURE 20: CONCENTRATIONS OF AMORPHOUS CHARRED ORGANIC MATERIAL, EMBEDDED IN VOID AND BETWEEN SURROUNDING QUARTZ GRAINS. A: SECTION 131-B (HOGE VAART), B: SECTION 131-E (HOGE VAART), C: SECTION 4063 (KAMPEN), D: SECTION 4266 (KAMPEN). PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL..

HAK-B-32 & HAK-B-62 from Dronten), the structure of these layers was never homogenous, and the boundaries between layers had a 'messy' appearance.

It is important to acknowledge that it is difficult to recognize stratigraphy on the microscale we are working at; stratigraphy within a thin section might still be part of a broader heterogeneous fill. Conversely, seemingly intact combustion stratigraphies have proven to show characteristics of intensive reworking on a micromorphological scale (Mallol et al. 2017, 315). Moreover, it has been suggested that the finer fraction present within combustion features can be subject to redistribution due to gravitational settling (Dibble et al. 2009, in Mallol et al. 2017, 315), therefore leading to a change in hetero- or homogeneity that is not related to the original use and function of the feature.

This does not mean, however, that it is entirely impossible to identify either intact or disturbed internal stratigraphy on the basis of soil micromorphology. Problems such as the ones above are mainly a problem of scale; the absence of separate micro-horizons within a thin section does not necessarily equate to the absence of this phenomenon on a macroscopic scale.

5.1.2 PRESENCE OF VOIDS/CONCENTRATIONS OF CHARRED MATERIAL

A recurring phenomenon that could possibly indicate some degree of reworking was found in the form of concentrations of charred and very finely fragmented ('dusty') organic material (fig. 20). These concentrations consist of a small area of fine purely charred material which is embedded in between and around the surrounding quartz grains. What is interesting, however, is the absence of similar concentrations of charcoal dust in the surrounding sediment; while some clumps of charred material are part of a larger domain that is rich in charred remains, many of them are part of otherwise relatively 'clean' substrate. It is possible that these concentrations were brought up (or down) from a horizon more rich in charred material, instead of being the result of the process of charring itself. A similar distribution of charcoal dust has previously been interpreted as the result of (anthropogenic) digging activities (Van Kappel & Exaltus 2019, 347). This interpretation, however, is solely based on earlier interpretations of similar features - not on experimental data. While thick horizons of this type of matrix indeed are likely the result of some type of reworking, smaller concentrations might just as well be the result of bioturbation. An alternative origin of the charred concentrations has been suggested (H. Huisman, pers. comment): some of the especially opaque and compressed examples might be interpreted as the product of burning tar-like masses.

An increase in porosity and the presence of larger voids (larger than normal packing voids) has been suggested to be another indicator for the reworking of combustion features (Mentzer 2014). Some larger voids (that could not clearly be attributed to bioturbation) were indeed recognized in the thin sections. It is, however, again difficult to recognize the extent and regularity of these indicators within our relatively small thin sections (in this case especially those from Dronten); it is therefore essential to compare the micromorphological observations with those made in the field on a macroscopic level.

5.1.3 EXTENT OF CHARCOAL FRAGMENTATION.

A third indicator of the reworking or reuse of hearth pits consists of the character and extent of charcoal fragmentation. Wood charcoal breaks in a different way than other decayed plant material - its fracture is characteristically conchoidal - and it is therefore quite easily distinguishable from non-woody charred remains (Karkanias & Goldberg 2018, 103). Examples of charcoal with such sharp fracture edges have been observed in thin sections from pits from all three sites (Dronten: HAK-B-32, HAK-B-62; Hoge Vaart-A27: 131-902; Kampen: 27). On occasion, the sharp fractures occur within the cell structure of a larger piece of charcoal, but more often the conchoidal breaks are limited to the edges of a fragment (fig. 21).

In contrast to the significance of sharp fragmentation observed in wood charcoal, another indicator for the reworking of a feature constitutes the rounding of charred organic fragments and fragile plant remains. The degradation and/or rounding of charcoal edges was observed in multiple instances, shown clearly in the examples of charred tree bark from section 51-II-D, as well as most of the smaller charcoal fragments present in other thin sections (see Table 6).

It has been suggested that pits with more strongly fragmented charcoal might have been fired for a longer time, or with different types of wood, than features with less fractured charcoal (Peeters & Hogestijn 2001, 130). However, it is important to distinguish between fragmentation effects that are the result of reworking a combustion feature on the one hand, and fragmentation that is the result of postdepositional processes (and thus not of the intentional use of the feature) on the other. Bioturbation by insects and other fauna, for instance, has been a known cause for the fragmentation and rounding of fragile (organic) materials (Mallol et al. 2017, 318), which does indicate a type of 'reworking' of the feature, but which is not a significant indication for anthropogenic activity.

FIGURE 21: EXAMPLES OF CHARCOAL FRAGMENTS WITH SHARP FRAGMENTATION EDGES, POSSIBLY INDICATIVE OF REWORKING. A: SECTION 1727 (DRONTEN), B: SECTION 2182 (DRONTEN), C: SECTION 1247 (DRONTEN), D: NOTE THE SHARP BREAKS ARE LOCATED IN THE INTERNAL STRUCTURE OF THE FRAGMENT, SECTION 131-B (HOGE VAART). PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

FIGURE 22: REWORKED CHARCOAL FROM A WATER-LAIN DEPOSIT AT THE SITE OF LA QUINA (FRANCE). NOTE THE SHARP FRACTURES IN THE INTERNAL STRUCTURE OF THE CHARCOAL FRAGMENT. FROM: MENTZER 2014, 644 (FIG. 10).

FIGURE 23: INCOMPLETELY CHARRED TREE BARK (SECTION 51-II-D, HOGE VAART). NOTE THE 'LAMINATED' STRUCTURE OF ALTERNATING DARK BANDS AND BROWN TRANSLUCENT CELLS. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

5.2 CHARRED ORGANIC CONSTITUENTS

FIGURE 24: WOOD CHARCOAL SPECIES DETERMINATION, A: POROUS HARDWOOD, FEATURE HAK-A-572 DRONTEN; B: CORYLUS AVELLANA, FEATURE HAK-B-32 DRONTEN; C: RING-POROUS HARDWOOD, FEATURE 51-914 HOGE VAART; D: SOFTWOOD, FEATURE 26 KAMPEN; E: FEATURE 26 KAMPEN; F: PINUS SYLVESTRIS, FEATURE 27 KAMPEN. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

One of the most important diagnostic elements found in hearth pits constitutes the broad category of charred organic remains. A single fire produces a variety of different charred products (Weiner 2010, 180), which can form the basis of answering several questions about the use and function of the features: the products might say something about the temperatures reached in the feature, the selection (or lack thereof) of organic material (more specifically wood or other plant remains), and ultimately about the possible use of the hearth pit.

5.2.1 DEGREE OF CHARRING (BROWN CHARCOAL)

Brown, incompletely charred charcoal was recognized in multiple thin sections from all three sites. Moreover, the charcoal fragments were not limited to a specific type of wood. These observations provide evidence for poor oxidizing conditions in relation to thermal alteration (which has previously been identified by use of geochemical analysis as well). The remains are the end product of pyrolysis as opposed to combustion, which requires both a reducing

environment as well as relatively low temperatures, suggesting that the samples in question were not taken from the primary direct heat source (Mallol et al. 2017, 310).

5.2.2 WOOD CHARCOAL SPECIES DETERMINATION

A number of charcoal fragments proved to be sufficiently intact to identify their species (Table 7). The determinations generally match previous conclusions of anthracological analysis: some pits contain softwood (mainly pine), some pits contain (ring)porous hardwood (mainly oak) and others represent a combination of both. No significant differences were observed between the three sites.

What is important to consider, is that the determined species might only represent the type of wood used in the final (or last) phases of hearth use. While it is suspected that the use of a hearth pit was a fairly short-lived event, there are indications for the re-use of certain features (Van Kappel & Exaltus 2012; Van Kappel & Exaltus 2019). Thus it is possible that the determined species might not be completely representative of the overall use of the hearth pit (Weiner 2010, 178).

It is also essential to contemplate the different speeds at which different wood taxa burn. Birch, for instance, burns quickly and completely, leaving no residue behind (Bishop et al. 2015, 60), whereas oak burns much more steady and produces less flame (loc. cit.). This might have led to an overrepresentation of slow-burning species (or, vice versa, the underrepresentation of quick-burning ones) in the archaeological record.

TABLE 7: OVERVIEW OF WOOD CHARCOAL PRESENT IN THIN SECTIONS OF WHICH THE SPECIES COULD BE DETERMINED. NOTE THE PRESENCE OF A COMBINATION OF SOFTWOOD (MAINLY PINE) AND HARDWOOD (MAINLY OAK) IN FEATURE 51-904 (HOGE VAART) AND FEATURE 75 (KAMPEN).

Site	Feature	Date (feature)	Wood species
Hoge Vaart	51-904	6135±49BP	Pinus sylvestris + Quercus
Hoge Vaart	51-914	7800±60BP	Ring-porous hardwood
Hoge Vaart	131-902	6112±45BP	Quercus + other porous hardwood
Dronten	HAK-A-572	6066-5909 BC	Porous hardwood
Dronten	HAK-B-32	5842-5670 BC 5976-5740 BC	Quercus + Corylus avellana
Dronten	HAK-B-62	5845-5669 BC	Betula + Corylus avellana + Diffuse porous wood
Kampen	26	7650±50BP	Softwood
Kampen	27	7730±50BP	Softwood + Pinus sylvestris
Kampen	75	6080±40BP	Quercus + Porous hardwood + Ring-porous hardwood + Softwood

5.2.3 IDENTIFICATION OF BARK

A number of incompletely charred (dark brown) fragments of plant tissue were found in thin section 51-II-d (in the absence of any charcoal), that the current author was unable to identify (fig. 23). Several botanical experts were contacted with the aim to identify the remains. The tissue was ultimately identified as tree bark. More detailed species determination was not possible for the consulted specialists, though the fact that bark was found in a concentrated

charred state is interesting in and of itself. This observation might be explained in several different ways. One possibility is that a fragment of bark came loose from one of the logs that was burnt in the pit and subsequently charred separately from the wood. Another explanation, however, could be that we are looking at the result of the deliberate selection and charring of tree bark for a planned purpose. We know that birch bark has been used in the past to produce tar (Groom et al. 2013)

5.2.4 AMORPHOUS ORGANIC COMBUSTION REMAINS

OPAQUE VISCOUS (VESICULAR) FRAGMENTS

A first prominent example of amorphous remains is that of char- or tar-like amorphous opaque masses with a vesicular internal structure (fig. 25). On occasion, these aggregates are attached to fragments of charcoal. This suggests that their origin is indeed plant-related, thus being the charred counterpart of wood resin secretions. The tar-like masses that are not attached to charcoal might as a result be interpreted as concentrations of wood tar as well.

FIGURE 25: AMORPHOUS OPAQUE COMBUSTION REMAINS WITH A VESICULAR STRUCTURE: A. NOTE THE REMAINS OF THE CELL STRUCTURE OF PINE WOOD ON ONE SIDE OF THE FRAGMENT, FEATURE 27 KAMPEN (SECTION 4062); B. FEATURE 27 KAMPEN (SECTION 4062); C. FEATURE 51-914 HOGE VAART (SECTION 51-1-D); D. FEATURE 131-902 HOGE VAART (131-E).

FIGURE 26 (LEFT): AN EXAMPLE OF 'FAT DERIVED CHAR' ATTACHED TO A FRAGMENT OF WOOD CHARCOAL, FOUND IN A MESOLITHIC SHELL MIDDEN (POÇAS DE SÃO BENTO, PORTUGAL). FROM: DUARTE ET AL. 2019, 494 (FIG. 4A)

FIGURE 27 (RIGHT): AN EXAMPLE OF 'FAT DERIVED CHAR' FROM AN IRON AGE OPEN AIR HEARTH (GREECE). NOTE THE LARGE VESICLES AND THE CRACKING (A SIGN OF DIAGENESIS) INDICATED BY THE RED ARROW. FROM: MALLOL ET AL. 2017, 305 (FIG. 31.2B)

FIGURE 28: CHARRED HUMUS AND HUMUS COATINGS. A: FEATURE 75, SECTION 4270 KAMPEN; B: FEATURE 131-902, SECTION 131-D HOGE VAART; C: FEATURE HAK-B-32, SECTION 1727 DRONTEN. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

An important question that cannot be answered definitively at the moment, is whether these vesicular opaque masses are the result of an intentional process of tar production, or whether they are the by-product of a different process that is not related to the production of tar (Huisman et al. 2019, 2). The occurrence of similar masses in a shell midden (Duarte et al. 2017) suggests that, at the very least, tar-like remains *can* be the accidental by-product of a fire that was not used to make tar, on the condition that a oxygen-poor environment is present.

CHARRED HUMUS (OR MODER³)

A second significant observation concerns the frequent presence of charred humus in the bottom part of the features; evidence of charred humus was observed at all sampled pits from Kampen and multiple pits from Hoge Vaart. Black cracked coatings around sand grains are thought to be composed of charred humus as well. While both raw humus as well as humus coatings were both present in the samples from Dronten, none of the pits contained evidence of their charred counterpart. What is important, is that the presence of charred humus represents a by-product of another intentional process; people did not set out to create charred humus, but did end up creating it as part of a different activity. Moreover, the morphology of the charred material in combination with the presence of charred sclerotia most probably indicates that the organic material was already decomposing at the moment of charring (Huisman et al. 2019, 8). The presence of charred humus has recently been related to the remains of burnt topsoil material (in the form of turfs) that was consciously deposited inside the hearth pits (loc. cit.). Experimental investigation has, however, shown that only the top 1-1,5cm of the substrate becomes blackened due to the incomplete combustion of soil organic matter (Mallol et al. 2013a; Mallol et al. 2013b). If the transforming effect of a fire on the subsoil is this limited, how can the charring of multiple layers of topsoil turfs be explained? This question should be one of the objectives of future (experimental) research.

At first sight, nearly all thin sections studied for this project appear to contain some amount of dark, charred organic remains without a clear internal structure. It is, however, difficult to distinguish burnt plant remains from fragments that are humified; both are darkened in colour and have degraded to a great extent (Canti 2017). Moreover, charcoal in thin sections is often encountered in the form of very fine (sand-sized) particles that are hard to differentiate from (uncharred) 'organic punctuations' that occur in the natural soil (loc. cit.). Again, the question of scale becomes important here; single observations might not suffice a clear identification, but dark points in a layer with larger charcoal fragments and charred coatings will clearly be more convincingly identified as charred organic remains than would be the case for a few dark points in an otherwise 'clean' natural layer.

³ It is very difficult, if not impossible, to distinguish between moder and humus in charred condition, especially when the substance has been compressed *before* charring. The substance will therefore be referred to as 'charred humus'.

FIGURE 29: DIFFERENT MICROSCOPIC INDICATIONS FOR BIOTURBATION, A: CIRCULAR DOMAIN WITH CONCENTRATED FRAGMENTS OF CHARRED ORGANIC TISSUE, SECTION 1247 DRONTEN; B: CIRCULAR DOMAIN POSSIBLY WITH CHARRED HUMUS CONCENTRATION, SECTION 131-E HOGE VAART; C: SLIGHTLY ELONGATED ROUNDED DOMAIN CONTAINING A CONCENTRATION OF CHARRED ORGANIC TISSUE, SECTION 2182 DRONTEN; D: BROWN 'CUT UP' ORGANIC TISSUE AND MICROFAUNA EXCREMENTS IN FRESH PLANT TISSUE, SECTION 4275-M KAMPEN. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

5.3 TOP PART OF HEARTH PIT FEATURES

Something that has been lacking in most earlier hearth pit discovery is the presence of complete pits, including the fill on top of the charred bottom layer. Luckily, more hearth pits have been recently discovered in an intact profile. We can therefore give some cautious interpretations as for the micromorphological characteristics of these top fills.

The top fill of feature 75 (Kampen) was shown to contain significant amounts of both charred as well as non-charred humus and organic tissue, as well as a large number of sclerotia. This microfabric looks very similar to the topsoil of the adjacent natural profile, but the material inside the feature continues to show further down than expected from the natural subsoil (Huisman et al. 2019, 9). The fill does not show the layering that can be associated with natural sedimentation; this has led the current author, as well as Huisman et al. (2019, 9) to suggest that the pit must have been filled in quite soon after use, most probably by people.

A second example of a more or less intact top horizon was recognized in HAK-B-62 (Dronten). The top horizon of the feature contains significantly more powdered charcoal than the adjacent natural profile, while the natural subsoil contains much more non-charred organic tissue. Again, no natural sedimentation seems to be present, but the similarities between the pit fill and the natural profile observed in Kampen are lacking here.

5.4 TAPHONOMY/DIAGENESIS

Indication of taphonomy and diagenesis might be observed on the level of the feature as a whole, as well as on the level of individual fill constituents such as the charred organic remains. In the case of charcoal for example, studies of modern and fossil material have shown that oxidation is the main diagenetic

reaction responsible for degradation. The oxidation process converts charcoal in a material that resembles soil humic substances, which on first sight might thus be misidentified as uncharred material (Weiner 2010, 179). To understand the original state (right after use) of hearth pit features and their contents, we thus need to consider all taphonomic processes that have influenced the archaeological record and that thereby have transformed the used feature into what we recognize now archaeologically.

5.4.1 BIOTURBATION

In almost all features signs of bioturbation were observed in various degrees of intensity. Cavities, channels and domains have been recognized in almost all pit features, many of which contained (fresh) rootlets in cross section. In contrast to the activity of soil fauna, compaction features are not a significant indicator since root growth is much more gradual than the movement of microfauna (Courty et al. 1989, 144). Plant bioturbation can, however, cause the movement of charred remains between different horizons, but this process appears to be of limited importance for the overall interpretation of our features. One indication of this phenomenon may be found in the thin section sampled below feature 26 (Kampen), where fragments of micro-charcoal were recognized *below* the bottom of the hearth pit. What is important to consider, is the possibility that rootlets have contributed to the fragmentation and/or degradation of the charcoal in the features.

The activity of soil fauna appears to also be partially responsible for the heterogeneity observed in some thin sections. Multiple sections contain rounded microfeatures that are loosely packed with charred material, with compaction at the edges and an otherwise quite 'clean' surrounding matrix (fig. 29a-c); this type of activity is very common for poorly structured (sandy) soils (Courty et al. 1989, 142). Another indicator for animal activity, the excrements of microfauna, were also seen on more than one occasion (fig. 29d).

While earthworm activity has previously been associated with samples that contain large amounts of charcoal, the typical channels created by earthworms (with layered compaction at both ends of the channel; Huisman et al. 2012, 997) were not observed in any of the sections for this study. This is actually expected for the sections which contain (charred) moder, because these soils are generally not suitable for earthworms. Instead, microarthropods are most active in these soils, which leave structures (e.g. microaggregates and organic material that is partially humified) that are more similar to what can be seen in our thin sections (Courty et al. 1989, 148).

5.4.2 PYRITE FORMATION

The presence of pyrite framboids in the sections is a reflection of local soil conditions: in our case it is either the result of anoxic groundwater with moderate to high bacterial activity in a reducing environment, or that of a moderately high groundwater level in freshwater peat-forming environments (Bouma et al 1990; Tang et al., 2001; Stahlschmidt et al. 2015a). It is not necessarily an indicator of significant changes in soil structure, but it is interesting to see that all three sites show the presence of pyrite to a certain extent (and thus manifest at least some comparable soil conditions).

FIGURE 30: PYRITE FORMATION IN FRESH PLANT TISSUE. A:SECTION 4267, KAMPEN; B: SECTION 4268, KAMPEN. PHOTOMICROGRAPHS IN PPL.

FIGURE 31: POSSIBLE INDICATION FOR ASH-RELATED DISPLACEMENT OF CLAY ILLUVIATION AND CHARCOAL DUST, KAMPEN (FEATURE 75). THE ORANGE ARROWS INDICATE DARK POWDERY CHARCOAL INSIDE THE CLAY COATINGS; THE YELLOW AND BLACK ARROWS INDICATE THE PRESENCE OF ILLUVIATED CLAY COATINGS (A: PPL, B: XPL).

5.4.3 ABSENCE OF ASH

When (well preserved) wood or bark ash is present in thin sections, its observable constituents comprise calcite, siliceous aggregates and phytoliths (Weiner 2010, 169). However, while the presence of ash is generally a direct indicator for combustion (though not necessarily in-situ!), the *absence* of ash does not necessarily lead to the conclusion that no fire was originally present. The feature might for instance have been cleared out after firing, removing any ash present. Moreover, there are secondary indicators for the original presence of ash where physical remains are lacking: Huisman et al. 2012 - ash can cause disintegration of combustion remains and the movement of clay.

While no traces of wood or bark ash were observed in any of the thin sections, a possible indirect example of the original presence of ash was observed in a sample from Kampen (taken from below the supposed bottom of hearth pit 75). Here we see

horizontal fibre-like depositions composed of powdery black organic remains (possibly charcoal dust) and illuviated clay particles (observed in XPL).

5.5 OTHER REMARKS

To conclude, we will consider a few more issues that are of importance for the interpretation of our micromorphological data before moving on to a broader discussion.

First of all, what does the absence of oxidation and/or rubification of the sediment mean in the context of hearth pit use? No evidence of strong iron oxide coatings was recognized in the features under current investigation, neither macroscopically nor on a microscopic level. The absence of oxidation indicators does not necessarily mean that fire was not originally present inside the pit; when charcoal and ashes are produced rapidly by the fire in a pit, it is possible that the centre of combustion is artificially raised. This quick building up of material beneath the fire might thus create an insulating layer, which makes it impossible for the bottom of the hearth (and the substrate) to oxidize (March et al. 2014).

Secondly, different activities (and processes) might actually lead to similar outcomes in terms of micromorphological observations. In case of the tar-like viscous substances, we cannot be sure whether our observations are the result of conscious tar production (which happens under reducing conditions), or whether they are the by-product of a completely different process (that also happens to require an oxygen-poor environment). We unfortunately do not have access to a database of 'baseline' data to compare our observations to archaeological outcomes of distinct processes.

Finally, before moving on to a broader contextualization of the results, we need to consider the questions relating to the meaning of the variation present in our micromorphological observations. Evidently, the contents of the ten pits that were investigated are not entirely similar. It is, however, difficult to make any definitive statements about the meaning of the micro-scale variability that we have observed between pits and sites. All pits "are not like the other", but is this indicative of different functionality, or of a variety in outcomes of a very uniformly practised process?

6. DISCUSSION

How do our micro-scale observations contribute to our knowledge on the use and function of Mesolithic hearth pits? To answer this question, we briefly need to readdress our initial research questions. These were related to: a. Identifying indicators for inter- and intrasite variation in and among the (contents of the) pit features, b. The use of the pit and the characteristics of the pit fills, more specifically its charred organic constituents, and c. The evaluation of methodology relating to the use of micromorphology in this specific case study. These three questions will be discussed accordingly, contextualizing the new observations within the existing corpus of knowledge and information on hearth pits and their use. Additionally, the implications of our inferences (based on microscale research) for our perception of hunter-gatherer behaviour and capability will be considered as well.

6.1 IDENTIFYING VARIATION

One of the objectives of this study was to *compare* hearth pit data on a range of scales, with a focus on micromorphological observations. In the search for variation, it is equally important to identify *similarities* as well as *differences* between individual pits and sites. A number of relevant conclusions can be drawn in this regard.

First of all, large quantities of charred humus in the bottom of hearth pits are present in features from both Hoge Vaart and Kampen, but not in those from Dronten. It is only a selection of features from the first two sites, however, that have shown this phenomenon; not every hearth pit at both sites contains the large amounts of charred humus. The pits that do, on the other hand, are quite similar in their composition, containing thick layers of the charred topsoil material but noticeably few larger fragments of wood charcoal or other charred organic remains. Secondly, fragments of a dark 'tar-like' (viscous, vesicular) substance have been identified at all three sites, in varying quantities. Not all features at each of these sites contain the material, however. The recognition of the tar-like fragments does not appear to correlate with the intensity of sampling, nor with the 'completeness' of the feature; while the complete and thoroughly sampled profile of hearth pit 75 (Kampen) did not yield any charred viscous tissue, pit 27 (Kampen), of which only the bottom fill was left and of which only one sample was taken, contained the largest fragment within the current investigation.

Thirdly, indications for ash-induced clay illuviation have only been recognized at possibly two of the features from all sites. While it is possible that this limited occurrence correlates with a lack of samples from the soil underneath hearth pits, it appears for now that it is a very restricted phenomenon. A fourth observation that is interesting both in terms of scale comparison as well as a lack of variation concerns the incidence of (identifiable) firewood species. Thin sections from all three sites, though not all pit features, have yielded a variety of determinable charcoal fragments. No significant patterns could be identified among these observations. Anthracological analysis of macroscopic wood charcoal, however, has in contrast managed to pinpoint general selection patterns related to environmental change. Soil micromorphological results were not able to match this interpretation.

Finally, all of the investigated features show varying degrees of bioturbation that can be attributed to roots as well as micro- and mesofauna. In this case, the differences *between features* provide the most interesting results. Podzol soils such as the one encountered in Kampen have limited soil-fauna activity (Huisman et al. 2019, 9), but the different features within the site show varying degrees of bioturbation. The amount of bioturbating activity thus appears to be varying on a very *localized* scale.

Having identified a range of indicators for intra- and inter-site variability, the meaning of this variation needs to be considered. To what extent are the differences and similarities between pits and sites relevant?

Studies and interpretations of artefact variation are manifold, all trying to get to grips with the meaning and creation of temporal, geographic and functional categories on the basis of variation and standardization (Eerkens 2000; Eerkens & Bettinger 2001; Eerkens & Lipo 2005).

Variability among archaeological observations is, to a certain extent, an inevitable result of human involvement: skilled craftsmen can knap dozens of morphologically similar projectile points that still show a degree of variation among them (Eerkens & Bettinger 2001, 494). This unavoidable deviance is partially caused by what is termed *scalar error*; errors that occur in the translation of mental images into physical objects (Eerkens & Bettinger 2001, 494). Mistakes as the result of this 'error of translation' increase in absolute size as the mental template for the object grows in size. In other words, the errors are larger when people make larger objects (loc. cit.). Moreover, different people will almost definitely have different ideas on what constitutes the 'ideal' shape or size of an object, adding another degree of variation that is not necessarily meaningful in terms of classification (Eerkens & Bettinger 2001, 500).

Soil features cannot be treated entirely similar to artefacts, however, nor can hearth pits be considered equal to other soil features such as postholes. While the morphology of artefacts is meaningful, either stylistic or functional, and the shape of a posthole is directly related to the shape and thickness of the pole once in it, the exact shape of a hearth pit appears to be of less importance. General principles of course apply, ensuring consistency in the outcome of the process the pit was used for. If one individual, however, would dig and fire ten hearth pits successively, they would probably not look *exactly* the same - certainly not on a microscopic level, since the complete absence of morphological variety is not relevant for the function of the pit. Morphological variability on a macroscale might therefore not be meaningful, but unintentionally caused micromorphological characteristics, in contrast, might very well be.

Still, we have also observed variation on a micromorphological level. Why do so many hearth pits *not* contain the vitrified, tar-like substances or the large quantities of charred humus that were identified microscopically? Again, this is most likely an issue of **scale**: we are looking at a small sample of a larger pit, which has also been bisected during excavation. The absence of certain evidence in a thin section does not necessarily equate to the absence of this evidence in the rest of the feature. Some of the identified variation is most probably the result of local geology and/or hydrology, while other indicators might be related to anthropogenic activity; to elucidate the actual processes responsible for a certain phenomenon, it is thus important to compare different scales of observation (*Ch. 2.3.1*).

In the context of interpreting the use and function of hearth pits, the identification of **presence** or **absence** (as opposed to the 'degree' of presence) might be more valuable, at least when the meaning of a certain micromorphological phenomenon is still unclear. In other words, in this stage of the research it would be more relevant to investigate the processes underlying certain micromorphological observations, as opposed to questioning why some pits look slightly different than others. This does not mean, however, that variation in absence or presence of phenomena should be ignored; it might actually be essential in the search for hearth pit use and function.

6.2 HEARTH PIT USE AND FUNCTION: EXAMINING EXISTING HYPOTHESES

Thanks to previously conducted research, we know a lot about hearth pits in terms of their spatial distribution, chronology and (to a certain extent) about their contents. One important question that remains incompletely answered so far, however, addresses the likelihood of one of four hypotheses on hearth pit use and function:

1. The features are in fact the result of natural as opposed to anthropogenic activity,
2. The pits were used for tar production,
3. The pits were used for food-related tasks and

4. The pits were used for tool modification such as cracking stone.

How has micromorphological analysis contributed to arguing either for or against these existing ideas? For each of the hypotheses, the micromorphological results will be considered within a broader geographical context and in the light of previously existing ideas and evidence from both ethnographic as well as archaeological contexts (Table 7).

6.2.1 ANTS: A NON-HUMAN AGENT

A 2015 study which was touched upon briefly earlier in this study, contested the anthropogenic character of Mesolithic hearth pits, arguing instead for an interpretation as burnt ant mounds (Crombé et al. 2015, 158). The authors suggest that, on the basis of their spatial distribution, subsoil characteristics and the lack of association with human occupation remains, the dark 'pit fill' actually represents the collapsed remains of a once above-ground ant hill (op. cit. 169).

The implications of such a non-anthropogenic explanation would be far-reaching; not only would the current collection of hearth pits be dismissed as the remains of biological activity, all future archaeological investigation of the features would be considered valueless.

The micromorphological results of the current study have not contributed to either the confirmation or the dismissal of the model proposed by Crombé. This is not entirely unexpected: modern (burnt) ant mounds have not previously been sampled for micromorphology, so there is no comparative data available at this moment. While plenty of evidence for bioturbation was observed in the thin section from all three sites, there is no definitive indication that ants are responsible for these phenomena. This situation might change soon, however: in April of 2019 a small field survey of known ant hill locations in Heeze (The Netherlands) was conducted by the Cultural Heritage Agency (RCE). Both burnt and non-burnt mounds were sectioned and sampled for micromorphological analysis. Human activities produce unique micromorphological combinations of fabrics (as do micro- and macrofauna), so it ought to be possible to distinguish between ant- and anthropogenic activity. Results will follow in the future, but baseline observations for further investigation have indeed been collected.

TABLE 7: AN OVERVIEW OF EVIDENCE FOR THE FOUR MAIN HYPOTHESES ON HEARTH PIT USE AND FUNCTION (BURNT ANT MOUNDS, TAR PRODUCTION, COOKING-RELATED PRACTICES AND THE THERMAL PREPARATION OF LITHICS).

Hypothesis	Source	Location	Description	References
Ants	Biology?			
Tar production	Historic	Macedonia and Syria	From Theophrastus' 'Enquiry into plants': pine-wood logs were heaped on a sloping piece of cleared ground, covered with earth and fired. The resin then flowed out down the slope into a hole	Hort 1916; In: Orengo et al. 2013
	Ethnographic	Southern Turkey	Tar production in double pit, with firing compartment containing the pine (cedar) wood; this compartment is covered with a thick layer of leaves and herbs, and another layer of mud. The other compartment is connected and used to collect the <i>katran</i> tar. Temperatures remain above 300°C, and the distillation process can take up to 15 days.	Kurt et al 2008
	Archaeology	Middle Sweden	Evidence of 'tar-dales' and funnel shaped pits associated with tar production in the Roman Iron Age	Hjulström et al. 2006
	Experimental	N/A	Experimental aceramic production of birch bark tar in a pit, bark covered with sand and	Pfeifer & Clausen 2016

			clay, fire on top of pit; shallow pit provided tar, but also lots of charred bark - for the deep pit the temperature inside the pit did not become high enough	
	Experimental	N/A	Experimental exploration of aceramic production of birch bark tar, using a pit proved to be unsuccessful	Groom et al. 2013
Cooking	Archaeology	Hempens	Five 'cooking stones'; four made of granite, one of quartzitic sandstone	Hielkema 2006
	Archaeology	NP3 (Veenkoloniën)	Some flint cooking stones that were distinguishable from flint artefact that 'accidentally' burnt	Groenendijk 1997
	Archaeology	Halsskov (Denmark)	With the exemption of one pit, none of the features that indicated burning contained (fragments of) stones. A number of features, however, did contain parenchymous tissue of pignut tubers and ramson bulbs, as well as raspberry seeds, hazelnuts and acorns	Kubiak-Martens 2002; Robinson & Harild 2002
	Archaeology	Northwestern North American Plains	Hearth pits without any rock elements were found to contain charred limber pine (<i>Pinus flexilis</i>) seeds	Armstrong 1993, 13; Dering 1996; in: Wandsnider 1997, 32
	Archaeology	Southern North American Plains	Hearth pits without rock elements were found to contain remains of onions and charred camas	Armstrong 1993, 13; Dering 1996; in: Wandsnider 1997, 32
	Ethnographic	North America	Extensive overview of traditional pit cooking practices of plant foods, roasting of nuts and seeds and roasting of meat	Wandsnider 1997
	Ethnographic	Canada	Steaming bulbs of wild onion in hearth pits overnight, roots are roasting directly in the coals of a hearth (inside a pit) or wrapped in leaves that are put in hot ashes, or wrapping the food in birch bark and putting it in a pit, after which the pit is filled with hot sand and a fire is built on top of it	Kubiak-Martens 2002; Kari 1995
	Archaeology	Duvensee	Large-scale hazelnut roasting, though in shallow depressions (not strictly pits)	Holst 2010
	Ethnographic	South Africa (!Kung)	Roasting of Mongongo nuts using sand as a heat conductor (no open fire)	Holst 2010
	Experimental	N/A	Roasting of hazelnuts in a small pit covered with sand and a fire on top, intended to see what would happen if a storage unit was burnt: result is inedible nuts after a short period of time, but they are indeed severely charred. No mention of the appearance of the pit itself	López-Dóriga 2015
Lithic heat treatment	Ethnographic	Middle North America	Raw material was buried in earth, on top of which a fire was built. After the fire was extinguished, the material was left to cool down for several days in the pit.	Olausson & Larsson 1982
	Experimental	N/A	A large pit was dug in which successive layer of charcoal and sand were created, between which the flint was heated. This was done to ensure gradual temperature changes.	Mandeville & Flenniken 1974; in Mercieca & Hiscock 2008

6.2.2 TAR PRODUCTION

The production of tar, a dark viscous substance distilled out of wood, roots or tree bark, requires the exclusion of oxygen and careful temperature control (Koller et al. 2001, 392). To meet these requirements, the process of tar production most often entails the indirect heating of wood or bark in a reducing environment (Groom et al. 2013, 48). Numerous examples of tar use in early prehistoric and ethnographic contexts have been published; utilization of the substance ranges from adhesives (Groom et al. 2013) to waterproofing (Lyford 1943, in: Schenck & Groom 2016) and even the use of tar as medicinal 'chewing gum' (Aveling & Heron 1999).

Evidence of prehistoric tar production in hearth pit structures is most often indirect (i.e. experimental or ethnographic as opposed to archaeological) and mainly concerns the production of birch bark tar. While plenty of research has been done on the production of tar and pitch in Palaeolithic and Mesolithic contexts (Grünberg 2002; Koller et al. 2001; Wadley 2010; Palmer 2007), in most instances surface hearths or raised structures - as opposed to pit structures - are suggested to be the most effective method of production. Nevertheless, some evidence can be found regarding the use of pits for tar distillation (Table 7).

FIGURE 32: AN EXPERIMENTAL PIT STRUCTURE USED FOR BIRCH BARK TAR PRODUCTION. FROM: GROOM ET AL. 2013, 57 (FIG. 8).

The traditional production of tar from *Cedrus libani* A. Rich (*Pinaceae*) in Southern Turkey involves the digging of two pits - one large (1m by 2m wide and 1,5m deep) firing compartment that contains the *Cedrus* wood, and a second smaller one that serves as a container for the tar (Kurt et al. 2008, 616). Wood is packed tightly into the firing pit and then covered with a thick layer of leaves and herbs, and a second layer consisting of mud. The firing compartment is subsequently ignited (including the tar-containing material!) and temperatures in the structure remain above 300°C until the fire is burnt up. Allowing time for the construction to cool down, the entire distillation process can take up to 15 days (op. cit. 617). Funnel-shaped pits from the Roman Iron Age found in Sweden show a comparable compartmentalization that separates the wood from the collection of the tar (Hjulström et al. 2006), as does a literary account of the Greek writer Theophrastus: in his *Enquiry Into Plants* he describes the production of tar in Macedonia and Syria, where pine-wood logs were heaped on a sloping piece of cleared ground and subsequently covered with earth after which they were fired. The collection of the end-product occurred in a small pit some distance down the slope (Hort 1916).

Since our Mesolithic hearth pits do not show the compartmentalization present in the abovementioned examples, a more accurate parallel might actually be found in the experimental research of Groom et al. (2013) and Pfeifer & Clausen (2016). In both experiments a pit structure was used for aceramic birch bark tar production; Groom et al. used turf, leaves and straw to cover the layer of birch bark (fig. 8), whereas the experiment by Pfeifer & Clausen covered the bark with sand and clay. Both experimental structures were heated by a fire on top of the covered pit. Unfortunately, the experiments were equally similar in their negative

outcome: in both cases the temperature reached inside the pit did not nearly become high enough for effective tar distillation.

How do our micromorphological observations fit the other evidence for the use of hearth pits as tar-production structures? The tar-like substances that were observed in multiple thin sections were, when possible to identify, attached to (or part of) of *pine* wood charcoal. At the moment it is, however, not possible to differentiate between micro-scale products of an intentional tar production process on the one hand, and the accidental by-products of a different activity on the other hand. Evidence shows that pine wood will, under oxygen-poor conditions, result in the tar-like substances observed, and these conditions are not unique to tar production (see *Ch. 6.2.3*). Indications for a reducing environment inside the pit structure have been observed as well, as has the intentional selection of certain wood taxa for combustion.

6.2.3 COOKING-RELATED PRACTICES

Evidence of hearth pit use related to food preparation is known from both archaeological as well as ethnographic sources. This evidence can be both direct (remains of the food itself) as well as indirect (artefacts and soil feature characteristics related to cooking) in nature.

While finds other than charred organic remains are very rare in the context of Mesolithic hearth pits, sporadic examples of (supposed) cooking stones are known from both Hemptens and the Veenkoloniën (Table 7). Direct evidence of (plant) food preparation in Dutch hearth pits falls into one of two categories: the presence of parenchymous tissue (associated with edible plant parts such as bulbs, tubers and roots) on the one hand, and that of hazelnut shells and other botanical macroremains on the other hand (*Chapter 2.2.2*). Remains of animal food such as burnt bone, have not been found in Dutch contexts. The analysis of hearth pit fills from Halskov (Denmark) has provided very similar results: remains of edible plants were recovered, but, with the exemption of one pit, none of the features that indicated burning contained (fragments of) stones (Kubiak-Martens 2002; Robinson & Harild 2002). Additional examples are known from Palaeoindian contexts in the northwestern North American Plains (9400BP) and the southern Plains (dating as early as 8000BP; Armstrong 1993, 13; Dering 1996; in: Wandsnider 1997, 32).

Ethnographic evidence of pit cooking is manifold, providing examples of the roasting of meat, cooking of plant foods and the roasting of nuts and seeds (Table 7). In a 1997 publication, LuAnn Wandsnider provides an extensive overview of hearth pit cooking practiced by several indigenous North American hunter-gatherer and (small) agricultural societies. Plant food processing generally appears to be focused on inulin-rich plant parts such as tubers and roots; by processing large amounts of camas, agave or lily bulbs, for instance, people managed to take advantage of an energy-rich and durable food source that is abundantly available in an otherwise resource-poor area (Wandsnider 1997, 24; Kubiak-Martens 2002,30; Spikins 2000, 38). Moreover, there are different ways in which plant foods are pit-cooked: sometimes roots are roasted directly in the coals of a hearth or wrapped in leaves that are put in hot ashes inside a pit (Kubiak-Martens 2002, 30), while another practice involves wrapping the food in birch bark and putting it in a pit, after which the pit is filled with hot sand and a fire is built on top of it (Kari 1995).

As for the possibility of roasting of nuts and seeds in hearth pits, evidence for this practice can be found in both archaeological and ethnographic contexts, as well as experimental work (Table 7). There are some clear advantages for preparing nuts in this fashion: not only does roasting prolong the edibility (and storability) of large amounts of nuts and green fruits, roasting makes nuts also easier to crack and thus more readily consumable (Score & Mithen 2000, 511; Talalay et al. 1984, 351, in: Holst 2010; Turner 2014, 306). Moreover, nuts are reduced in volume and weight by processing (roasting) them, making them easier to transport and thus providing an organizational advantage for mobile groups of hunter-gatherers (Holst 2010, 2874). Roasting the nuts in a pit as opposed to an open fire has the clear advantage of containing them in a closed

context, thus ensuring a more even result, and preventing direct contact with the fire (which will cause the fruits to become inedible; López-Dóriga 2013; Score & Mithen 2000).

While direct evidence of meat preparation is lacking from archaeological hearth pit contexts, it is evident that meat can be, and *is* in currently existing societies, prepared in hearth pits (see Wandsnider 1997 for a substantial overview of examples). The chief of the North American Crow tribe describes the process of cooking in 'meat-holes' in great detail: the bottom of a deep pit would be covered with heated small boulders, which themselves would be covered with a thick layer of branches. Thick chunks of meat, sprinkled with water, were placed on top of this layer and then covered with more branches, then more meat, and so on, until the pit was filled. An animal hide was put on top of the pit, along with a layer of gravel and a small log fire, which was kept going by the men (Linderman 1962, 253; in: Wandsnider 1997, 19-20). What might remain archaeologically of such a practice, is a deep pit with a great amount of charcoal and charred organic remains in addition to the layer of boulders at the bottom. It is hard to say whether the meat itself would have left any residu, if at all.

An interesting additional observation concerns the common absence of heating rocks in hearth pit cooking (fig. 3). The presence of heated rocks appears to indicate that a certain temperature could be maintained inside the pit for a relatively long time (Wandsnider 1997, 28), but rock elements are not at all a prerequisite for pit-cooking, nor is the absence of heating rocks in archaeological contexts indicative of a *lack of cooking*. This might actually be predominantly the case for the practice of meat roasting.

FIGURE 33: THE PRESENCE OF ROCK ELEMENTS IN PITS USED FOR THE COOKING OF PLANT- AND ANIMAL PRODUCTS. FROM: WANDSNIDER 1997, 21 (FIG. 5).

Taking all the previously known evidence into account, how did the newly gathered micromorphological data contribute to the overall picture? Large amounts of charred plant tissues were indeed commonly observed in many of the thin sections. It is incredibly difficult (if not impossible), however, to reconstruct whether these charred remains are the remnants of plant foods that were cooked, or whether they represent the organic content of the natural subsoil (which was then charred for an unknown purpose). Charred botanical macroremains or parenchymous tissue have previously been identified in other research (*Chapter 2.2.2*), but soil micromorphology has not contributed more to the identification of the charred (non-woody)

remains.

The indirect indications for the presence of ash in Kampen (feature 75) might provide another link between the micromorphological observations and the cooking-hypothesis. As discussed earlier, cooking in hot ashes is a known practice, but the presence of an active fire *inside* a cooking pit has not been recorded in ethnographic literature. The possible presence of ash would in this case then not indicate *in situ* fire, but instead the deposition of hot ashes constituting the remains of a fire that was lit elsewhere. Another possibility, however, is that the ash entered the pit (and the subsoil) by accident, as a result of clearing the remains of a fire that was enkindled *on top* of the feature. This construction, in which a pit is filled with material on top of which a fire is lit, is more widely known in existing literature relating to traditional pit cooking. Moreover, the oxygen-starved environment inside a pit that is closed off from a nearby heat source has been recognized in the form of tar-like substances in multiple thin sections from all three sites. The presence of brown (incompletely charred) charcoal in a number of thin sections forms an additional indication for oxygen-poor conditions inside some of the hearth pits. A final micromorphological observation that might point towards the direction of the cooking-hypothesis is constituted by the large amounts of charred humus in feature 51-904 and the abundant uncharred organic remains in the top of feature 75, which have been interpreted by Huisman et al. (2019, 9-10) as the remains of topsoil turfs. The insulation these turfs would have provided (to control the influence of the fire on the pit contents), correlates with the function of similar layers/covers of sand or plant debris described in ethnographic studies on hearth pit cooking. Overall, there thus are quite a few significant micromorphological observations that support the interpretation of the features as being used for cooking-related practices.

6.2.4 THERMAL STONE PREPARATION

The fourth and final hypothesis of hearth pit use comprises the *heat treatment* of flint (and other siliceous rocks). When the material is subjected to heat, it is significantly easier to flake (reducing the force necessary up to 30%; Sollberger & Hester 1972, 181) and a sharper edge can be created, although the edge will become more prone to chipping (Solberger & Hester 1972; in Olausson & Larsson 1982, 277). It is not difficult to imagine these altered properties being greatly beneficial to a prehistoric flint knapper.

Evidence for the thermal preparation of flint in hearth pits is quite scarce, though some ethnographic and experimental studies can be found (see Table 7). In an experiment conducted by Mandeville & Flenniken in 1974, a pit approximately 60cm in diameter and ca. 70cm deep was dug (fig. 34a). A fire was lighted in the bottom of the pit and kept alight until an approximately 30 to 35cm thick layer of coals was formed. The coals were then covered with a thin layer of sand, on top of which the flint was placed. The flint was then covered with another layer of sand, and a second fire was built on top of this sand layer (which was again maintained until a layer of coals was built up). The pit was then finally covered with a 10cm thick layer of sand and allowed to cool down for approximately 20 hours (Mandeville & Flenniken 1974, 146). A maximum temperature of 325 °C was reached in the pit during the period the pit was capped off with sand (op. cit. 147).

The North American Shoshoni used a similar technique for stone preparation, burying the roughly knapped material in the ground after which a fire was lit on top of the pit. The material was left in the ground for multiple days after the fire had burnt out to ensure gradual temperature changes in the process of cooling (Olausson & Larsson 1982).

What these two examples have in common, apart from the use of fire and pits, is that low temperatures must be ensured inside of the pit. When flint is exposed to too much heat, the material will become extremely brittle and unusable. An oxygen-poor environment is not necessary for the heat treatment of the stone, but it is a logical consequence of the way the temperature is managed (by creating insulating layers of earth or sand).

The results of the micromorphological analysis contribute to the plausibility of this functional hypothesis as follows: the alternation of layers with large amounts of charred organic material and wood charcoal on the one hand, and cleaner layers of sand on the other, has been observed in the pit features from Dronten. With the removal of the heated flint from the pit, one would expect the internal structure of the pit to be disturbed, mixing the layers of cleaner and charcoal-rich material in the process. This matches the micromorphological observations: none of the layers identified have clear boundaries, being very irregular ('messy') in appearance instead. In the suggested feature of Mandeville & Flenniken, however, the lower thick layer of coals remains fairly undisturbed. Since there is no clear reason to clear out this bottom layer of coals from the pit, the amount of wood charcoal in the thin sections should to some extent reflect the original concentration of coals in the feature. This is not the case; while charred organic material is indeed abundant, the remnants of wood charcoal are not as commonly present and, when present, significantly fragmented.

Another observation that suggests the stone-heating activity to be plausible, are the indirect indications for the presence of ash as seen in the illuviated clay and powdered charcoal from Kampen (feature 75). Ash is the byproduct of a well-oxygenated fire, so if ash was indeed present in this pit, this would mean that either the remnants of such a fire were deposited in the hearth pit, or that a fire was lit *in situ*. The flint-preparation hypothesis would be an (anthropogenic) scenario in which the presence of fire *in the feature* would make sense. There is, however, another process that would explain the presence of ash; to access the pit contents, the subsoil as well as possible remains of a surface fire will have been disturbed and mixed together to a certain extent. This might have caused ash to enter the pit structure and the subsoil, even though fire was never present in the feature itself. The micromorphological observation of the (indirect) presence of ash is thus not definite evidence for Mesolithic flint heating.

FIGURE 34: EXPERIMENTAL EXAMPLES OF STRUCTURES USED FOR THERMAL FLINT PREPARATION. MERCECA & HISCOCK 2008, 2637 (FIG. 3).

Revisiting the hypotheses discussed above, it is important to conclude with the observation that it is difficult to distinguish either of the possible hearth pit functions on the basis of micromorphological characteristics alone. The micromorphology seems to support more than one of the potential scenarios, and without any baseline data about the micromorphological 'residue' left behind by the various processes, any differentiation between them will remain impossible.

6.3 IMPLICATIONS FOR HUNTER-GATHERER STUDIES

The previous paragraphs have demonstrated that micromorphological observations indicate the probability of one of three scenarios, which all require a significant time and resource investment: all hypotheses require the careful maintenance of fire and a long period in which the feature is left to process its contents.

If one of the proposed functions does indeed turn out to be related to the Mesolithic hearth pits in the Netherlands, this has important implications for our perception of prehistoric hunter-gatherer behaviour in this part of the world. In the light of the discussion on either the passive adaptation or the active modification of the landscape by hunter-gatherers (*Chapter 2.1*), the scale on which hearth pits have been created would certainly argue in favour of the actively modifying hunter-gatherer. Moreover, the time invested in the use of the features (though we still cannot be sure of their function) in combination with the large number of times the sites have been revisited, sketches a (seasonally?) mobile society using fixed locations in the landscape for established purposes. While there are in this case no indications of resource management such as the firing of vegetation, the act of pit-digging⁴ at a significant spatial and chronological scale can be seen as a different form of landscape modification.

The idea of repeated location use by hunter-gatherers is hardly new; mobile hunter-gatherer societies are known to use the same travel routes on a seasonal basis (Binford 1980; Lovis & Donahue 2011), setting up camp at previously used and known sites and constructing cache pits for storage along the way (Cunningham 2011). The large concentrations of hearth pits on locations that have (based on direct dating of the features) been revisited for many centuries might be examples of sites along such traditional travel routes. This interpretation has interesting consequences for the way Mesolithic communities are perceived in the Netherlands; it shifts the focus from individual sites at fixed locations in the prehistoric landscape (as is currently the case) towards a more dynamic perspective in which the Dutch hearth pit sites are part of a large network of hunter-gatherer spatial knowledge that stretches beyond modern boundaries.

6.4 THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL METHOD IN MESOLITHIC ARCHAEOLOGY

6.4.1 REFLECTING ON METHODOLOGY

The final section of this thesis will evaluate the use of soil micromorphology in hearth pit research, which was one of the objectives of the study. The methodology used in the current research does not stand on its own; recent ethnographic, experimental and archaeological work on early prehistoric combustion features (and their micromorphological characteristics) has provided a well-established framework for the comparison of charred organic material and combustion residues as well as various indicators for the disturbance of fire residues (Mallol et al. 2013a; Mallol et al. 2013b).

Choosing a qualitative in favour of a quantitative approach has proven to be fruitful: the identification of the *presence* or *absence* of certain phenomena has made it possible to compare features within and between sites without getting lost in minor (quantitative) details. The availability of samples from the natural soil adjacent to some features was crucial in the analysis of the top part of hearth pits (which had not been possible before), and interesting observations such as the presence of tar-like substances, charred humus and ash-related displacement of clay were made in multiple thin sections.

⁴ If topsoil sods were indeed used as insulation material in hearth pits, the cutting of these turfs would of course constitute another type of small-scale landscape modification.

Some difficulties arose during the study as well, however. The thin sections selected for analysis were not always sampled with the intention of representing the hearth pit fill (as in the case of Hoge Vaart-A27), which to a certain extent 'hindered' the ability to compare observations. Moreover, the thin sections did not share the same size: while the samples from Hoge Vaart were quite large, the long thin sections from Dronten provided less visibility. The latter samples, however, did always comprise a continuous profile, which was not consistently the case for the other thin sections.

A final challenge was formed by the translation of micromorphological observations into cultural interpretation. This will always remain a difficult issue, but a proper starting point might be to remain well aware of the scale of observation and the inferences one needs to make to come to a culturally meaningful interpretation.

6.4.2 SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

"Finding out to what extent these reconstructions are valid must be one of the objectives of future study." - (Groenendijk 1987, 99)

"Although we have already built a substantive record for the Netherlands, there is still a lot to learn." (Peeters & Niekus 2017, 237)

Though the research presented in this thesis has certainly contributed to our knowledge on the function of Mesolithic hearth pits, the search for definitive answers does still not end here. In line with the previous recommendations of Groenendijk (1987) and Peeters & Niekus (2017), a series of suggestions for future investigation will therefore be made.

It is evident that the micromorphological data available to us at present are not sufficient to come to a well-rounded conclusion on the use of hearth pit features. While the use of qualitative as opposed to quantitative microscopic analysis has proven fruitful in identifying the presence of a number of interesting observations (*Chapter 5*), the available dataset is still not robust enough.

We know that most use-related hypotheses can be found somewhere in the ethnographic record. We also know that our micromorphological observations match the observations one would expect as the outcome of more than one of these hypotheses. The problem, however, is that it appears to be the case that multiple uses/functions leave the same macro- and microscopically observable residues. It would therefore be of great importance to create a baseline of micromorphological data from features of which the function and use is known. Because of this very reason, micromorphological research on hearth pits would benefit from more experimental work: known as well as hypothetical pit structures and uses can be replicated in a controlled study, after which the resulting soil profile can be sampled for very specific phenomena of which the genesis is known. One of the questions remaining unanswered after this study, for instance, concerns the origin of the thick horizon of charred humus present in the bottom of the pits. Testing out the effects of a nearby fire on layers of non-charred topsoil material might in this case be a good first step towards building a known set of processes responsible for certain micromorphological phenomena.

In an ideal situation there would also be the opportunity to sample ethnographic examples of hearth pits, as was done for (surface) fires made and abandoned by the Hadza of Tanzania (Mallol et al. 2007). Features from such contexts are intensively and expertly used, and thus provide a more realistic background to test certain hypotheses than experimental structures (in very controlled conditions). This might not be very feasible, however: aside from the obvious difficulties in finding time and money for such an endeavour, the number of societies that use hearth pits similar to our archaeological examples is very scarce.

Many of the suggestions for future research proposed by Mallol et al. (2017, 324-325) in the context of research on combustion structures, apply to the micromorphological investigation of Mesolithic hearth pits as well. While a broad range of scientific techniques (including FTIR and organic chemistry) have been used in investigating the hearth pit contents, the total number of pits these techniques were used on is only very small. To aid the possibility of comparison between features, it might therefore be useful to, taking into account the costs, select one technique to sample/measure multiple hearth pits. The techniques applied should be integrated well, preferably through clear communication between experts.

Whatever future research might entail, the fact is that if we continue along the same path - sampling in the same fashion as we are now and studying our thin sections with the same knowledge we have at present, we will end up with results similar to previous analyses and therefore continue to ask the same unanswered questions. For such a common and widespread phenomenon as that of Mesolithic hearth pits, this would mean the loss of a great opportunity to expand our knowledge on early prehistoric hunter-gatherer societies.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The main aim of this study has been to gain insight into the use and function of Mesolithic hearth pits features that are found consistently around the Netherlands. While existing research shed light on the spatial configuration of these pits, their chronological distribution and general morphology, information on the exact function of these features remained unavailable. Moreover, an overview of inter- and intrasite variation between hearth pits was lacking. By using *soil micromorphology* in the form of a quantitative approach, the analysis in this study has demonstrated that the hearth pits might have been used for tar production, food preparation or the thermal preparation of lithics. All three functions require low temperatures in addition to an oxygen-starved environment. It is difficult to differentiate between these hypotheses on the basis of micromorphological observations, since the characteristics observed could theoretically be the result of either of the three activities. Moreover, a clear corpus of baseline observations specifically related to the various functions is currently not available. Still, there seems to be a certain degree of variation among the features, with tar-like substances and charred topsoil material only being present in a select few pits. Whether these differences are related to meaningful functional variation or to post-depositional influences remains unclear. Local geology or hydrology might also be partially responsible. Nevertheless, the large amounts of features on long revisited sites that required a certain amount of time investment and a temporal lack of mobility indicates the importance of the hearth pits in Mesolithic hunter-gatherer communities. It is suggested that the pit clusters might be representative of prehistoric travel routes.

In the light of future research it is recommended that a set of baseline micromorphological observations is collected through either experimental work or the sampling of features in the context of ethnographic study. Moreover, the scientific techniques already used on a small number of hearth pits should be implemented on more features, to facilitate comparison. Even though this study has not been successful in providing a conclusive answer to the question on the function and use of hearth pit features, it gives valuable insight into some possible interpretations that can be tested in a very targeted fashion. Mesolithic hearth pits should remain in our focus, under the lens.

REFERENCES

- Achard-Corompt, N., Ghesquière, E., Laurelut, C., Remy, A., Isabelle, R., Riquier, V. and Sanson, L., 2017. Des fosses par centaines, une nouvelle vision du Mésolithique en Champagne: analyse et cartographie d'un phénomène insoupçonné. In: N. Achard-Corompt, E. Ghesquière & V. Riquier (eds.), *Creuser au Mésolithique - Digging in the Mesolithic, actes de la séance de la Société préhistorique française (Châlons-en-Champagne, 29-30 mars 2016), Séances de la Société préhistorique française*, vol. 12, Société Préhistorique Française, Paris, 11-25.
- Armstrong, S.W., 1993. *Alder Complex kitchens: experimental replication of Paleoindian cooking facilities*. (PhD Dissertation), University of Idaho.
- Aveling E.M. & Heron, C., 1999. Chewing tar in the early Holocene. *Antiquity*, 73(281), 579–584.
- Bell, M., Manning, S. & Nayling, N., 2009. Dating the coastal Mesolithic of western Britain: a test of some evolutionary assumptions. In: Crombé, P., Van Strydonck, M., Sergant, J., Boudin, M. and Bats, M. (eds.) *Chronology and evolution within the Mesolithic of north-west Europe: proceedings of an international meeting, Brussels, May 30th-June 1st 2007*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing, Newcastle, 615-634.
- Bennett, K.D., Simonson, W.D. & Peglar, S.M., 1990. Fire and man in post-glacial woodlands of eastern England. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 17(6), 635-642.
- Binford, L.R., 1980. Willow smoke and dogs' tails: hunter-gatherer settlement systems and archaeological site formation. *American antiquity*, 45(1), 4-20.
- Bishop, R.R., Church, M.J. & Rowley-Conwy, P.A., 2015. Firewood, food and human niche construction: the potential role of Mesolithic hunter-gatherers in actively structuring Scotland's woodlands. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 108, 51-75.
- Blinkhorn, E., Lawton -Matthews, E. & Warren, G. 2017. Digging and filling pits in the Mesolithic of England and Ireland: comparative perspectives on a widespread practice. In: N. Achard-Corompt, E. Ghesquière & V. Riquier (eds.), *Creuser au Mésolithique / Digging in the Mesolithic: Actes de la séance de la Société préhistorique française de Châlons-en-Champagne (29-30 mars 2016). Séances de la Société préhistorique française*, vol. 12, Société Préhistorique Française, Paris, 211-224.
- Bonsall, C., Radovanović, I., Roksandic, M., Cook, G.T., Higham, T., Pickard, C. & Boroneanț, V., 2008. Dating burial practices and architecture at Lepenski Vir. In: Bonsall C, Boroneanț V, Radovanović I, editors. *The Iron Gates in Prehistory*. Oxford: Archaeopress, 175-204.
- Borić, D., 2002. The Lepenski Vir conundrum: reinterpretation of the Mesolithic and Neolithic sequences in the Danube Gorges. *Antiquity*, 76(294), 1026-1039.
- Bos, J.A. & Dijkshoorn, M., 2019. *Vegetatie en landschapsreconstructie*. In: Geerts, R.C.A, Müller, A., Niekus, M.J.L.Th. & Vermue, F.J., 2019. *Mesolithische kampen onder de oever van het Reevediep. Een archeologische opgraving van vindplaats 9 in het tracé van de hoogwatergeul in het Reevediep te Kampen*. ADC monografie 26, 48-58.
- Bos, J.A. & Urz, R., 2003. Late Glacial and early Holocene environment in the middle Lahn river valley (Hessen, central-west Germany) and the local impact of early Mesolithic people—pollen and macrofossil evidence. *Vegetation History and Archaeobotany*, 12(1), 19-36.

Bos, J.A., Huisman, D.J., Kiden, P., Hoek, W.Z. & Van Geel, B., 2005. Early Holocene environmental change in the Kreekrak area (Zeeland, SW-Netherlands): a multi-proxy analysis. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 227(4), 259-289.

Bos, J.A., van Geel, B., Groenewoudt, B.J. & Lauwerier, R.C.M., 2006. Early Holocene environmental change, the presence and disappearance of early Mesolithic habitation near Zutphen (The Netherlands). *Vegetation History and Archaeobotany*, 15(1), 27-43.

Botanical Society of Britain and Ireland, 2019. *Online Atlas of the British and Irish Flora*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.brc.ac.uk/plantatlas/content/acknowledgements>> [Accessed on 12th of September 2019]

Bouma, J., Fox, C.A., Miedema, R., 1990. Micromorphology of hydromorphic soils: applications for soil genesis and land evaluation. In: Douglas, L.A. (Ed.), *Soil Micromorphology: A Basic and Applied Science*. Developments in Soil Science 19. Elsevier, Amsterdam, 257-278.

Bouman, M.T.I.J., & Bos, J.A.A., 2012. 10. Paleoecologie. In: Hamburg, T., Müller, A. & Quadflieg, B. (eds.), *Mesolithisch Swifterbant. Mesolithisch gebruik van een duin ten zuiden van Swifterbant (8300–5000 v. Chr.). Een archeologische opgraving in het tracé van de N23*, 299-340.

Boyd, W.E. & Kenworthy, J.B., 1991. The use of wood as a natural resource at a Scottish Mesolithic site. *Glasgow Archaeological Journal*, 17(17), 11-24.

Breider, R., 2013. *Haardkuilen en plantgebruik in het Mesolithicum: over botanische resten in haardkuilen en wat ze impliceren over het gebruik van deze kuilen. Een overzicht en vergelijking van tien Nederlandse en Belgische vindplaatsen*. (Ba Thesis), Rijksuniversiteit Groningen: Groningen, The Netherlands.

Brown, T., 1997. Clearances and clearings: deforestation in Mesolithic/Neolithic Britain. *Oxford Journal of Archaeology*, 16(2), 133-146.

Bush, M.B., 1988. Early Mesolithic disturbance: a force on the landscape. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 15(4), 453-462.

Canti, M.G., 2017. Charred plant remains. Archaeological soil and sediment micromorphology: Oxford, Wiley-Blackwell, 141-142.

Childe, V.G., 1925. *The dawn of European civilization*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.

Colombaroli, D., Vannièrè, B., Emmanuel, C., Magny, M. & Tinner, W., 2008. Fire—vegetation interactions during the Mesolithic—Neolithic transition at Lago dell'Accesa, Tuscany, Italy. *The Holocene*, 18(5), 679-692.

Coughlan, M.R., 2015. Traditional fire-use, landscape transition, and the legacies of social theory past. *Ambio* 44(8), 705-717.

Courty, M.A., Goldberg, P. and Macphail, R., 1989. *Soils and micromorphology in archaeology*. Cambridge, UK.

Crombé, P., Sergeant, J., Robinson, E. & De Reu, J., 2011. Hunter–gatherer responses to environmental change during the Pleistocene–Holocene transition in the southern North Sea basin: Final Palaeolithic–Final Mesolithic land use in northwest Belgium. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 30(3), 454-471.

- Crombé, P., Robinson, E., Van Strydonck, M. & Boudin, M., 2012. Radiocarbon dating of Mesolithic open-air sites in the coversand area of the north-west European plain: problems and prospects. *Archaeometry* 55(3), 545-562.
- Crombé, P., Langohr, R. & Louwagie, G., 2015. Mesolithic hearth-pits: fact or fantasy? A reassessment based on the evidence from the sites of Doel and Verrebroek (Belgium). *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 61, 158-171.
- Cunningham, P., 2011. Caching your savings: the use of small-scale storage in European prehistory. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 30(2), 135-144.
- Czarnik, S.A., 1976. The theory of the Mesolithic in European archaeology. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society*, 120(1), 59-66.
- Dering, J.P., 1996. Utilization of geophytes on the Southern Plains: Identification and assessment of a once archaeologically "invisible" plant resource. In: *Abstracts of the 61st Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology*.
- Dibble, H.L., Berna, F., Goldberg, P., McPherron, S.P., Mentzer, S., Niven, L., Richter, D., Sandgathe, D., Théry-Parisot, I. & Turq, A., 2009. A preliminary report on Pech de l'Azé IV, layer 8 (Middle Paleolithic, France). *PaleoAnthropology*, 2009, 182-219.
- Duarte, C., Iriarte, E., Diniz, M., & Arias, P., 2017. The microstratigraphic record of human activities and formation processes at the Mesolithic shell midden of Poças de São Bento (Sado Valley, Portugal). *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences*, 1-27.
- Dunham, S.B., 2000 Cache pits: ethnohistory, archaeology, and the continuity of tradition. In: Nassaney, M. & Johnson, E.S. (eds.). *Interpretations of Native North American life: material contributions to ethnohistory*; Gainesville; U. Florida Press: 225-260
- Eerkens, J.W., 2000. Practice makes within 5% of perfect: visual perception, motor skills, and memory in artifact variation. *Current Anthropology*, 41(4), 663-668.
- Eerkens, J.W. & Bettinger, R.L., 2001. Techniques for assessing standardization in artifact assemblages: can we scale material variability?. *American Antiquity*, 66(3), 493-504.
- Eerkens, J.W. & Lipo, C.P., 2005. Cultural transmission, copying errors, and the generation of variation in material culture and the archaeological record. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 24(4), 316-334.
- Exaltus, R., 2001. Deel 14 Micromorfologie: onderzoek aan slijpplaatmonsters van grondsporen. In: Hogestijn, J.W.H. & Peeters, J.H.M. (eds.), *De mesolithische en vroeg-neolithische vindplaats Hoge Vaart-A27 (Flevoland)*, Amersfoort, Rijksdienst voor het Oudheidkundig Bodemonderzoek (Rapportage Archeologische Monumentenzorg, 79).
- Fries, J.E., Jansen, D. & Niekus, M.J.T., 2013. Fire in a hole! First results of the Oldenburg-Eversten excavation and some notes on Mesolithic hearth pits and hearth-pit sites. *Settlement and Coastal Research in the Southern North Sea Region*, 36, 99-110.
- Garvey, R. & Bettinger, R.L., 2014. Adaptive and ecological approaches to the study of hunter-gatherers. In: Cummings, V., Jordan, P. & Zvelebil, M. (eds.) *The Oxford Handbook of the Archaeology and Anthropology of Hunter-Gatherers*, 69-91.

- Geerts, R.C.A, Müller, A., Niekus, M.J.L.Th. & Vermue, F.J., 2019. *Mesolithische kampen onder de oever van het Reevediep. Een archeologische opgraving van vindplaats 9 in het tracé van de hoogwatergeul in het Reevediep te Kampen*. ADC monografie 26.
- Goldberg, P., Weiner, S., Bar-Yosef, O., Xu, Q. & Liu, J., 2001. Site formation processes at Zhoukoudian, China. *Journal of Human Evolution*, 41(5), 483-530.
- Goldberg, P. & Aldeias, V., 2018. Why does (archaeological) micromorphology have such little traction in (geo) archaeology?. *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences*, 10(2), 269-278.
- Granai, S., & N. Achard-Corompt. Environnement, datation et fonctionnement des fosses mésolithiques de Recy-Saint-Martin-sur-le-Pré «le mont Grenier-Parc de Référence»(Marne): les réponses des malacofaunes continentales. In: N. Achard-Corompt, E. Ghesquière & V. Riquier (eds.), *Creuser au Mésolithique / Digging in the Mesolithic: Actes de la séance de la Société préhistorique française de Châlons-en-Champagne (29-30 mars 2016). Séances de la Société préhistorique française*, vol. 12, Société Préhistorique Française, Paris, 69-86.
- Grant, M.J., Hughes, P.D. & Barber, K.E., 2014. Climatic influence upon early to mid-Holocene fire regimes within temperate woodlands: a multi-proxy reconstruction from the New Forest, southern England. *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 29(2), 175-188.
- Groenendijk, H.A., 1987. Mesolithic hearth-pits in the Veenkoloniën (prov. Groningen, the Netherlands), defining a specific use of fire in the Mesolithic. *Palaeohistoria* 29, 85-102.
- Groenendijk, H.A., 2004. Middle Mesolithic occupation on the extensive site NP3 in the peat reclamation district of Groningen, the Netherlands. In: Crombé, P. & Vermeersch, P.M. (eds.), *Acts of the XIVth UISPP congress, University of Liège, Belgium, 2-8 September 2001, Section 7, The Mesolithic*, Oxford (BAR International Series 1302), 19-26.
- Groenendijk, H.A., Mook-Kamps, E., Smit, J.L. & Jansma, E., 1997. *Op zoek naar de horizon: het landschap van Oost-Groningen en zijn bewoners tussen 8000 voor Chr. en 1000 na Chr.* Regio-Project.
- Groenendijk, H.A. & Smit, J., 1990. Mesolithische Herdstellen: Erfahrungen eines Brennversuchs. *Archäologische Informationen*, 13(2), 213-220.
- Groom, P., Schenck, T. & Pedersen, G.M., 2013. Experimental explorations into the aceramic dry distillation of *Betula pubescens* (downy birch) bark tar. *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences*, 7(1), 47-58.
- Grøn, O., Kuznetsov, O. & Klokkernes, T., 2002. The tent in the middle of the world. In *Hunter-gatherer Studies and the Reshaping of Anthropology. Ninth International Conference on Hunting and Gathering Societies*.
- Grünberg J.M., 2002. Middle Palaeolithic birch-bark pitch. *Antiquity* 66:15–16
- Hamburg, T., Müller, A. & Quadflieg, B., 2012. Mesolithisch Swifterbant. Mesolithisch gebruik van een duin ten zuiden van Swifterbant (8300–5000 v. Chr.). Een archeologische opgraving in het tracé van de N23.
- Hielkema, J.B., 2006. Sporen en vondsten; datering en verspreiding. In: Hielkema, J.B. (ed.), *Jager-verzamelaars langs de Wâldwei. Een archeologisch onderzoek van een vindplaats uit het Mesolithicum, het Midden-Neolithicum en de Late IJzertijd/Romeinse Tijd bij Hempens, gemeente Leeuwarden (Fr.)*, Groningen: ARC, 27-54.

- Hjulström, B., Isaksson, S. & Henniuss, A., 2006. Organic geochemical evidence for pine tar production in middle Eastern Sweden during the Roman Iron Age. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 33(2), 283-294.
- Hoek, W.Z., 1997. Late-glacial and early Holocene climatic events and chronology of vegetation development in the Netherlands. *Vegetation History and Archaeobotany*, 6(4), 197-213.
- Hogestijn, J.W.H. & Peeters, J.H.M., 2001 (eds.). De mesolithische en vroeg-neolithische vindplaats Hoge Vaart-A27 (Flevoland). *Rapportage Archeologische Monumentenzorg*, 79.
- Holst, D., 2010. Hazelnut economy of early Holocene hunter-gatherers: a case study from Mesolithic Duvensee, northern Germany. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 37(11), 2871-2880.
- Hörnberg, G., Bohlin, E., Hellberg, E., Bergman, I., Zackrisson, O., Olofsson, A., Wallin, J.E. & Pässe, T., 2006. Effects of Mesolithic hunter-gatherers on local vegetation in a non-uniform glacio-isostatic land uplift area, northern Sweden. *Vegetation History and Archaeobotany*, 15(1), 13-26.
- Hort, A., 1916. *Theophrastus' Enquiry into Plants and minor works On Odours and Weather Signs* (Loeb Classical Library). London: William Heinemann.
- Huisman, D.J. & Deeben, J., 2009. Soil features. In: Huisman, D.J. (Ed.), *Degradation of Archaeological Remains*. SdU, Den Haag, 147-176.
- Huisman, D.J., Braadbaart, F., van Wijk, I.M. & van Os, B.J.H., 2012. Ashes to ashes, charcoal to dust: micromorphological evidence for ash-induced disintegration of charcoal in Early Neolithic (LBK) soil features in Elsloo (The Netherlands). *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 39(4), 994-1004.
- Huisman, D.J., Niekus, M.T., Peeters, J.H.M., Geerts, R.C.A. and Müller, A., 2019. Deciphering the complexity of a 'simple' mesolithic phenomenon: Indicators for construction, use and taphonomy of pit hearths in Kampen (the Netherlands). *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 109, 104987.
- Huizer, J., 2019. 3.2 Fysische geografie. In: Geerts, R.C.A, Müller, A., Niekus, M.J.L.Th. & Vermue, F.J., 2019. *Mesolithische kampen onder de oever van het Reevediep. Een archeologische opgraving van vindplaats 9 in het tracé van de hoogwatergeul in het Reevediep te Kampen*. ADC monografie 26, 35-45.
- Ilson, P.J. (ed.), 2013. *Jagers en verzamelaars bij Scheemderzwaag-Scheemda en -Opdiep*. Raap-Rapport 2310, Raap Archeologisch Adviesbureau.
- Innes, J.B. & Blackford, J.J., 2003. The ecology of late Mesolithic woodland disturbances: model testing with fungal spore assemblage data. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 30(2), 185-194.
- Innes, J.B., Blackford, J.J. & Rowley-Conwy, P.A., 2013. Late Mesolithic and early Neolithic forest disturbance: A high resolution palaeoecological test of human impact hypotheses. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 77, 80-100.
- Kari, P.R., 1995. *Tanaina Plantore Denaina Ketuna. An ethnobotany of the Denaina Indians of Southcentral Alaska, 4th edn*, Alaska Native Language Center, University of Alaska. Fairbanks.
- Karkanias, P. & Goldberg, P., 2018. *Reconstructing Archaeological Sites: Understanding the Geoarchaeological Matrix*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kedar, Y. and Barkai, R., 2019. The Significance of Air Circulation and Hearth Location at Paleolithic Cave Sites. *Open Quaternary*, 5(1).

- Koller, J., Baumer, U. & Mania, D., 2001. High-tech in the Middle Palaeolithic: Neandertal-manufactured pitch identified. *European Journal of Archaeology*, 4(3), 385-397.
- Kooistra, L.J., 2011. 11 Houtskool en houtgebruik. In: Lohof, E., Hamburg, T. & Flamman, J., 2011. *Steentijd opgespoord. Archeologisch onderzoek in het tracé van de Hanzelijn-Oude Land*. Combined Archol rapport & ADC rapport 138, 483-496.
- Kooistra, L.J., 2012. 14 Houtskool uit mesolithische kuilen. In: Hamburg, T., Müller, A. & Quadflieg, B. (eds.), *Mesolithisch Swifterbant. Mesolithisch gebruik van een duin ten zuiden van Swifterbant (8300–5000 v. Chr.)*. Een archeologische opgraving in het tracé van de N23, 375-386.
- Kubiak-Martens, L., 2002. New evidence for the use of root foods in pre-agrarian subsistence recovered from the late Mesolithic site at Halsskov, Denmark. *Vegetation History and Archaeobotany*, 11(1-2), 23-32.
- Kubiak-Martens, L., Kooistra, L.I. & Langer, J.J., 2011. 12 Mesolithische teerproductie in Hattemerbroek, in: Lohof, E., Hamburg, T. & Flamman, J. (eds.), *Steentijd opgespoord. Archeologisch onderzoek in het tracé van de Hanzelijn-Oude Land*. Combined Archol rapport & ADC rapport 138, 497-512.
- Kubiak-Martens, L., Langer, J.J. & Kooistra, L.I., 2012.. 11 Plantenresten en teer in haardkuilen. In: Hamburg, T., Müller, A. & Quadflieg, B. (eds.), *Mesolithisch Swifterbant. Mesolithisch gebruik van een duin ten zuiden van Swifterbant (8300–5000 v. Chr.)*. Een archeologische opgraving in het tracé van de N23, 341-360.
- Kurt, Y., Kaçar, M.S. & Isik, K., 2008. Traditional tar production from *Cedrus libani* A. Rich on the Taurus Mountains in southern Turkey. *Economic Botany*, 62(4), 615-620.
- Lawton-Matthews, E., & Warren, G., 2015. Pits in the Irish Mesolithic. In: Bicho, N., Detry, C., Price, T.D. & Cunha, E. (eds.), *Muge150: The 150th Anniversary of the Discovery of Mesolithic Shellmiddens*, Cambridge Scholars Publishing, Vol. 2, 139-152.
- Linderman, F.B., 1962. *Plenty-coups, chief of the Crows*. University of Nebraska Press, Lincoln.
- Lohof, E., Hamburg, T. & Flamman, J., 2011. *Steentijd opgespoord. Archeologisch onderzoek in het tracé van de Hanzelijn-Oude Land*. Combined Archol rapport & ADC rapport, 138.
- López-Dóriga, I.L., 2015. An experimental approach to the taphonomic study of charred hazelnut remains in archaeological deposits. *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences*, 7(1), 39-45.
- Louwe Kooijmans, L.P. (ed.), 2001. *Hardinxveld-Giessendam De Bruin: een kampplaats uit het Laat-Mesolithicum en het begin van de Swifterbant-cultuur (5500-4450 v. Chr.)*. ROB: Rapportage Archeologische Monumentenzorg 88, Amersfoort.
- Louwe Kooijmans, L.P. (ed.), 2001. *Hardinxveld-Giessendam, Polderweg. Een jachtkamp uit het Laat-Mesolithicum, 5500-5000 v. Chr.* ROB: Rapportage Archeologische Monumentenzorg, 83, Amersfoort.
- Lovis, W.A. & Donahue, R.E., 2011. Space, information and knowledge: Ethnocartography and North American boreal forest hunter-gatherers. *Information and its role in hunter-gatherer bands*, 5, 59-88.
- Lucas, G., 2018. *Writing the Past: Knowledge and Literary production in Archaeology*. New York: Routledge.

- Lyford, C.A., 1943. *Ojibwa crafts*. Bureau of Indian Affairs, Lawrence, Kansas
- Macklin, M.G., Bonsall, C., Davies, F.M. & Robinson, M.R., 2000. Human-environment interactions during the Holocene: new data and interpretations from the Oban area, Argyll, Scotland. *The Holocene*, 10(1), 109-121.
- Macphail, R.I., Courty, M.A. & Goldberg, P., 1990. Soil micromorphology in archaeology. *Endeavour*, 14(4), 163-171.
- Mallol, C., Hernández, C.M., Cabanes, D., Sistiaga, A., Machado, J., Rodríguez, Á., Pérez, L. & Galván, B., 2013a. The black layer of Middle Palaeolithic combustion structures. Interpretation and archaeostratigraphic implications. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 40(5), 2515-2537.
- Mallol, C., Hernández, C.M., Cabanes, D., Machado, J., Sistiaga, A., Pérez, L. & Galván, B., 2013b. Human actions performed on simple combustion structures: an experimental approach to the study of Middle Palaeolithic fire. *Quaternary International*, 3-15.
- Mallol, C., Marlowe, F.W., Wood, B.M. & Porter, C.C., 2007. Earth, wind, and fire: ethnoarchaeological signals of Hadza fires. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 34(12), 2035-2052.
- Mallol, C., Mentzer, S.M. & Miller, C.E., 2017. 31 Combustion Features. In: Nicosia, C. & Stoops, G. (eds.) *Archaeological Soil and Sediment Micromorphology*, Wiley-Blackwell, 299-330.
- Mandeville, M.D. & Flenniken, J.J., 1974. A Comparison of the Flaking Qualities of Nehawka Chert: Before and After Thermal Pretreatment. *Plains Anthropologist*, 19(64), 146-148.
- March, R.J., Lucquin, A., Joly, D., Ferreri, J.C. & Muhieddine, M., 2014. Processes of formation and alteration of archaeological fire structures: complexity viewed in the light of experimental approaches. *Journal of archaeological method and theory*, 21(1), 1-45.
- Marchand, G., 2017. Inventaire et interprétation des structures en creux des sites mésolithiques de France atlantique. In: N. Achard-Corompt, E. Ghesquière & V. Riquier (eds.), *Creuser au Mésolithique / Digging in the Mesolithic: Actes de la séance de la Société préhistorique française de Châlons-en-Champagne (29-30 mars 2016)*. *Séances de la Société préhistorique française*, vol. 12, Société Préhistorique Française, Paris, 129-146.
- Marguerie, D. & Hunot, J.Y., 2007. Charcoal analysis and dendrology: data from archaeological sites in north-western France. *Journal of archaeological science*, 34(9), 1417-1433.
- Mason, S.L.R., 2000. Fire and Mesolithic subsistence—managing oaks for acorns in northwest Europe?. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 164(1-4), 139-150.
- McParland, L.C., Collinson, M.E., Scott, A.C., Campbell, G. & Veal, R., 2010. Is vitrification in charcoal a result of high temperature burning of wood?. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 37(10), 2679-2687.
- Meier, T., 2012. 6.4 'Landscape', 'environment' and a vision of interdisciplinarity. In: Kluiving, S. & Guttman-Bond, E. (eds.) *Landscape Archaeology between Art and Science, From a Multi- to an Interdisciplinary Approach*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 503-514.
- Mentzer, S.M., 2014. Microarchaeological approaches to the identification and interpretation of combustion features in prehistoric archaeological sites. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*, 21(3), 616-668.

- Mercieca, A. & Hiscock, P., 2008. Experimental insights into alternative strategies of lithic heat treatment. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 35(9), 2634-2639.
- Milner, N, Conneller, C., & Taylor, B., 2018a. *Star Carr Volume 1: A Persistent Place in a Changing World*. York: White Rose University Press.
- Milner, N, Conneller, C., & Taylor, B., 2018b. *Star Carr Volume 2: Studies in Technology, Subsistence and Environment*. York: White Rose University Press.
- de Moor, J., 2012. 2 Fysische geografie. In: Hamburg, T., Müller, A. & Quadflieg, B. (eds.), *Mesolithisch Swifterbant. Mesolithisch gebruik van een duin ten zuiden van Swifterbant (8300–5000 v. Chr.). Een archeologische opgraving in het tracé van de N23*, 63-83.
- Moore, J., 2000. Forest fire and human interaction in the early Holocene woodlands of Britain. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 164(1-4), 125-137.
- Niekus, M., 2011. Ruimtelijke configuraties van mesolithische haardkuilen in Noord-Nederland. *Paleo-Aktueel*, 22, 16-23.
- Olausson, D.S. & Larsson, L., 1982. Testing for the presence of thermal pretreatment of flint in the Mesolithic and Neolithic of Sweden. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 9(3), 275-285.
- Opbroek, M. & Hamburg, T., 2012. 5. Sporen en Structuren. In: Hamburg, T., Müller, A. & Quadflieg, B. (eds.), *Mesolithisch Swifterbant. Mesolithisch gebruik van een duin ten zuiden van Swifterbant (8300–5000 v. Chr.). Een archeologische opgraving in het tracé van de N23*, 113-146.
- Orengo, H.A., Palet, J.M., Ejarque, A., Miras, Y. & Riera, S., 2013. Pitch production during the Roman period: an intensive mountain industry for a globalised economy?. *Antiquity*, 87(337), 802-814.
- Palmer, F., 2007. Die Entstehung von Birkenpech in einer Feuerstelle unter paläolithischen Bedingungen. *Mitteilungen der Gesellschaft für Urgeschichte*, 16, 75–83
- Peeters, J.H.M., 2007. Hoge Vaart-A27 in context: towards a model of Mesolithic-Neolithic land use dynamics as a framework for archaeological heritage management: Amsterdam.
- Peeters, J.H.M., 2009. Occupation continuity” and “behavioural discontinuity”: abrupt changes in forager land-use at the Mid/Late Atlantic boundary in the Flevoland Polders (The Netherlands). In Crombé, P., Van Strydonck, M., Sergant, J., Boudin, M. & Bats, M. (eds.), *Chronology and Evolution within the Mesolithic of North-West Europe. Proceedings of an International Meeting, Brussels, May 30th-June 1st*, 693-708.
- Peeters, J.H.M., Hanraets, E., Hogestijn, J.W.H. & Jansma, E., 2001. Deel 12. Dateringen: ¹⁴C-analyse en dendrochronologie. In: Hogestijn, J.W.H. & Peeters, J.H.M. (eds.), *De mesolithische en vroeg-neolithische vindplaats Hoge Vaart-A27 (Flevoland)*, Rapportage Archeologische Monumentenzorg 79, Amersfoort, ROB.
- Peeters, J.H.M, & Hogestijn, J.W.H., 2001. Deel 20. Op de grens van land en water: jagers-visser-verzamelaars in een verdrinkend landschap. In: Hogestijn, J.W.H. & Peeters, J.H.M. (eds.), *De mesolithische en vroeg-neolithische vindplaats Hoge Vaart-A27 (Flevoland)*, Rapportage Archeologische Monumentenzorg 79, Amersfoort, ROB.
- Peeters, J.H.M. & Niekus, M. 2017, Mesolithic pit hearths in the northern Netherlands. Function, time-depth and behavioural context. In: N. Achard-Corompt, E. Ghesquière & V. Riquier (eds.), *Creuser au Mésolithique / Digging in the Mesolithic: Actes de la séance de la Société*

préhistorique française de Châlons-en-Champagne (29-30 mars 2016). Séances de la Société préhistorique française, vol. 12, Société Préhistorique Française, Paris, 225-239.

Peeters, J., Raemaekers, D., Devriendt, I.I.J.A.L.M., Hoebe, P.W., Niekus, M., Nobles, G.R. and Schepers, M., 2017. *Paradise Lost? Insights into the early prehistory of the Netherlands from development-led archaeology*. Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed.

Perry, D. W., 1997. The archaeology of hunter-gatherers: plant use in the Dutch Mesolithic. A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy, Department of Anthropology, New York University, May 1997. Ann Harbor, Michigan: UMI Dissertation Services.

Perry, D., 2002. Preliminary results of an archaeobotanical analysis of Mesolithic sites in the Veenkoloniën, Province of Groningen, the Netherlands. In: Mason, S.L.M. & Hather, G.J. (eds.), *Hunter-gatherer archaeobotany: Perspectives from the northern temperate zone*, 108-116.

Pfeifer, W. & Claussen, M., 2016. Experiments on possible Stone Age glue types. In: Hurcombe, L. & Cunningham, P. (eds.) *The Life Cycle of Structures in Experimental Archaeology: An Object Biography Approach*, Sidestone Press, 115–127.

Price, T.D., 1987. The Mesolithic of Western Europe. *Journal of World Prehistory*, 1(3), 225-305.

Preston, P.R. & Kador, T., 2018. Approaches to Interpreting Mesolithic Mobility and Settlement in Britain and Ireland. *Journal of World Prehistory*, 1-25.

Ramenofsky, A.F. & Steffen, A., 1998. Units as tools of measurement. In: Ramenofsky, A.F. & Steffen, A. (eds.), *Unit issues in Archaeology*, 3-17.

Robinson, D.E. and Harild, J.A., 2002. Archaeobotany of an early Ertebölle (late Mesolithic) site at Halsskov, Zealand, Denmark. In: Mason, S.L.M. & Hather, G.J. (eds.), *Hunter-gatherer archaeobotany. Perspectives from the northern temperate zone.*, 84-95.

De Roller, G.J., 2006. Hout. In: Hielkema, J.B. (ed.), *Jager-verzamelaars langs de Wâldwei. Een archeologisch onderzoek van een vindplaats uit het Mesolithicum, het Midden-Neolithicum en de Late IJzertijd/Romeinse Tijd bij Hempens, gemeente Leeuwarden (Fr.)*, Groningen: ARC, 167-180.

Score, D. & Mithen, S., 2000. The experimental roasting of hazelnuts. In: Mithen, S. (Ed.), *Hunter-Gatherer Landscape Archaeology. The Southern Hebrids Mesolithic Project 1988-98*. Oxbow Books, Oxford, 507-512.

Schweingruber, F.H., 1990. *Mikroskopische Holz Anatomie. Formenspektren mitteleuropäischer Stamm- und Zweighölzer zur Bestimmung von rezentem und subfossilem Material*. 3. Aufl. Birmensdorf, Eidg. Forschungsanstalt für Wald, Schnee und Landschaft.

Simmons, I.G., 1975. Towards an ecology of Mesolithic man in the uplands of Great Britain. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 2(1), 1-15.

Simmons, I.G. & Innes, J.B., 1987. Mid-Holocene adaptations and later Mesolithic forest disturbance in northern England. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 14(4), 385-403.

Sollberger, J.B. & Hester, T.R., 1973. Some additional data on the thermal alteration of siliceous stone. *Bulletin of the Oklahoma Anthropological Society*, 21, 181-185.

Spek, T., Bisdorf, E.B.A. and Smeerdijk, D.G., 1999. Verdrongen dekzandgronden in Zuidelijk Flevoland (archeologische opgraving 'Hoge Vaart-A27'): een aanvullend bodemkundig en

palaeocologisch onderzoek naar de landschapsvormende processen tijdens de laatste fase van de: Rapport 472.2 55.

Spek, Th., Bisdom, E.B.A. & Van Smeerdijk, D.G., 2001. Deel 8. Bodemkunde en landschapsecologie II: aanvullend onderzoek naar landschapsvormende processen. In: Hogestijn, J.W.H. & Peeters, J.H.M. (eds.), *De mesolithische en vroeg-neolithische vindplaats Hoge Vaart-A27 (Flevoland)*, Rapportage Archeologische Monumentenzorg 79, Amersfoort, ROB.

Spikins, P., 1999. *Mesolithic northern England: environment, population and settlement*. Oxford: Archaeopress (British Archaeological Reports, British Series 283).

Spikins, P., 2000. *Mesolithic Northern England: Environment, Population and Settlement*. (BAR British Series 283) Oxford: Archaeopress.

Spikins, P., 2008. Mesolithic Europe: glimpses of another world. In: Bailey, G. & Spikins, P. (eds.), *Mesolithic Europe*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1-17.

Stahlschmidt, M.C., Miller, C.E., Ligouis, B., Goldberg, P., Berna, F., Urban, B. & Conard, N.J., 2015. The depositional environments of Schöningen 13 II-4 and their archaeological implications. *Journal of human evolution*, 89, 71-91.

Stahlschmidt, M.C., Miller, C.E., Ligouis, B., Hambach, U., Goldberg, P., Berna, F., Richter, D., Urban, B., Serangeli, J. & Conard, N.J., 2015. On the evidence for human use and control of fire at Schöningen. *Journal of Human Evolution*, 89, 181-201.

Stoops, G., 2003. Guidelines for analysis and description of soil and regolith thin sections. Soil Science Society of America Inc..

Talalay, L., Keller, D.R., Munson, P.J., 1984. Hickory nuts, walnuts, butternuts, and hazelnuts: observations and experiments relevant to their aboriginal exploitation in Eastern North America. In: Munson, P.J. (ed.), *Experiments and Observations on Aboriginal Wild Plant Food Utilization in Eastern North America*. Prehistory Research Series, vol. VI, 2. Indiana Historical Society, Indianapolis, 338-359

Tang, D., Yang, Q., Zhou, C., Kang, X., Liu, D. & Huang, W., 2001. Genetic relationships between swamp microenvironment and sulfur distribution of the Late Paleozoic coals in North China. *Sci. China D* 44, 555-565

Taylor, B., Milner, N., & Conneller, C., 2019. Excavations at Star Carr: past and present. In D. Groß, H. Lübke, J. Meadows, & D. Jantzen (eds.), *Working at the sharp end: from bone and antler to Early Mesolithic life in Northern Europe*. Kiel/Hamburg: Untersuchungen und Materialien zur Steinzeit in Schleswig-Holstein und im Ostseeraum 10.

Tolksdorf, J.F., Klasen, N. & Hilgers, A., 2013. The existence of open areas during the Mesolithic: evidence from aeolian sediments in the Elbe-Jeetzel area, northern Germany. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 40(6), 2813-2823.

Trigger, B.G., 1989, *A history of archaeological thought*. Cambridge University Press: Cambridge.

Turner, Nancy J., 2014, *Ancient Pathways, Ancestral Knowledge: Ethnobotany and Ecological Wisdom of Indigenous Peoples of Northwestern North America*. McGill-Queen's University Press.

Van Kappel, K. & Exaltus, R., 2012. Bijlage I: bodemmorfologisch onderzoek vindplaats 5. In: Hamburg, T., Müller, A. & Quadflieg, B. (eds.), *Mesolithisch Swifterbant. Mesolithisch gebruik*

van een duin ten zuiden van Swifterbant (8300–5000 v. Chr.). Een archeologische opgraving in het tracé van de N23, 447-492.

Van Kappel, K. & Exaltus, R., 2019. Bijlage III: Micromorfologisch onderzoek Grundlagen. In: Geerts, R.C.A, Müller, A., Niekus, M.J.L.Th. & Vermue, F.J., 2019. *Mesolithische kampen onder de oever van het Reevediep. Een archeologische opgraving van vindplaats 9 in het tracé van de hoogwatergeul in het Reevediep te Kampen*. ADC monografie 26, 341-349.

Van Rijn, P. & Kooistra, L.I., 2001. Deel 15 Hout en houtskool: het gebruik van hout als constructiemateriaal en brandstof. In: Hogestijn, J.W.H. & Peeters, J.H.M. (eds.), *De mesolithische en vroeg-neolithische vindplaats Hoge Vaart-A27 (Flevoland)*, Amersfoort, Rijksdienst voor het Oudheidkundig Bodemonderzoek (Rapportage Archeologische Monumentenzorg, 79).

Verlinde, A.D., & Newell, R.R.. 2006. *A multi-component complex of Mesolithic settlements with late Mesolithic grave pits at Mariënberg in Overijssel*. Amersfoort: Rijksdienst voor het Oudheidkundig Bodemonderzoek (Nederlandse Archeologische Rapporten 22).

Visser, D., Whitton, C., Brinkkemper, O. & Hogestijn, J.W.H., 2001. Deel 11 Archeobotanie: de analyse van botanische macroresten. In: Hogestijn, J.W.H. & Peeters, J.H.M. (eds.), *De mesolithische en vroeg-neolithische vindplaats Hoge Vaart-A27 (Flevoland)*, Amersfoort, Rijksdienst voor het Oudheidkundig Bodemonderzoek (Rapportage Archeologische Monumentenzorg, 79).

Vos, P. & S. de Vries 2013: 2^e generatie palaeogeografische kaarten van Nederland (versie 2.0). Deltares, Utrecht. Downloaded on [01-04-2019] from <www.archeologiein nederland.nl>.

Wadley, L., 2010. Compound-adhesive manufacture as a behavioral proxy for complex cognition in the Middle Stone Age. *Current Anthropology*, 51(S1), 111-119.

Wandsnider, L., 1997. The roasted and the boiled: food composition and heat treatment with special emphasis on pit-hearth cooking. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 16(1), 1-48.

Wansleben, M. & Laan, W., 2012. 4 Ruimtelijke analyse. In: Hamburg, T., Müller, A. & Quadflieg, B. (eds.), *Mesolithisch Swifterbant. Mesolithisch gebruik van een duin ten zuiden van Swifterbant (8300–5000 v. Chr.). Een archeologische opgraving in het tracé van de N23*, 85-112.

Warren, G., Davis, S., McClatchie, M. & Sands, R., 2014. The potential role of humans in structuring the wooded landscapes of Mesolithic Ireland: a review of data and discussion of approaches. *Vegetation history and archaeobotany*, 23(5), 629-646.

Wattez, J., Onfray, M. & Coussot, C., 2017. Géoarchéologie des fosses profondes mésolithiques: des aménagements pour quels usages? In: N. Achard-Corompt, E. Ghesquière & V. Riquier (eds.), *Creuser au Mésolithique / Digging in the Mesolithic: Actes de la séance de la Société préhistorique française de Châlons-en-Champagne (29-30 mars 2016). Séances de la Société préhistorique française*, vol. 12, Société Préhistorique Française, Paris, 87-98.

Weiner, S., 2010. *Microarchaeology: beyond the visible archaeological record*. Cambridge University Press.

Wit, M.J.M. de (MUG Ingenieursbureau), 2016. *Archeologisch proefsleuvenonderzoek op plangebied Molenakkers II, fasen 2 en 3 te Dalen, gemeente Coevorden (DR)*. (Mug-publicatie 2016-12)

Woelders, L., Bos, J.A., de Kort, J.W. & Hoek, W.Z., 2016. Early Holocene environmental change and the presence of Mesolithic people in the Tengelroyse Beek valley near Mildert, the Netherlands. *Vegetation history and archaeobotany*, 25(2), 177-189.

Woldring, H., Schepers, M., Mendelts, J. & Fens, R., 2012. 24 Camping and foraging in Boreal hazel woodland–The environmental impact of Mesolithic hunter-gatherers near Groningen, the Netherlands. In: Niekus, M.J.L.T., Barton, R.N.E., Street, M. & Terberger, T. (eds.), *A mind set on flint*, Groningen: Barkhuis Publishing, 381-392.

Woodman, P.C., 1985. *Excavations at Mount Sandel 1973-1981*, Belfast, Her Majesty's Stationary Office.

APPENDIX

DRONTEN

HAK-A-572

Dronten 1727-1 (1-15cm)

The groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains. A few small domains, some with rootlets in cross section. Common organic fraction including concentrations of humus, two larger (± 1 cm) charcoal fragments with sharp edges, several smaller (1-2mm) charcoal fragments and several similarly sized fragments of charred organic tissue, and very finely fragmented black (powdery) charred organic matter of which the concentration increases from 9cm downwards. The remaining organic fraction consists of a few small fragments of decaying organic tissue containing pyrite globules.

Dronten 1727-2 (16-30cm)

The groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Common organic fraction including two small (± 5 mm) charcoal fragments, one of which has a partially viscous (vesicular) structure that is black and opaque, a few rootlets and fragments of fresh plant tissues. An increase in powdered charcoal as well as small (< 1 mm) fragments of charcoal and charred organic material is seen further downwards. The bottom half of this section appears more homogenous, in contrast to the slightly more 'messy' appearance of the top.

Dronten 1727-3 (31-45cm)

The groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains, more loosely packed towards the bottom of the section. Abundant organic fraction ending halfway down the section, including one larger (± 2 cm) charcoal fragment and a number of smaller pieces (< 5 mm) with extremely sharp breaking edges, similarly sized charred fragments of charred organic tissue, two small (< 5 mm) charcoal fragments show a partially viscous (vesicular) structure that is opaque and black. Sporadic non-charred sclerotia.

One larger (± 2 cm) piece of charcoal
Number of smaller (< 5 mm) pieces of charcoal and similarly sized charred fragments of organic tissue. Two small fragments of charcoal show a partially viscous (vesicular) structure that is black and opaque. The bottom of the section is relatively clean, containing almost no charred remains of any size. Some medium to small domains with fresh and degraded plant tissues. Sporadic uncharred sclerotia.

prof. 51-I_b
12-27cm

Hoge Vaart 51-I-b (12-27cm)

Subangular unsorted quartz sand grains make up the groundmass. Common medium channels with fresh rootlets. Abundant organic fraction including (fragments of) sclerotia, plant tissues (brown and black brown concentrations of amorphous organic matter, tissue and punctuations), some fungal hyphae, charred organic remains and charcoal fragments. Humus coatings present in the bottom half of the section, alongside strongly degrading organic material.

96.044

Prof. 51-I-c

27-42cm

96.045

Hoge Vaart 51-I-c (27-42cm)

Subangular unsorted quartz sand grains make up the groundmass. Common narrow channels and some domains (with rootlets in cross section) in the top half of the section, few small domains in the bottom half. Common organic fraction including (fragments of) sclerotia throughout the entire section, plant tissues (brown concentrations of amorphous organic matter, orange-brown fresh rootlet tissue), charred organic remains and charcoal fragments (ranging in size from <1mm to 2 cm) with sharp edges. One larger (2 cm) charcoal fragment, of which the sides have a viscous (vesicular) structure and are black and opaque. One smaller fragment (± 2 mm) shows a similar structure. The larger charcoal fragments are mainly concentrated in the upper left corner and at the right side of the thin section. Burnt moder or humus (also as coatings) quite evenly dispersed in the top half of the section, and present as a circular concentration in the bottom right corner of the section.

Prof. 51-I-d
← top 34-42cm

96096

Hoge Vaart 51-I-d (34-42cm)

The mineral fraction of the groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Common medium domains in the right half, most with rootlets in cross section. Common organic fraction including some (fragments) of sclerotia, common small fragments of charred organic tissue and charcoal (up to 1mm) dotted throughout the entire section and a small (± 2 mm) fragment of charred organic tissue that shows a viscous (vesicular) structure and that is black and opaque. Partially charred humus or moder in the right two-thirds of the section (not very evenly dispersed), also as coatings.

Prof. 51-II-b

12-27cm

96.048

Hoge Vaart 51-II-b (12-27cm)

The mineral fraction of the groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Abundant medium channels and quite large voids in top half, some of which with fresh rootlets in cross section, one domain with strongly degrading organic material/plant tissue inside of fresh plant tissue. Few domains with rootlets in cross section in bottom half of the thin section. Remaining organic fraction including a number of sclerotia, small (<1mm) charcoal fragments and fragments of charred plant tissue, two small fragments (± 1 mm) of charred bark, a circular concentration of charred plant tissue in the bottom left corner of the section and common charred and uncharred moder or humus heterogeneously dispersed in voids between grains; all of which is prevalent in the bottom half of the section, much less so in the top half. Overall quite heterogeneous ('messy'), not a lot of proper coatings.

Prof. 51-II-c

-2½-12½cm

510-96

Hoge Vaart 51-II-c (2,5-12,5cm)

Transition from peat to sand.

Top 5 cm: The groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains, in combination with horizontally oriented orange, brown and black-brown partially amorphous organic matter (peat). Some fungal spores and hyphae.

Bottom: Subangular unsorted quartz sand grains make up the groundmass. Matrix has a very messy appearance. Common medium and small channels and domains, most of which contain rootlets. Common organic fraction, including fragments of plant tissues (brown, orange-brown), some small (<1mm) pieces of charcoal and charred organic material, one small (± 2 mm) piece of black and opaque charcoal with a viscous (vesicular) structure. The bottom of the section shows a slightly darker horizontal band with more degraded organic material, organic coatings and humus than the surrounding soil. Quite a large number of non-charred (fragments of) sclerotia.

Prof. 51-II-d

13 1/2 - 28 1/2 cm

96.050

Hoge Vaart 51-II-d (13,5-28,5cm)

The mineral fraction of the groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Common small channels and domains, most of which contain fresh rootlets in cross section. Abundant organic fraction, including plant tissues (brown and orange-brown fresh tissue, dark brown amorphous concentrations, humus formation in degrading tissue), a large number of sclerotia (some charred) and a few concentrations of fine amorphous black material that is dispersed between surrounding quartz grains. 8-9 cm wide horizontal dark band consisting of abundant fine fragmented charred organic tissue, one larger (1cm) fragment of charred bark and several more smaller fragments of charred bark, all quite rounded off at the edges. Two similar fragments are present at the very top and bottom of the section. Gypsum crystals present in this layer.

The bottom three cm under the dark band is much more clean, apart from the fragment of charred bark and light concentrations of charred organic tissue. Very sporadic pyrite globules within fresh plant tissue.

Prof 131-b

16-31cm

Hoge Vaart 131-b

The groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Few small domains, containing fresh rootlets in cross section. Abundant organic fraction including common charred moder or humus, some (fragments of) sclerotia and small charred organic fragments that are unevenly dispersed throughout the matrix; overall 'messy' heterogeneous impression. Partially charred brown charcoal fragments with sharp edges (N=10) and one very large (± 4 cm) piece of sharp fragmented charcoal of which the right half is very heavily degrading (possibly due to thin section production); the latter contains 'holes' consisting of clean quartz grains and structures black bands. Some iron oxide globules and gypsum crystals in the left part of the section; possibly a few vitrified pyrite globules (jarosite + gypsum) in this part of the section as well. A band with slight clay coatings 2-4 cm from top, and very light 'dusty' clay coatings with some iron oxide at the bottom of the section.

96.052

Prof. 131-c

0-15cm

96.053

Hoge Vaart 131-c

The mineral fraction of the groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Common medium channels and large domains, most of which containing rootlets and fresh plant tissues. Common organic fraction including abundant sclerotia (some of which are pretty large, ± 1 mm), plant tissues (brown and orange brown fresh tissue, amorphous orange brown concentrations), very finely fragmented charred plant tissue and small (<1 mm) charcoal fragments (heterogeneously dispersed throughout the entire section). Charred moder or humus (also as coatings) quite evenly dispersed throughout entire thin section.

Prof 131-d
13-28cm

96.054
150.96

Hoge Vaart 131-d

Subangular unsorted quartz sand grains make up the groundmass. Present small to large domains, most of which contain fresh rootlets in cross section. Abundant charred moder or humus (also as coatings) increasing in amount and thickness towards the bottom of the section. Remaining organic fraction includes some sclerotia in top half of the section, and some small (<0,5m) pieces of charcoal (edges rounded off; one containing iron oxide and pyrite globules in its cell matrix). Most charred organic fragments are very finely fragmented and/or heavily degraded.

Prof 131-e

12-27cm

Hoge Vaart 131-e

The groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Few medium channels and domains with fresh rootlets in cross section. Top 4 cm dark grey charred humus or moder, one elongated diagonal band that is slightly darker than the surrounding matrix as well, because of more charred material. Remaining organic fraction includes a few sclerotia, one small square charcoal fragment ($\pm 0,5$ cm) with sharp edges and one small fragment of charred black opaque organic tissue that shows a viscous (vesicular) structure. Overall impression of matrix is quite heterogeneous ('mucky').

96.055

Prof 131-f

0-15cm

Hoge Vaart 131-f

Subangular unsorted quartz sand grains make up the groundmass. Some small and large domains, few of which with rootlets and/or fresh plant tissue. Remaining organic fraction includes three small (<0,5cm) fragments of partially amorphous black charred organic tissue that have a viscous (vesicular) structure and common black very small charred fragments of organic tissue, present throughout entire section. Sporadic light charred coatings.

96.056

KAMPEN

22

Kampen 4065

The groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Few small voids, some rounded and some with fresh rootlets or (-fragments). Very few charred tissue fragments and some thin organic coatings in the top 1cm of the section. Small organic fraction in the bottom half of the section, consisting of thin organic (humus) coatings.

S26

Kampen 4066

Unsorted subangular quartz grains make up the groundmass. Few small channels and voids with some fresh rootlets in cross section. Common organic fraction including decaying plant tissues (brown and orange-brown, some with few fungal spores), some small charcoal fragments, small fragments of charred organic material. Some pyrite globules present in fresh plant tissue. Charred moder- or humus coatings are irregularly distributed throughout the section, being more concentrated in the top half of the section.

S26

Kampen 4062

The groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Common small channels with some small rootlets. Common charred organic fraction evenly distributed throughout section including (fragments of) sclerotia, small fragments of charcoal and charred organic matter (0,5-2mm). One larger charcoal fragment (>2cm) with small concentrations of FeO and decaying organic remains embedded in its matrix. The sides of the charcoal fragment have a viscous (vesicular) structure and are black and opaque. A second, much smaller, fragment shows similar characteristics. Charred humus or moder is evenly distributed throughout the section.

Kampen 4063

The groundmass consists of unsorted subangular quartz grains that are more tightly packed towards the bottom of the section. Common charred organic fraction (slightly increasing towards the bottom of the section) including decaying plant tissue with pyrite globules, common small (brown) charcoal fragments and a concentration of fine amorphous black organic material, dispersed in between the surrounding grains. Charred moder- or humus coatings are present throughout the entire section.

Kampen 4264

The mineral fraction of the groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. One small domain with fresh rootlet in cross section, containing pyrite globules. Common organic fraction including a few small charcoal particles (<1mm), few (partially charred) sclerotia, sporadic fungal spores and a few fragments of fresh plant tissue. Charred moder or humus is distributed throughout the entire section, slightly increasing in concentration towards the bottom half of the section. Charred moder or humus coatings present throughout entire section, coatings are also attached to fresh plant tissue. Some cracked quartz grains with very fine charred moder or humus dust embedded in cracks.

Kampen 4265

Unsorted subangular quartz grains make up the groundmass. Common medium vertical channels with rootlets and few larger domains containing quartz grains of a slightly smaller fraction than the surrounding matrix. These larger domains also contain concentrations of uncharred moder/humus. At the bottom of the section there is a small (<1mm) fragment of black opaque viscous (organic) material with a slightly vesicular structure.

Kampen 4266

The groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Common medium channels, some with rootlets. Common organic fraction including strongly decaying plant tissues (brown, orange brown), some associated with a concentration of pyrite framboids, a number of sclerotia, abundant amounts of dark moder and/or humus, (partially) charred organic tissue fragments (dark brown, black brown), a small (<1mm) fragment of charcoal and a concentration of fine amorphous black organic material, dispersed in between the surrounding grains.

Kampen 4267

Unsorted subangular quartz grains make up the groundmass. Common medium sized vertically oriented channels with rootlets, some of which contain concentrations of pyrite globules, and one slightly larger domain in the left of the section. Common organic fraction including sclerotia, plant tissue fragments (orange brown and brown) and small (<1mm) charred fragments of organic tissue. Even more finely fragmented charred organic material is dispersed throughout the entire thin section, increasing in amount towards the bottom. Plenty of humus coatings in the top half of the section, strongly decreasing towards the bottom.

Kampen 4268
 The groundmass is made up of unsorted subangular quartz grains. Two medium sized vertical channels with rootlets and a number of smaller domains, some with concentrations of pyrite globules. Abundant charred moder or humus, unevenly dispersed throughout the section, though present throughout the whole. Common organic fraction including a large number of (charred) sclerotia, some small (<1mm) fragments of charred organic material and a couple of charcoal fragments. Charred coatings present.

Kampen 4269
 Unsorted subangular quartz grains make up the groundmass. Few very small domains. Abundant organic fraction including a larger charcoal fragment (± 1 cm) in bottom left, a few smaller fragments of charcoal (<3mm) in top half of section, abundant small sclerotia distributed throughout entire section, and abundant charred organic particles (black). Charcoal fragments are significantly degrading. Charred moder or humus coatings present throughout entire section, but considerably more and thicker towards the bottom half of the section. Partially charred (brown) moder or humus present mainly in top half of section.

Kampen 4270

Unsorted subangular quartz grains make up the groundmass. Some small domains containing rootlets in cross-section. Abundant organic fraction, including small (<5mm) fragmented pieces of charcoal, some fresh plant tissue (brown, orange-brown) containing pyrite globules, and a concentration of fine amorphous black organic material, dispersed in between surrounding grains.

Abundant charred moder or humus, also as coatings, dispersed throughout the entire section though more prevalent towards the bottom. Sporadic small concentrations of iron oxide.

Kampen 4271

The groundmass is made up of subangular unsorted quartz grains. Some medium channels and domains, sporadically containing fresh rootlets in cross section. Organic fraction present, including few fragments of fungal tissue, small charred (black) organic fragments and fresh plant tissue containing pyrite globules. Charred organic fragments are mainly present in the top half of the section, though a small amount of punctuations is present at the bottom. Light charred moder or humus coatings evenly distributed throughout the top 3,5 cm of the section.

Kampen 4272

Unsorted subangular quartz grains make up the groundmass. Common narrow channels, sporadically containing fresh rootlets in cross section. Small organic fraction, including a few sclerotia and a few fragments of fresh plant tissue (orange-brown).

Kampen 4273

The groundmass is made up of subangular unsorted quartz grains, though grains are more tightly packed in and below a dark coloured band (around 4-5 cm from top section). Possibly some size sorting (smaller grains) within the darker coloured band. Few small domains (not containing any material). Present organic fraction including few decaying organic remains (brown, dark brown) and sporadic charred amorphous concentrations (black). Within the darker 'wavy' band dark charred fragments of organic material are unevenly dispersed. The band consists of common humus coatings, and also illuviated clay coatings with powdered charred organic remains. A small (<0,5cm) vertical band at the bottom of the thin section contains quite a few dark (dark brown) humus (organic) coatings as well.

Kampen 4274

The groundmass is made up of subangular unsorted quartz grains. Few small domains, sporadically containing fresh rootlets in cross section. Small organic fraction including a few small fragments of plant tissue and some very small black punctuations. Sporadic small concentrations of iron oxide, unevenly distributed throughout section.

Kampen 4275-B

The groundmass is made up of subangular unsorted quartz grains. Common medium channels and domains, decreasing in size towards the bottom of the section, some with rootlet tissue. Common organic fraction, including sclerotia concentrated around degrading plant tissue (brown, orange brown), degraded moder (?) and many fungal hyphae (**Top**) and thick humus coatings distributed evenly throughout the bottom part of the section.

Kampen 4275-M

Unsorted subangular quartz grains make up the groundmass. Narrow elongated channels and some small domains present throughout entire section, few of which contain rootlet tissue. Common organic fraction consisting of very fine amorphous organic material (brown), a small concentration of excrement (and moder-like material) and humus coatings that decrease in thickness towards the bottom of the section. Between 3 and 4 cm from the top of the section lays a band of sediment (ca. 7mm thick) that is significantly darker in colour than the surrounding groundmass, and which contains very thick humus coatings and small black, heterogeneously dispersed organic points. Sporadic pyrite globules.

Kampen 4275-O

The groundmass is made up of subangular unsorted quartz grains. Sporadic small domains with rootlets in cross-section, some very small domains (<1mm) with excrements. Organic fraction present, including a few sizeable (1-2mm) fragments of fresh plant tissue (light brown) and a few (decaying) sclerotia. Very light humus coatings present throughout the entire section, slightly increasing in thickness towards the bottom.

Kampen 4276-M

The groundmass is made up of subangular unsorted quartz grains. Sporadic domains with fresh rootlets in cross-section. Organic fraction present, including a few fragmented sclerotia and fragments of fresh plant tissue (light brown, orange). Some very light humus coatings unevenly distributed throughout the section.

Kampen 4276-B

Unsorted subangular quartz grains make up the groundmass. Sporadic very small domains containing rootlets (brown, orange brown) in cross section. Some very light organic coatings.

Kampen 4276-O

Unsorted subangular quartz grains make up the groundmass. One larger vertical domain with fresh plant tissue (rootlet) in cross section. Sporadic organic fraction including a few small fragments of fresh plant tissue.

